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Master's Thesis

Indirekte Suche eines minimalen Modells zerfallender Dunkler Materie

Indirect Detection of a Minimal Decaying Dark Matter Model

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Abstract

We derive lower limits on the lifetime of decaying dark matter in a minimal model with respect to trilinear R -parity violating decays into three quarks or two quarks and a lepton. To this end, we calculate the partial and differential decay rates of these decays at tree level. Furthermore, we base our lifetime analyses on the measurements of the antiproton flux by the PAMELA satellite, the diffusive gamma-ray flux measured by the Fermi-LAT research system and the upper limit on the antideuteron flux observed by the BESS experiment. Scanning a dark matter mass range from 10 GeV to 1 TeV we find lifetime limits that can be as high as $\sim 1 \cdot 10^{31}$ s and as low as $\sim 5 \cdot 10^{26}$ s in the antiproton channel. In addition, gamma-ray limits take values inside the range from $\sim 1 \cdot 10^{27}$ s to $\sim 1 \cdot 10^{28}$ s whereas the limits from antideuteron searches are below $\sim 1 \cdot 10^{26}$ s.

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1 Introduction

Our understanding of the universe is incomplete which manifests itself in the deficiencies of current physical theories like the standard model of particle physics or cosmology. Among these deficiencies stands out the puzzling problem of dark matter, though its existence is a well-approved building block of cosmological and particle physical theories. In fact, many strong evidences for the presence of dark matter were found in the decades after its first mentioning in the studies of Jeans (1922) and Zwicky (1933). However, each of these evidences is based on the gravitational interaction of dark matter with its surrounding. Thus, the only definite statement about its nature is the following: Dark matter must be massive and there must be much of it in the universe.

Of course, many solutions to this puzzle were proposed: On one side, some of them try avoiding to increase the population of the already existing particle zoo by altering the known laws of gravity or by postulating large amounts of very low-luminous and massive objects in the halo of galaxies. Nevertheless, experimental measurements indicate that these conjectures are either inconsistent or they do not account for all of the necessary amount of dark matter. On the other side, a particle physics solution to the problem seems to be the favored alternative since all astrophysical and cosmological constraints on the nature of dark matter can be resolved within particular models.

As a matter of fact, it is not even known whether dark matter is stable or unstable, where in the latter case it must be very long-lived such that, for instance, enough of it would be left since the Big Bang. From a cosmological point of view, there is no obstruction why unstable dark matter should not be realized in the universe and, furthermore, any model describing such a dark matter candidate has no need for a stabilizing symmetry. Hence, dark matter could interact with ordinary standard model matter directly as a singlet, although only gravitational interactions were ever observed.

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To broaden the understanding of dark matter, physicists have at hand three possibilities to detect its interactions apart from gravitational forces: the production of dark matter in collision events, the direct observation of interactions or the indirect observation of dark matter annihilations (for stable dark matter) or dark matter decays (for unstable dark matter). This latter main technique to explore the nature of dark matter is the so-called indirect detection which tries to identify the remnants of dark matter annihilations or decays within the cosmic rays penetrating the Earth's atmosphere. These processes yield rather model-dependent spectra of standard model particles and hence, a possibility to test and constrain different dark matter models arises. Furthermore, due to the increasing amount of data and precision of cosmic ray measurements via experiments like PAMELA [44] and AMS-02 [16] indirect detection is becoming a flourishing branch of dark matter research. This technique was further encouraged by an unexpected excess in the cosmic rays' positron to electron fraction being a possible imprint of a hypothetical dark matter component. The excess was first measured by the PAMELA collaboration [9] and later confirmed by independent research groups like the Fermi collaboration [6] or the AMS collaboration [5].

Indirect detection methods have been used to constrain various dark matter models. Among these models the possibility of decaying dark matter was studied in rather well-motivated cases like leptophilic decaying dark matter or gravitinos with R -parity breaking [22]. Nevertheless, unstable dark matter models can be constructed from a more general viewpoint. Introducing a minimal decaying dark matter model via a Majorana dark matter particle and a single heavy, colored or electroweakly charged scalar yields a viable theory that might be a low-energy limit of a more complex model like the R -parity violating MSSM [23].

In this thesis, we want to analyze the phenomenological impacts of this minimal model on the antiproton, gamma-ray and antideuteron cosmic rays by comparing the expected dark matter fluxes to recent cosmic ray measurements of the PAMELA satellite [12], the Fermi-LAT collaboration [7] and the BESS balloon-borne experiment [72]. This way we will work out further constraints on the cosmological acceptable lifetimes of dark matter particles in a minimal model context assuming dark matter masses in a range from 10 GeV to 1 TeV.

In this thesis we proceed as follows: In chapter 2 we give a review on the current status of dark matter research. To this end, we introduce basic cosmological concepts mandatory to explain the thermal history of dark matter. Moreover, we provide

several evidences for the existence of dark matter and state viable theories describing dark matter candidates. We conclude with a discussion of the distribution of dark matter in galaxies. The subsequent chapter 3 explores the composition of cosmic rays and investigates whether the particle fluxes of dark matter annihilations or decays can leave significant imprints in these channels. Furthermore, we present several tools to obtain theoretical predictions of cosmic ray fluxes from astrophysical processes and putative dark matter interactions. In the following, chapter 4 introduces the minimal decaying dark matter model. Having established its content, we proceed by calculating partial and differential decay widths of several trilinear R -parity violating decay modes of the dark matter candidate and end by providing an overview of the mechanisms accounting for the relic density of this specific dark matter particle. In chapter 5 we present the main results of our study: We first illustrate our approach to simulate the minimal model's dark matter decays with MADGRAPH5 and PYTHIA8 and to generate the decay spectra of several particles after the hadronization of the daughter particles. Subsequently, we discuss the derived decay spectra by drawing comparisons to similar spectra available in the literature and, finally, we state lower bounds on the dark matter lifetime obtained from indirect searches in the gamma-ray, antiproton and antideuteron channel of cosmic rays. We conclude and summarize this thesis in chapter 6. Moreover, we give an outlook to further studies and unresolved questions of indirect searches for dark matter.

The appendix encompasses supplementary material to the thesis: App. A fixes the used unit system and lists the values of the appearing physical constants. App. B sets the conventions of special relativity and provides an overview of useful formulæ in connection with the calculation of squared matrix elements from Feynman diagrams. In the following App. C we state the Feynman rules of the minimal model and derive the most important kinematical relations in connection with three-body decays. Eventually, App. D lists all scripts that were applied in the course of the thesis.

2 The Nature of Dark Matter

The postulate of the presence of some invisible but gravitationally interacting matter, the so-called dark matter, took a long time to become the well-established fact among the physical community which it currently is. In this chapter we will, thus, provide a short introduction to cosmological key concepts and the thermal production of dark matter in the early universe. Subsequently, we give a review on selected observations in the past supporting the existence of dark matter. Moreover, we shortly state and explain the most common models appearing in the contemporary literature dealing with dark matter. Finally, we conclude the chapter by giving an overview of frequently-used dark matter density profiles which describe the distribution of dark matter inside galaxies and which will be part of later studies in this thesis.

2.1 Foundations of Cosmology

Before we investigate the nature of dark matter, we want to give a short and concise overview of the most important ingredients of cosmological models. These foundations we will need to present a simplified reasoning that answers the question how a hypothetical amount of dark matter could be produced in the early era of the universe.

2.1.1 The Dynamics of the Universe

The starting point of contemporary cosmology is the assumption of the *Big Bang* scenario at the beginning of the universe, i.e., the universe evolved from a state where all energy was focused in one point to its present form. The dynamics of this evolution is given by the Einstein equations which almost follow directly from first principles by assuming that: First, they are invariant under all possible coordinate transformations, second, the equations result in Newton's law of gravity if the

weak field approximation is used and third, the equations are second order partial differential equations which are linear in all second derivatives. The result reads

$$R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2}Rg_{\mu\nu} = 8\pi GT_{\mu\nu} + \Lambda g_{\mu\nu}, \quad (2.1.1)$$

where R denotes the Ricci scalar which is obtained from the Ricci tensor $R_{\mu\nu}$ by contracting with the metric of space-time $g_{\mu\nu}$. The Ricci tensor itself is derived by contractions from the Riemann curvature tensor of space-time. The tensor $T_{\mu\nu}$ is the energy-momentum tensor of a specific type of matter and Λ is usually referred to as the cosmological constant. Ignoring the cosmological constant for a moment, this system of equations contains the main statement of Einstein's general relativity, namely that the geometry of the universe given on the left-hand side of Eq. 2.1.1 is determined by its energy content on the right-hand side.

The cosmological constant can be seen as an ingredient that could have been written on both sides of the Einstein equations because it is neither describing the energy of a particular kind of matter nor is it a simple feature of the universe's geometry. It rather refers to the energy of space-time itself and is, in this sense, a "vacuum energy" inducing gravitational forces even in the absence of all matter.

The dynamics of the universe is then a specific solution to the Einstein equations that is derived by inserting two assumptions about its overall shape: The universe we observe is *homogeneous* and *isotropic* where the first assumption is supported by direct evidences coming from galaxy surveys indicating a homogeneous distribution of objects on scales larger than ~ 100 Mpc [106]. Translating these assumptions to the general metric of space-time, we find

$$g_{\mu\nu}dx^\mu dx^\nu = ds^2 = dt^2 - a(t)^2 \left[\frac{dr^2}{1 - kr^2} + r^2 (d\theta^2 + \sin^2\theta d\varphi^2) \right], \quad (2.1.2)$$

with $a(t)$ being the so-called scale factor and k characterizes the spatial geometry of the universe while being restricted to three distinct values, namely

$$k = \begin{cases} -1 & , \text{open geometry} \\ 0 & , \text{flat geometry} \\ 1 & , \text{closed geometry} \end{cases} .$$

Inserting the energy-momentum tensor $T^\mu_\nu = \text{diag}(\rho_{\text{tot}}, -p, -p, -p)$ of a perfect fluid in thermodynamic equilibrium at rest (which is a good approximation on large scales) into the Einstein equations with the metric of Eq. 2.1.2, yields the Friedmann equations that govern the evolution of the universe. The quantities inside the energy-momentum tensor are ρ_{tot} which denotes the total average energy density of the universe including all species of energy (matter, radiation and vacuum energy) and the isotropic pressure p due to the matter presence. The equation of state, i.e. $p_i = w_i \rho_i$, depends on the properties of matter species i and must be specified when necessary. The usual matter contributions to the universe possess the following values: Radiation and relativistic particles are assigned $w_r = 1/3$, pressureless matter and dust (e.g. nonrelativistic particles) have $w_m = 0$ and the vacuum energy is assigned a negative pressure via $w_\Lambda = -1$.

One component of this set of equations reads

$$\left(\frac{\dot{a}(t)}{a(t)}\right)^2 + \frac{k}{a(t)^2} = \frac{8\pi G}{3} \rho_{\text{tot}}, \quad (2.1.3)$$

where the Hubble parameter $H(t) = \dot{a}(t)/a(t)$, describing the expansion rate of the universe, is often used as an abbreviation. Eq. 2.1.3 can be interpreted in another way, by defining the critical energy density

$$\rho_{\text{crit}} = \frac{3H^2}{8\pi G},$$

which yields information about the geometry of space since for $k = 0$, i.e. a flat Minkowskian universe, $\rho_{\text{tot}} = \rho_{\text{crit}}$. Introducing the quantity $\Omega_i = \rho_i/\rho_{\text{crit}}$ which measures the ratio of the energy density of a specific species of matter and the critical density, we find the cosmological parameter

$$\Omega_{\text{tot}} =: \Omega = \sum_i \Omega_i = \sum_i \frac{\rho_i}{\rho_{\text{crit}}} = \frac{\rho_{\text{tot}}}{\rho_{\text{crit}}}$$

and may rewrite Eq. 2.1.3 in a concise way

$$\Omega - 1 = \frac{k}{H(t)^2 a(t)^2},$$

where the relation between the cosmological parameter Ω and the geometry of the universe becomes more evident.

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The Friedmann equations describe an expansion of the observable universe with increasing time which is reflected by photons through a redshift z of their wavelength. This redshift parameter is the fractional difference between the observed wavelength λ_{obs} of a photon emitted at a time t_{em} with wavelength λ_{em} inside a distant galaxy

$$z = \frac{\lambda_{\text{obs}} - \lambda_{\text{em}}}{\lambda_{\text{em}}} = \frac{a_0}{a(t_{\text{em}})} - 1, \quad (2.1.4)$$

where a_0 refers to the present value of scale factor. In other words, the light detected today originates from an earlier time t_{em} which is due to Eq. 2.1.4 in one-to-one correspondence with a specific value of the redshift parameter z and can therefore be equally used as a measure of time. Using the Friedmann equations again, yields the redshift dependence of the energy density species which subsequently leads to a cosmological sum rule

$$1 = \frac{H_0^2}{H(z)^2} \left[\Omega_r (1+z)^4 + \Omega_m (1+z)^3 + \Omega_\Lambda - \frac{k}{a_0^2 H_0^2} (1+z)^2 \right], \quad (2.1.5)$$

where $H_0 = 100h \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1} = (67.31 \pm 0.96) \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$ with $h \simeq 0.67$ denotes the present-day value of the Hubble parameter [51].

2.1.2 Thermal Production of Dark Matter in the Early Universe

Consider a relativistic and stable (or very long-lived) thermal dark matter particle χ being in thermal equilibrium with radiation and ordinary matter in the early universe. The relic density of this particle can easily be understood by a straightforward reasoning: As long as the temperature of the universe was larger than the particle's mass m_χ , the number of particles χ in this thermal equilibrium was stabilized by annihilations with its antiparticle into lighter particles $\chi\bar{\chi} \rightarrow \bar{l}l$ and the reversed process $\bar{l}l \rightarrow \chi\bar{\chi}$. Furthermore, scatterings like $\chi l \leftrightarrow \chi l$ guaranteed an energy exchange between ordinary matter and radiation such that the temperature of the dark matter was that of its surrounding. Usually, dark matter is assumed to be a Majorana particle, i.e. it is its own antiparticle. With increasing time the universe cooled down until its temperature fell below the mass of the dark matter particle. At this point the equilibrium abundance decreased exponentially as long as the rate of the dark matter pair-annihilation was smaller than the expansion rate H of the

universe. In this situation the process that maintained the equilibrium froze out and a cosmological relic abundance froze in [96].

This rather qualitative argument can be made quantitative by the means of the Boltzmann equation

$$\hat{L}[f] = \hat{C}[f],$$

where \hat{L} denotes the Liouville and \hat{C} denotes the collision operator that describe the interactions of the considered particles species and that act on its phase space distribution $f(x, p)$. Moreover, this distribution will either be the usual Einstein-Bose or Fermi-Dirac distribution depending on the spin of the dark matter particle. Using this underlying distribution we can express the number density n_χ^{eq} of the particle in thermal equilibrium as

$$n_\chi^{\text{eq}} = \frac{g}{(2\pi)^3} \int f(x, p) d^3p$$

which implies that for temperatures $T \gg m_\chi$ the number density behaves like $n_\chi^{\text{eq}} \sim T^3$, i.e. there are approximately as many dark matter particles as photons and for $T \ll m_\chi$ it shows an exponential Boltzmann suppression according to

$$n_\chi^{\text{eq}} \simeq g \left(\frac{m_\chi T}{2\pi} \right)^{3/2} e^{-\frac{m_\chi}{T}},$$

where g always refers to the particle's number of internal degrees of freedom. As mentioned in the simple reasoning beforehand, if the dark matter particle remained in thermal equilibrium because the expansion rate of the universe increased quite slowly then there would be nearly no dark matter in the present universe due to this exponential suppression.

After expanding such that the universe's temperature dropped below the dark matter's mass, also the thermally averaged annihilation rate per particle, $\Gamma = \langle \sigma_{\text{ann}} v \rangle n_\chi$, of χ decreases, where $\langle \sigma_{\text{ann}} v \rangle$ denotes the thermally averaged annihilation cross-section into lighter particles and v the relative velocity. Hence, the interaction rate of these equilibrium annihilations shrunk and at some point the density of the dark matter became so diluted by the universe's expansion that annihilation was not effective anymore. In return, this also implied that any creation via the reversed process also stopped and therefore the total number of dark matter particles froze out. This is the so-called chemical freeze-out which is followed at some later time

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by the kinetic freeze-out referring to the moment where also scattering processes became inefficient such that the dark matter thermally decoupled from the rest of the universe. The chemical freeze-out is supposed to have taken place when $\Gamma \leq H$, i.e. the annihilation rate has dropped below the expansion rate of the universe.

In fact, after some manipulations the Boltzmann equation can be expressed as a differential equation that governs the time evolution of the number density $n_\chi(t)$ of the dark matter particle [100]:

$$\frac{dn_\chi}{dt} + 3Hn_\chi = -\langle\sigma_{\text{ann}}v\rangle \left[n_\chi^2 - (n_\chi^{\text{eq}})^2 \right]. \quad (2.1.6)$$

Eq. 2.1.6 is usually rewritten in terms of new variables

$$Y := \frac{n_\chi}{s}, \quad Y^{\text{eq}} := \frac{n_\chi^{\text{eq}}}{s} \quad \text{and} \quad x := \frac{m_\chi}{T},$$

where $s = 2\pi^2 g_\star T^3/45$ denotes the entropy density of the universe with g_\star relativistic degrees of freedom (that depend on the universe's temperature T). The resulting equation [100]

$$\frac{dY}{dx} = -\frac{\langle\sigma_{\text{ann}}v\rangle s}{Hx} \left[Y^2 - (Y^{\text{eq}})^2 \right]$$

cannot be solved in terms of analytic functions and must be treated numerically. There are, nevertheless, many assumptions and approximations at hand which lead to rough estimates of the expected relic abundances of the dark matter particles. An explicit treatment of these simplifications can be found in [37, 96, 100] which eventually yields

$$\Omega_\chi h^2 = \frac{m_\chi n_\chi}{\rho_{\text{crit}}} \simeq \left(\frac{3 \cdot 10^{-27} \text{ cm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}}{\langle\sigma_{\text{ann}}v\rangle} \right).$$

The numerical solution of the Boltzmann equation is depicted in Fig. 2.1.1. Both the crude estimate and the numerical solution provide us with one striking feature: Assuming an annihilation cross-section on the scale of weak interactions, we receive a relic abundance of dark matter that is in agreement with the measurements of the dark matter content of the universe although the derivation of the relic abundance involves only cosmological arguments. This coincidence is sometimes referred to as the ‘‘WIMP-miracle’’.

This production mechanism accounts for the relic density of relativistic dark matter candidates which are in equilibrium during the early universe. However, we later

Figure 2.1.1: Numerical solution of the Boltzmann equation in terms of the comoving number density. The dashed curves portray the expected relic abundances after freeze-out whereas the solid line displays the number density in equilibrium. The solutions reveal that for increasing thermally averaged cross-section of annihilations $\langle\sigma_{\text{ann}}v\rangle$ the relic abundance drops because the particles tend to exit the equilibrium at later times. Adjusted picture of [100].

introduce the dark matter particle of our minimal decaying dark matter model. The couplings of this particle to radiation and ordinary matter are suppressed to an extent that it is out-of-equilibrium even though the temperature of the universe is larger than dark matter's mass. We will describe in Sec. 4.3 the freeze-in and SuperWIMP production mechanisms which can be applied to these kinds of dark matter particles in order to generate the dark matter relic density we observe today.

2.2 Why should there be Dark Matter?

The first evidences of dark matter appeared in the field of astronomy most probably because the motion of celestial bodies possesses a remarkable feature: Two objects mutually interact gravitationally. Even if one of them does not emit any photons, and is hence invisible, it exerts a force on the other particle which can be seen as a test particle inside the invisible object's force field. Thus, non-luminous bodies can be detected by their gravitational influence on their surrounding. In this light,

the question arises whether the visible amount of matter suffices to account for all observed celestial motion within the universe.

2.2.1 The First Evidences

Presumably the first person noticing the existence of dark matter was the British astronomer James Jeans in 1922 [64]. Pursuing the aim of determining the dynamical density of matter in the vicinity of the Sun, he analyzed the vertical oscillation of stars and interstellar gas around the galactic plane. Surprisingly, these motions could not entirely be explained by the available visible matter. He argued that there must exist two dark stars for every bright star [93]. These observations and calculation were redone several times throughout the past century leading to numerous validations of Jeans' results [29, 110].

A decade later in 1933 Fritz Zwicky examined the redshifts of galaxies inside the Coma galaxy cluster noticing that the constituent galaxies possess much larger velocities compared to the mean velocity of the whole cluster than what can be expected from the visible total mass of the cluster, i.e. the Coma cluster could not exist at all if there were not any additional invisible matter keeping the galaxies together. He claimed the dark mass component to be ten times the visible mass [121]. Modern methods of mass determination via gravitational lensing, which will be explained later on, verified the early estimates of Zwicky [101]. However, it should be noted that these evidences did not receive much attention from the scientific community.

2.2.2 Rotation Curves of Galaxies

Another unexpected mass deficiency was revealed while studying the rotation of spiral galaxies. Within these galaxies a theoretical prediction of the behavior of their angular velocity ω with increasing radius r can be obtained using Newton's law of gravity: Far from the galactic center its gravitational potential cannot be distinguished from the one of a point mass M at the center. Neglecting all other forces, the centrifugal force of an object with mass m orbiting around the center at a distance r and the gravitational attraction towards it must be equal: $G\frac{Mm}{r^2} = \frac{m\omega^2}{r}$, which implies $\omega \propto r^{-\frac{1}{2}}$. In other words, one would expect the outer regions of spiral galaxies to possess a lower angular velocity than the inner regions. However, the astronomers Babcock (1939) and Oort (1940) observed the opposite, the outer

2.2 Why should there be Dark Matter?

Figure 2.2.1: Rotation curve of the galaxy M31 found by combining two independent measurements using the optical spectrum (filled triangles) and the hydrogen’s 21 cm spectral line respectively as given in [114]. The surface density and the cumulative mass were then derived from these data sets.

regions showed a large excess in their angular velocity [26, 109]. The subject of Babcock’s studies was the Andromeda galaxy M31 whose rotation curve received much attention in the following decades. The result of Roberts and Whitehurst in Fig. 2.2.1 portrays remarkable features. On one side, with increasing radius it seems that the angular velocity is also increasing first and at some radius it is staying constant. On the other side, the cumulative mass inside the galaxy derived directly from the rotation curve must also grow monotonically with the radius. But therein lies the problem, the amount of visible mass contained in the outer regions of spiral galaxies cannot account for these observations. Several scenarios were proposed to solve this issue:

- A population of invisible objects distributed over the whole galaxy could accumulate enough mass.
- The circular orbits of galactic objects are being distorted by yet unknown sources.
- General relativity and, in particular, Newtonian gravity do not describe the observations properly because these theories are incomplete and they have to be modified. One example of such modifications is the so-called Modified Newtonian Dynamics, or short MOND [105].

In fact, either assuming an invisible mass contribution due to dark matter or altering the existing laws of gravity leads to reasonable predictions of the measured rotation

curves. But eventually, the first explanation gathered more supporters and rotation curves of spiral galaxies became a major evidence of dark matter.

2.2.3 Gravitational Lensing and the Bullet Cluster

Large invisible amounts of matter can be revealed because these clusters will bend and distort the light emitted from stellar objects in their background on the way towards an observer according to Einstein's laws of general relativity. In principle, they act analogously to ordinary optical lenses although being based on gravitational interactions. Hence, they are called gravitational lenses and it is possible to infer the mass distribution inside a certain part of the observable universe by analyzing the degree of light bending through this so-called gravitational lensing. The universe provides us with many sources where gravitational lensing can be studied and several of these sources include hints on the existence of dark matter like the merger of two galaxy groups in the Ursa Major system called Cheshire Cat group in Fig. 2.2.2.

Figure 2.2.2: Optical and X-ray image of the Cheshire Cat galaxy group as observed by the Hubble and Chandra space telescopes. Around the two bright elliptical galaxies in the middle of the picture several arcs of lensed distant background galaxies are visible [3].

The most prominent feature of this merger are the two elliptical galaxies which emit most of their radiation in the pink-coded X-ray spectrum. In their vicinity four arcs of stellar objects appear which are produced by gravitational lensing of background galaxies. According to [92] these arcs should have been closer to the elliptical galaxies if one wanted to explain this lens only via the visible mass of the merger. In fact, there must be an additional mass component invisible to the

space telescopes Hubble and Chandra to account for this configuration if the dark matter hypothesis is assumed to be true. Nonetheless, since the putative dark matter and the luminous matter component display a spatial overlap, an explanation by complementary theories such as MOND cannot be excluded.

The results of the observation and study of the object 1E 0657–558 (“Bullet Cluster”), a merger of two galaxy clusters, are claimed to be one of the most striking evidences of the existence of dark matter. Its immense value for dark matter searches is based on the spatial segregation of visible and hypothetic invisible contributions. Fig. 2.2.3 yields a composite image of this cluster by joining information about its optical and X-ray spectrum.

Figure 2.2.3: Composite image of the object 1E 0657–558 (“Bullet Cluster”) portraying the cluster’s galaxies in the optical range and its two clouds of X-ray emitting hot gas in red. The hypothesized dark matter contribution was calculated by the gravitational lensing effects on background galaxies and it is shown in the blue regions [1].

The color code of this figure is to be interpreted as follows: There are three types of interacting objects during the merging of two clusters. The stellar components of the merger are shown in their optical spectrum and were not much affected by mutual gravitational interactions as they act as collisionless particles. The red regions of hot gas were inferred from the merger’s X-ray spectrum and account for the majority of visible matter inside this object. As gaseous matter electromagnetically interacted during the merging, it was slowed down to a higher extent than the stellar component causing their spatial decoupling as depicted in the photograph of the bullet cluster. Nevertheless, by applying gravitational lensing to this merger, the authors of [49] found the main part of its mass being distributed according to the blue regions in

Fig. 2.2.3. Furthermore, they state with a statistical significance of 8σ that any modified law of gravity cannot fully explain such an observation because, e.g. in the MOND scenario, one would expect gravitational lensing to be strongest in the vicinity of the hot plasma. Thus, the computed mass discrepancy must be due to the presence of dark matter in the blue regions which is moreover supported by its spatial distance to the merger's plasma since dark matter is supposed to interact very weakly with ordinary matter.

2.2.4 Cosmological Evidences through the CMB

The picture about the presence of dark matter is completed by adding the information we can infer from the measurements of the *Cosmic Microwave Background* (CMB). The CMB is a microwave radiation that, on one hand, resembles a nearly perfect blackbody spectrum with a temperature of $T = 2.725$ K [34] and, on the other hand, it is almost isotropic which is in agreement with the assumption of an isotropic universe. In fact, the CMB is a remnant radiation that shows the universe at a particular moment in its evolution approximately 380.000 years after the Big Bang [34] and therefore contains many information about the universe's shape at that time. To be more precise, at about 380.000 years after the Big Bang all baryonic matter had already formed and due to the universe's temperature it existed in the form of ionized plasma. Thus, many freely moving charged particles were available on which photons could scatter and any atomic state was directly ionized by highly energetic photons. Therefore the universe was nearly opaque to radiation which means that no telescope can ever look behind this epoch in the history of the universe. However, the expansion of the universe led eventually to further cooling and at about 3700 K electrons and nuclei recombined, i.e. they were able to form stable atoms such that radiation could move freely. This moment, where the radiation decoupled from matter, is called the last scattering surface and the CMB is its present form after further expansion [106].

The large-scale isotropy of the CMB features, however, very small anisotropies of the order $\delta T/T \sim 10^{-5} - 10^{-4}$ which were discovered and investigated by several satellite missions like the COBE, WMAP or Planck satellite. These anisotropies encode information about various cosmological parameters and the structure of the universe at the time of recombination. The usual approach to extract these properties is to

Figure 2.2.4: Temperature power spectrum of the CMB as measured by the Planck satellite and published in [8]. The error bars of the data points are due to cosmic variance whereas the green-shaded region is referring to the variance of the best-fit curve given in green that was obtained using the six-parameter Λ CDM model. Note that the horizontal axis is logarithmic up to ~ 50 and linear afterwards and the vertical axis is giving the value of $l(l+1)C_l/2\pi$ in units of μK^2 .

decompose the measured CMB into spherical harmonics $Y_{lm}(\vartheta, \varphi)$ according to

$$\frac{\delta T}{T}(\vartheta, \varphi) = \sum_{l=2}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-l}^l a_{lm} Y_{lm}(\vartheta, \varphi)$$

and to analyze the power spectrum $l(l+1)C_l/2\pi$ as a function of the multipole moment l , where

$$C_l := \langle |a_{lm}|^2 \rangle = \frac{1}{2l+1} \sum_{m=-l}^l |a_{lm}|^2$$

receives its main contribution from fluctuations on angular scales of $\vartheta \propto \pi/l$.

The extracted power spectrum, which is depicted in Fig. 2.2.4 and taken from the Planck release of 2013, features multiple peaks where, for instance, the position of the first peak yields the geometry of space. The measurements by the WMAP satellite give rise to a value of [34]

$$\Omega_{\text{tot}} = 1.02 \pm 0.02$$

which indicates a flat universe according to Eq. 2.1.5 and is confirmed by the most recent measurements of the Planck mission [51].

A species of dark matter that had already decoupled from the thermal equilibrium at the time of recombination, so-called cold dark matter, would have left imprints of its presence as fluctuations in the CMB: During the radiation-dominated epoch of the universe free streaming of particles, i.e. traveling at relativistic velocities in random directions, made structure formation impossible. However, when matter density and radiation density became equal as the universe cooled, this free streaming was reduced such that baryonic matter was able to accumulated into gravitational wells produced by anisotropies of the hypothetic dark matter density. The regions of higher baryonic density led then to the structure formation in the universe and left imprints on the CMB. Without such a species of dark matter, any small fluctuations of matter density would get washed out by the interactions with radiation.

In general, the parameters of a particular cosmological model can be fitted to the shape of the power spectrum. The model best-fitting the CMB data is the Λ CDM model of cosmology that describes a flat universe dominated by the cosmological constant Λ and cold dark matter (CDM) which is explained in the subsequent chapter. The Planck data point to the following energy decomposition of the universe [8]:

$$\begin{aligned}\Omega_\Lambda &= 0.686 \pm 0.020 \\ \Omega_b h^2 &= 0.02207 \pm 0.00033 \\ \Omega_c h^2 &= 0.1196 \pm 0.0031.\end{aligned}$$

In fact, the Planck satellite revealed that the sum of dark energy Ω_Λ of about 69% and baryonic density Ω_b of about 5% cannot account for the total energy density of the universe which is restored in the Λ CDM model by adding about 26.5% of cold dark matter Ω_c . Apart from all explicit cosmological models, it seems that there is not enough energy in the universe without an additional dark component.

2.3 Review on Dark Matter Models

Almost one century passed since the first evidences of dark matter came to light. Within this century the hypothesis of the existence of invisible matter inside the

universe gathered more and more supporters. However, the rising number of scientists dealing with this topic increased the number of proposed models that gave an explicit answer to the question what dark matter actually is composed of. In the following, we provide a rather incomplete list of proposed explanations for the observed dark matter which, in parts, are still viable models used in recent research.

2.3.1 Baryonic Dark Matter

Thinking about dark matter as a form of usual baryonic matter seemed natural in the early stages of its exploration. However, there are two main reasons why baryonic dark matter cannot provide all of the observed dark matter: First, most historical conjectures about the nature of baryonic dark matter were easily ruled out by observations, for instance: Greater amounts of interstellar dust would have revealed themselves by extinction of light emitted by background sources and nearby stars whereas large gas clouds would have caused absorption lines in the spectra of background objects.

Second, constraints from the Primordial Nucleosynthesis disfavor large amounts of baryonic dark matter. Nucleosynthesis describes the generation of light elements in the first minutes after the Big Bang and can be understood merely in terms of standard model physics. Hence, it yields reliable predictions of quantities in the early universe without the need for any cosmological model building. The results of Primordial Nucleosynthesis are in agreement with astrophysical observations and they constrain the total amount of baryonic matter to be not larger than $\sim 4\%$ of the critical cosmological density ρ_{crit} whereas the amount of dark matter lies inside a range from 20% to 30% of the critical density [64].

Nevertheless, there might exist a small fraction of dark matter that can be attributed to baryonic matter. A certain class of objects, called *Massive Compact Halo Objects* (MACHOs), contributes to the invisible matter in the universe. This class includes any compact, massive object that has a very small luminosity such that it escapes usual detection devices. On galactic scales the most promising candidates are remnants of dead stars, like black holes, neutron stars and white dwarfs, or objects that did not accumulate enough mass to start nuclear fusion processes of hydrogen in their core, like brown dwarfs and Jupiter-like planets. Reaching the scale of galaxy clusters, very low-luminous galaxies are viable MACHOs. In fact, although being nearly invisible to any telescopes, their gravitational interaction can be detected

using gravitational lensing methods. However, the galactic dark matter halo cannot be entirely made of MACHOs; recent observations rather suggest that at most one-third of the invisible matter originates from massive low-luminosity objects [96].

2.3.2 Nonbaryonic Dark Matter

This category mostly consists of particle-like dark matter candidates that are neutral, in order to avoid electromagnetic interactions spoiling the invisibility, and very weakly interacting. One important classification of nonbaryonic dark matter is into hot and cold dark matter. These terms refer to the speed of the dark matter at the time of galaxy formation in the beginning of the universe: Hot dark matter moved with relativistic velocities whereas cold dark matter was only moving nonrelativistically. Thus, both categories had different impacts on the structure formation because hot dark matter could not have clustered in galaxies unless it cooled to nonrelativistic speeds. Examining the galactic structure formation process might yield new insights to the question whether most of the nonbaryonic dark matter is cold or hot.

Hot nonbaryonic dark matter The most promising candidate inside this class is a light neutrino with a mass below 100 eV because, assuming the neutrino to be a Majorana fermion, it would reproduce the measured relic density of dark matter in the universe [96]. It should be noted that the three standard model neutrino generations only provide a tiny fraction of the observed dark matter density and candidates like sterile neutrinos carrying no standard model charges are much more viable. Nevertheless, since hot dark matter began to cluster after galaxy structure formation had started, simulations of these processes indicated that a universe dominated by hot dark matter would not look like the observed universe [30]. In fact, adding topological defects to the simulations improves the results but there remain problems considering, for instance, the accumulation of hot dark matter in dwarf galaxies [77]. These issues support the idea that the majority of dark matter in the universe is not made out of hot dark matter.

Cold nonbaryonic dark matter These dark matter candidates mostly encompass particle extensions of the standard model where the majority of contemporary literature focuses on two specific cases, axions and *Weakly Interacting Massive Particles* (WIMPs).

Axions were introduced in QCD as a solution to its strong-CP problem invoking the Nambu-Goldstone theorem. Later on it was recognized that under certain assumptions the axion becomes a viable dark matter candidate whose mass is constrained by astrophysical arguments and laboratory experiments to be $\lesssim 0.01$ eV [37]. Experimental efforts are made in order to directly detect a resonant axion-to-photon conversion inside magnetic fields proving the existence of this type of cold dark matter.

However, WIMPs are up to now considered to be the best explanation of the nature of dark matter, since the WIMP production in the early universe perfectly coincides with the observed structure formation after the Big Bang. WIMPs are usually introduced as stable extensions of the electroweak sector of the standard model which includes the introduction of an additional stabilizing symmetry in the theory. There are various examples of WIMP candidates, for example, fourth-generation Dirac or Majorana neutrinos, the neutralino as the lightest supersymmetric particle of a supersymmetric extension of the standard model, the axino as superpartner of the axion or the gravitino being the superpartner of the graviton inside the theory of supergravity. Any of these candidates is likely to have a mass between 10 GeV to a few TeV and to show interactions with ordinary matter which resemble weak interactions [96].

2.4 The Distribution of Dark Matter inside of Galaxies

An essential step in this thesis is the calculation of cosmic ray fluxes due to dark matter decays. The dominant part of these decays are assumed to have taken place inside the Milky Way making it necessary to understand the distribution of dark matter inside of it. The usual approach for spiral galaxies assumes a spherical dark matter halo which contains all of the luminous parts of the galaxy, i.e. its galactic center and its thin stellar disk. The study of N -body simulations of structure formation during the evolution of the universe pointed towards a power-law-like universal dark matter profile parameterized as [37]

$$\rho(r) = \frac{\rho_0}{\left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^\gamma \left[1 + \left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^\alpha\right]^{\frac{\beta-\gamma}{\alpha}}}. \quad (2.4.1)$$

These N -body simulations motivated the Navarro-Frenk-White (NFW) density profile (cf. Eq. 2.4.2) being often considered as a benchmark model which, however, shows deviations from experimental observations in the Milky Way. According to [107] the cored Burkert profile (cf. Eq. 2.4.2), exhibiting a shallow dark matter density at the galactic center, seems to describe recent data of external galaxies and of stellar velocities inside the Milky Way better than the NFW profile. Besides the Burkert profile, the likewise cored isothermal profile (cf. Eq. 2.4.2) is often considered in the literature. Nevertheless, there are many more explicit choices for the parameters of the universal profile that yield viable density profiles when it comes to N -body simulations. A special profile is given by the Einasto profile (cf. Eq. 2.4.2) because it does not converge to a shape included in Eq. 2.4.1 and, in fact, coincides better with recent numerical simulations [48].

Of a special interest is the local dark matter density ρ_{\odot} at the position of the Sun because, as we will later see, it directly influences the strength of any dark matter cosmic ray contribution. The value of this specific property is inferred from the rotation curves of the Milky Way which brings in several difficulties due to our position inside the galaxy in question. Furthermore, the resulting values of the local density were obtained by assuming a particular dark matter density profile. Canonically, it is chosen to be $\rho_{\odot} = (0.3 \pm 0.1) \text{ GeV/cm}^3$ so that the error band includes most of the results given in the literature [37, 96]. There are, however, approaches trying to give an estimate of the local density in a model independent way. Their results seem to be slightly larger than the canonical choice, for instance, $\rho_{\odot} = (0.43 \pm 0.11) \text{ GeV/cm}^3$ as stated in [116]. We will include this ongoing debate in this thesis by setting $\rho_{\odot} = (0.4 \pm 0.1) \text{ GeV/cm}^3$ and translate the error of the local dark matter density to an uncertainty of the cosmic ray fluxes.

In the following, we give a list of dark matter density profiles and the best choices for their parameters in Tab. 2.4.1 on which we will base our computations of dark matter induced cosmic ray fluxes.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{NFW:} \quad \rho_{\text{NFW}}(r) &= \rho_0 \frac{R}{r} \left(1 + \frac{r}{R}\right)^{-2} \\
 \text{Einasto:} \quad \rho_{\text{Ein}}(r) &= \rho_0 \exp\left\{-\frac{2}{\alpha} \left[\left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^{\alpha} - 1\right]\right\} \\
 \text{Isothermal:} \quad \rho_{\text{Iso}}(r) &= \rho_0 \left[1 + \left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^2\right]^{-1}
 \end{aligned}$$

2.4 The Distribution of Dark Matter inside of Galaxies

Dark matter halo	α	β	ρ_0 [GeV/cm ³]	R [kpc]
NFW	-	-	24.42	0.184
Einasto	0.17	-	28.44	0.033
Isothermal	-	-	4.38	1.387
Burkert	-	-	12.67	0.712
Moore	1.16	-1.84	30.28	0.105

Table 2.4.1: Summary of the parameters characterizing the dark matter density profiles we use in this thesis. The given parameter values are taken from [48]. Notice that in this review the parameters were fitted to reproduce astrophysical observations of the Milky Way and not according to N -body simulations.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Burkert: } \quad \rho_{\text{Bur}}(r) &= \rho_0 \left[1 + \left(\frac{r}{R} \right) \right]^{-1} \left[1 + \left(\frac{r}{R} \right)^2 \right]^{-1} \\
 \text{Moore: } \quad \rho_{\text{Moo}}(r) &= \rho_0 \left(\frac{R}{r} \right)^\alpha \left(1 + \frac{r}{R} \right)^\beta.
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.4.2}$$

Finally, note that we do not assume any form of subhalos inside the given density profile which are, however, observed in high-resolution N -body simulations [78] and expected from the behavior of cold dark matter.

3 Indirect Searches for Dark Matter

In this chapter we lay the groundwork for the subsequent treatment of a particular dark matter model. To this end, we illustrate the general relation between cosmic rays and dark matter interactions that might be used to indirectly detect it. Furthermore we present and discuss recent results of indirect searches for dark matter. Eventually, we give insight in the theoretical calculation of dark matter cosmic ray contributions within the gamma-ray, antiproton and antideuteron channel.

3.1 General Aspects of Indirect Detection of Dark Matter

As presented in the previous chapter, there are compelling evidences supporting the existence of dark matter. However, none of these evidences is an indisputable direct sight of non-gravitational dark matter interactions. On the other hand it is, indeed, a crucial necessity to observe dark matter interactions with ordinary matter or itself since such events would yield information about the properties of dark matter which would narrow down the viable classes of dark matter models. As dark matter was postulated to interact very weakly with ordinary matter, its direct detection seems rather cumbersome but the search for dark matter pair-annihilations or decays yields a complementary approach. The model-dependent outcome of such self-interactions contains significant amounts of standard model particles which will propagate through the galaxy and universe. At some point these dark matter interaction remnants might cross the Earth's atmosphere where experimental setups are able to detect them as contribution to the cosmic rays. This is the general scheme of indirect dark matter searches: Searching for dark matter contributions to particular cosmic ray fluxes which appear as excesses above the expected astrophysical background flux and which provide information about dark matter properties.

A key problem of indirect searches is the determination of particular cosmic ray channels and their respective energy ranges where a substantial dark matter signal can be expected. In fact, any dark matter contribution will have to compete with the standard astrophysical flux in the respective channel and the question remains whether the astrophysical component entirely hides the dark component or not. Thus, it is necessary to understand the astrophysical processes that are the source for the observed cosmic rays. In the following we will, therefore, investigate matter and antimatter cosmic ray fluxes in detail and present recent experimental results in the context of indirect detection.

3.1.1 Prospects of Matter Cosmic Ray Channels

Almost all primary cosmic rays, i.e. particles whose origin is situated outside of the Earth's atmosphere (for instance, the Milky Way or even extragalactic sources), consist of high-energy matter particles of which approximately 86% are protons, 11% are helium nuclei, 1% are heavier nuclei up to uranium and 2% are freely-moving electrons [112]. A large amount of these particles have likely been accelerated by blast waves of galactic supernovae remnants [40]. Although their production mechanisms are understood in a larger energy range, charged matter cosmic rays are not suitable for the purpose of indirect searches because the astrophysical background is immense and any dark matter component is disguised by it.

Therefore, the focus lies on neutral matter particles, in particular gamma-ray photons and neutrinos which yield rather different prospects in the context of dark matter physics. These channels also suffer from an astrophysical background but the hypothetical dark matter contribution provides characteristic advantages in comparison to the one of charged particles:

- Neutral particles are not deflected by galactic magnetic fields, hence travel along straight lines and experiments with directional sensitivity are able to localize to origin of the respective particle.
- Neutrinos and, to a lesser extent, photons rarely scatter and interact with interstellar matter inside the Milky Way. Thus, most of these particles reach the Earth's atmosphere unaltered and keep information about their production site.
- Since both particle species are stable, weakly interacting with interstellar matter and (nearly) traveling at the speed of light, even sources outside of the

Milky Way could give rise to a sizable amount of cosmic ray events. Among these sources are satellite galaxies, galaxy clusters or the extragalactic space [120].

A distinction between these two channels must be made when it comes to experimental observations and the analysis of the respective cosmic ray events. In this thesis, however, we only concentrate on the gamma-ray photon channel.

Neutrinos In contrast to photons, neutrinos are usually detected in underground experiments via Cherenkov light in large volumes of water or ice, for example, the IceCube telescope in Antarctica or ANTARES at the ground of the Mediterranean Sea [13]. This approach is necessary since neutrinos interact very weakly with matter, thus, gaining a sizable amount of interactions requires a large volume of material. Underground-based neutrino observations suffer from an additional source of background in the GeV to TeV range, namely atmospheric neutrinos, i.e. neutrinos that are produced inside the Earth's atmosphere by primary cosmic rays scattering on terrestrial particles. These interactions produce preferentially pions and kaons which decay after a while leaving an electron and muon neutrino yield. However, the reduction of this particular background is the reason why these experimental sites are constructed underground.

Further astrophysical sources of neutrinos include those produced during cosmic ray scatterings in the Sun's corona which was studied in [90] and more distant galactic sources such as interactions of primary cosmic rays with the interstellar medium [25, 91]. The Sun's contribution to the neutrino flux can be eliminated by excluding studies in the direction of the Sun whereas galactic sources seem to be irreducible. In addition, neutrinos from all astrophysical and dark sources suffer from neutrino oscillations which have to be taken into account in case of flavor specific analyses.

Gamma-ray photons Indirect searches focusing on gamma-ray photons rely on the investigation of many distinct observables. Among those one finds the extragalactic gamma-ray background (EGB) and gamma-ray lines.

The EGB comprises a large variety of both individual and diffuse gamma-ray sources localized in a region that spans from the edge of the Milky Way to the edge of the observable universe. Therefore, this background is supposed to contain numerous physical phenomena, for instance, active galactic nuclei, star-forming galaxies and gamma-ray bursts [59]. Since the gamma-ray signals from dark matter annihilations or decays are almost isotropic diffuse fluxes, they should be part of the EGB.

Unfortunately, it is impossible to measure this fundamental quantity directly because of the finite resolution of all experimental instruments. In principle, if one was able to resolve every individual extragalactic gamma-ray source completely then one would obtain the EGB. In practice, however, the resolution of telescopes and other devices is limited such that distant individual sources contribute to the so-called isotropic diffuse gamma-ray background (IGRB) which is isotropic on large angular scales. The sum of individually resolved extragalactic sources and the IGRB yields, in return, an upper limit on the EGB intensity [7].

In order to extract the two components of the EGB, contaminating sources like galactic gamma-ray emissions due to cosmic ray interactions with the interstellar matter and secondary gamma-rays from cosmic ray interactions in the Earth's atmosphere have to be subtracted. To this end, the Milky Way's galactic disk is excluded and explicit galactic gamma-ray foreground models are constructed to describe this kind of contribution. Such an approach is, nevertheless, rather cumbersome and it introduces additional uncertainties due to the foreground modeling.

In the past a number of experiments examined the EGB, for example, an early observation in the 1970's via the SAS-2 satellite as well as more recent and detailed analyses by the Energetic Gamma Ray Experiment Telescope (EGRET) on the Compton Gamma Ray Observatory and by the Fermi Gamma-Ray Space Telescope (Fermi-LAT). In this thesis we consider the data of the latter collaboration provided in [7]. They were able to extract the IGRB in the energy range from 100 MeV to 820 GeV while observing no unexpected behavior that could give rise to dark matter contributions but it enables us to derive bounds on the properties of our specific dark matter model which we describe later in Chp. 4. Moreover, the IGRB spectrum dN/dE seems to be well described by a power law that features an exponential cutoff at high energies while being independent of the foreground model

$$\frac{dN}{dE} = I_{100} \left(\frac{E}{100 \text{ MeV}} \right)^{-\gamma} \exp \left(-\frac{E}{E_{\text{cut}}} \right),$$

where the best-fit values of the parameters γ , I_{100} and E_{cut} are given in the reference.

Gamma-ray lines serve as second starting point for indirect dark matter searches. Astrophysical gamma-ray spectra are commonly expected to follow a power law like the EGB but they do not exhibit any single lines. The presence of monochromatic signals inside these spectra would yield a striking evidence of particle physics con-

tributions, for example, photons originating from dark matter two-body decays. In this thesis, however, we do not include such searches.

3.1.2 Prospects of Antimatter Cosmic Ray Channels

Although making up only a tiny fraction of the cosmic rays, antiparticle channels are a much more viable starting point of indirect searches than matter channels: Typically, due to the matter-antimatter asymmetry of the universe, astrophysical antiparticle cosmic rays originate in interactions of matter primary cosmic rays with the interstellar medium (and, hence, are called secondary cosmic rays) and are not mere existing accelerated antimatter. Thus, the fluxes of astrophysical background and a hypothetic dark matter contribution should be at a comparable order of magnitude. In this sense, excesses above the expected background are detected more easily and reliably.

The majority of the indirect searches in the literature is based on antiprotons, positrons and antideuterons, i.e. the antimatter counterparts of the most abundant components of the cosmic rays, which are expected to yield the most promising prospects for dark matter signals since they are stable and are considered to be produced in sizable amounts.

3.1.2.1 Positrons

The astrophysical background of positrons is mainly produced by the spallation of high-energy primary cosmic rays on the interstellar medium in the Milky Way. In some sense, our galaxy operates as a large fixed target particle accelerator where the cosmic rays play the role of the accelerated particles and the galactic disk with its comprised gas is the fixed target. The source of positrons is predominantly the collision of protons with resting hydrogen producing charged pions which subsequently decay to muons that eventually decay to positrons [115]:

After they traveled through the galaxy, positrons appear as tiny fraction of the cosmic rays. Measurements of this flux are commonly provided in terms of the so-called positron to electron fraction

Figure 3.1.1: Positron fraction as measured by the PAMELA satellite. The black line shows the expected astrophysical background from secondary production, while the red data points are the PAMELA measurements [9].

$$\frac{\phi(e^+)}{\phi(e^-) + \phi(e^+)},$$

with $\phi(X)$ denoting the respective cosmic ray flux at the Earth's position. This quantity is usually analyzed because the systematic uncertainties of both the electron and positron flux measurements are considered to cancel since they share common sources. As a surprise to the scientific community, multiple independent experiments, for example, the Payload for Antimatter Matter Exploration and Light-nuclei Astrophysics (PAMELA) on the Resurs-DK1 satellite [9], the Alpha Magnetic Spectrometer on Space Shuttle flight STS-91 (AMS-01) [15], the balloon-borne HEAT-pbar experiment [32] and Fermi-LAT [6] presented coinciding results about an anomalous excess in this fraction with increasing kinetic energies which is depicted in Fig. 3.1.1.

Before investigating the origin of the excess at about $\simeq 10$ GeV, we give a simple reasoning explaining the expected behavior of the astrophysical background in this energy region: With increasing kinetic energy of the positron, the background flux decreases because high-energy particles move quickly through the galaxy without being deflected much by the galactic magnetic field and without undergoing many interactions with the interstellar medium. Since the positrons' production mecha-

nism relates their kinetic energies with the kinetic energies of the primary particles producing them, one expects a decreasing background. At lower energies, however, the primary matter particles are deflected more which implies that they stay longer inside the galaxy. This leads to a higher number of interactions with the interstellar medium, thus, to an enlarged positron yield.

Despite the excess above 10 GeV, the PAMELA data in Fig. 3.1.1 seem to contradict the background prediction even in the range below 10 GeV. According to [9] this might be an artifact of a charge-dependent solar modulation effect. Both solar modulation and the galactic propagation of antiparticles will be discussed in detail in Sec. 3.2.

One would like to understand the observed excess in the positron fraction as an indication for the presence of dark matter interactions, which is not unambiguously possible since earlier analysis of the HEAT data already revealed that, for instance, WIMP dark matter annihilations cannot account for the full size of the effect. In fact, the excess is about a factor of 50 larger than the expected dark matter contribution [87]. In order to maintain an explanation via dark matter presence, several auxiliary suggestions were made: On one side, there might be “boost factors” due to local fluctuations of the dark matter density that increase the average annihilation cross-section or decay rate. Such a boost factor can also be generated by introducing Sommerfeld enhancement or resonance effects as stated in [47]. Apart from these ad-hoc methods, the nature of the excess might be a simple astrophysical source like positrons produced in the magnetosphere of nearby pulsars or secondary production of positrons taking place in the acceleration region of supernova remnants [11].

Nevertheless, the example of positron cosmic rays showed that antimatter channels are viable candidates for indirect searches although the actual interpretation of detected excesses is cumbersome. Analyses of the positron channel are not included in this thesis.

3.1.2.2 Antiprotons

Most of the cosmic ray antiprotons originate from spallation processes of high-energy primary cosmic ray nuclei impinging on hydrogen or helium inside the interstellar medium in the Milky Way’s galactic disk. Antiprotons of this production reaction tend to possess larger kinetic energies due to the following argument: Since for every produced antiproton during these interactions, electric charge and baryon number

are supposed to be conserved, at least three protons must be created at the same time via

$$p + H \longrightarrow \bar{p} + p + p + p + X.$$

This imposes a threshold of $E_p = 7m_p$ on the energy of the incoming proton in the rest-frame of the interstellar hydrogen [36]. Conservation of the incoming proton's momentum additionally demands that the antiproton's momentum obtains a larger probability to be at higher kinetic energies. Nonetheless, as in the case of positrons, the expected background of astrophysical antiprotons decreases due to galactic magnetic fields and increases by going to lower energies where in this particular case a cutoff due to the production threshold should appear. However, this effect is washed out by the production process that features impinging helium nuclei instead of protons. These interactions do not suffer from an analogous threshold [36]. Furthermore, there are a few subdominant mechanisms that influence the number and energies of secondary antiprotons: Tertiary production via inelastic, non-annihilating scatterings with matter in the galactic disk which flatten the antiprotons' spectra and shift them to lower kinetic energies or annihilation on interstellar hydrogen and helium after their production which lowers the overall antiproton flux [115].

A hypothetic dark matter contribution of antiprotons to the astrophysical background would also not suffer from any threshold constraints, which implies that excesses above the expectations should be detectable in the low-energy range of the antiproton flux. This flux was measured and analyzed by numerous experiments, for example, a series of flights of the Balloon-borne Experiment with a Superconducting Spectrometer (BESS) from 1995 to 2000 [24], the balloon-borne BESS-Polar experiment [4], AMS-01 [14] and PAMELA [10]. Their results from 60 MeV to 180 GeV are summarized in Fig. 3.1.2 which also depicts the expected astrophysical background as a solid line.

Remarkably, this astrophysical background fits the data very well and no further dark contribution is necessary which, although, cannot be interpreted as an absence of dark matter annihilations or decays. These observations rather give rise to a possibility to constrain dark matter properties by imposing that the sum of background and dark matter contribution does not overshoot the experimental findings. In this thesis, we will adopt this scheme to derive bounds on the lifetime of the dark matter particle in our model. To this end, we do not take advantage of the PAMELA data

Figure 3.1.2: Summary of the observed cosmic ray antiproton flux from various contemporary experiments as stated in the legend. The black, solid or dashed lines indicate the expectation of the astrophysical background as calculated by different models of the galactic propagation of antiprotons[[10]].

in red in Fig. 3.1.2 but include the collaboration’s refined measurements given in [12] which extended the kinetic energy range from 180 GeV to 350 GeV. In addition, the AMS-02 collaboration recently published their final measurements of the proton and helium flux as well as the positron-to-electron fraction [16, 17] accounting for the full systematic and statistical errors. In fact, they also provided a preliminary result concerning the antiproton-to-proton ratio in [50] which lacks an elaborate treatment of errors and is only available in terms of a plot so that we exclude these most recent measurements from the derivation of lifetime limits.

3.1.2.3 Antideuterons

A last constituent of antimatter cosmic rays that is commonly investigated in the literature is the antideuteron which is the bound state of an antiproton and an antineutron. The interest in this channel arises due to the expected astrophysical background which is, on one side, very low and even further suppressed in the low-energy range and, on the other side, antideuterons do not suffer to a large extent from energy loss processes, in contrast to antiprotons. Thus, the antideuteron channel can be considered almost background-free in searches at low energies which raises the chance of a hypothetical antideuteron signal to originate from dark matter inter-

actions. In fact, not a single cosmic ray antideuteron has been detected in the past by the BESS experiment [72]. Moreover, there are no other recent measurements on this particular channel available. Nonetheless, several missions have already started collecting data such as AMS-02 or are planned to be launched in the near future like the Gaseous Antiparticle Spectrometer (GAPS).

As the antideuteron is a bound state of two particles its formation in astrophysical processes is a bit different compared to positrons and antiprotons. However, the main production mechanism is the spallation of high-energy primary cosmic ray protons on interstellar hydrogen but this time an antiproton and an antineutron must be created at the same time in this process. First of all, this increases the previously derived threshold of $E_p = 7m_p$ to an even higher threshold of $E_p^{\text{thresh}} = 16m_p$ [89] and secondly, both antiparticles are said to merge if the coalescence condition is fulfilled, i.e. the magnitude of their three-momentum difference must be smaller than a maximal momentum p_0 [60] which is also called coalescence momentum. This property is energy- and process-dependent and in order to obtain suitable estimates, one should calibrate p_0 , such that it reproduces the results of antideuteron formation in laboratory nucleus-nucleus-collisions in the respective energy range [89, 97].

The coalescence condition forces both particles to be produced either nearly at rest where the threshold for such spallation processes shrinks the probability of an appropriate production or they have to be produced with almost equal and parallel momenta. In any case, these constraining conditions lead to a suppressed astrophysical background which, using the coalescence description too, can be dominated by dark matter contributions in the low-energy range according to [60].

The coalescence approach features several drawbacks: On one hand, usually only the averaged antiproton and antineutron spectra of either the cosmic ray spallation or the dark matter interaction are taken into consideration. Such an approach is, however, inappropriate to reproduce the observed production rates as stated in [97]. A better treatment would be an event-by-event analysis of the coalescence condition in Monte-Carlo simulations which is done in the recent literature. On the other hand, the coalescence model is strictly deterministic, i.e. if the coalescence condition is fulfilled then both antiparticles form a bound state. This does not resemble the probabilistic nature of quantum mechanics which should be applied in the case of antideuteron formation. Therefore, the authors of [55] constructed a probabilistic formation model based on the total production cross-section of deuterons in particle collisions to account for their quantum behavior.

In this thesis we will include the antideuteron channel as an outlook to further studies and, thus, we only adopt the coalescence approach using averaged particle spectra, although we will use an astrophysical background calculation [89] that involved the Monte-Carlo event-by-event approach. Using the non-observation by the BESS experiment and prospected AMS-02 and GAPS sensitivities, we can derive upper bounds on the dark matter contribution of our model.

3.2 Deriving Theoretical Predictions for Cosmic Ray Fluxes

The production sites of astrophysical and dark matter antimatter cosmic rays are situated in distant regions inside the Milky Way's galactic disk where large amounts of the interstellar medium accumulated or respectively in the whole dark matter halo around the Milky Way. Therefore, these particles have to travel an enormous distance through the galaxy before they finally reach the Earth's atmosphere. Especially charged particles are affected by several physical phenomena on their journey inside the Milky Way that affect their kinetic energy and the length of their path to the Earth. Since experimental data encompass all of these known and possibly unknown effects, it is an essential step to construct models and theories that are able to describe the occurring galactic processes and, applied to the injection spectra of a cosmic ray particle species, yield an estimate of its expected flux that can be compared to the experimental findings.

Assuming we have accomplished the particle physics task of calculating the kinetic energy spectra of dark matter annihilations or decays per unit kinetic energy T and annihilation/decay, denoted by dN_f/dT , with respect to all particle species f stated in the previous chapter as well as the ones of their astrophysical counterparts, this chapter is supposed to give an illustrative overview of the astrophysical processes that affect these cosmic rays on their propagation to the Earth. Moreover, we will give explicit formulæ which quantitatively describe the resulting fluxes in the atmosphere. In general we will denote the cosmic ray flux of particle f by

$$\Phi_f := \frac{dN}{dAdtd\Omega}$$

which is nothing but the number of particles per unit area, time and solid angle.

As we are interested in the application of indirect searches to a specific decaying dark matter model, the given formulæ only refer to this particular case.

3.2.1 The Propagation of Gamma-Ray Photons

According to the discussion in Sec. 3.1.1, gamma-ray photons are not deflected by galactic phenomena and, hence, travel along straight lines to the Earth. Besides, it suffices to calculate the dark matter contribution to the gamma-ray flux because there is no theory prediction for the EGB and only experimental data are available. This situation simplifies the necessary amount of work as dark matter gamma-ray fluxes of galactic origin can be calculated by line of sight integrals over the dark matter density along the respective direction. In detail, two contributions have to be taken into consideration. Since dark matter is supposed to be distributed in the whole universe, extragalactic accumulations of dark matter yield an isotropic and diffuse component. These gamma-rays, however, might be produced at large distances such that the expansion of the universe becomes relevant and it must be included via the redshift of photons: Gamma-rays emitted at a distance corresponding to the redshift z and with an energy T will be shifted to the lower energy $T/(1+z)$. Accounting for the expansion of the universe, yields the differential gamma-ray flux at the Earth's position given by [83]

$$\frac{d\Phi_{\gamma}^{\text{exg}}}{dT} = \frac{\Omega_c \rho_{\text{crit}}}{4\pi m_{\text{DM}} H_0 \Omega_m^{\frac{1}{2}}} \int_1^{y_{\text{max}}} \sum_f \Gamma_f \left. \frac{dN_{\gamma}^f}{dT} \right|_{yT} \frac{y^{-\frac{3}{2}}}{\sqrt{1 + \frac{\Omega_{\Lambda}}{\Omega_m y^3}}} dy \quad , \quad (3.2.1)$$

where the sum runs over all decay channels f with partial decay width Γ_f of the dark matter particle that produces gamma-ray photons and m_{DM} denotes the mass of the dark matter particle. The variable $y := 1+z$ is a transformed redshift z and $y_{\text{max}} = 1+z_{\text{dec}}$ refers to the time where the photons decoupled from the thermal bath in the early universe and began to travel freely. Eq. 3.2.1 must be taken with several caveats: It is only valid, if one assumes the dark matter number density to stay constant on cosmological timescales which might be in tension with unstable dark matter. However, it is a good approximation since viable decaying dark matter candidates must have lifetimes larger than the lifetime of the universe. Furthermore, this equation holds technically speaking only during the matter and dark energy dominated epochs of the universe but since photons with very high redshifts

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contribute to a negligible extent, the integral can be performed up to $y_{\max} = \infty$. Last but not least, photons do not travel entirely freely, they might, for instance, interact with CMB photons or intergalactic background light [84].

The second contribution to the gamma-ray flux is of galactic origin but in this case anisotropic because the Earth is inside the object of interest which biases line of sight integrals. The galactic component takes the Milky Way's dark matter density profiles, discussed in Sec. 2.4, into account. The differential gamma-ray flux is then given by [48]

$$\frac{d\Phi_{\gamma}^{\text{halo}}}{dT}(\theta) = \frac{r_{\odot}\rho_{\odot}}{4\pi m_{\text{DM}}} \sum_f \Gamma_f \frac{dN_{\gamma}^f}{dT} \int_{\text{line of sight}} \frac{ds}{r_{\odot}} \left(\frac{\rho_{\text{DM}}(r(s,\theta))}{\rho_{\odot}} \right) \quad (3.2.2)$$

using $r(s,\theta) = (r_{\odot}^2 + s^2 - 2sr_{\odot}\cos\theta)^{\frac{1}{2}}$, θ that denotes the aperture angle between the direction of the line of sight and the axis connecting the Earth to the galactic center and $r_{\odot} = 8.33$ kpc being the Sun's distance to the galactic center. We are left here with a dependence on the aperture angle which is commonly expressed in terms of the galactic longitude l and the galactic latitude b via $\cos\theta = \cos l \cos b$:

$$J(l,b) = \int_{\text{line of sight}} \frac{ds}{r_{\odot}} \left(\frac{\rho_{\text{DM}}(r(s,l,b))}{\rho_{\odot}} \right).$$

In order to achieve an increase in statistics by observing a large sector of the whole sky, one averages this quantity over the corresponding part of the galaxy, i.e. one uses:

$$\bar{J} = \frac{4}{\Delta\Omega} \int_{b_{\min}}^{b_{\max}} \int_{l_{\min}}^{l_{\max}} J(l,b) \cos b \, dl db, \quad \Delta\Omega = 4 \int_{b_{\min}}^{b_{\max}} \int_{l_{\min}}^{l_{\max}} \cos b \, dl db.$$

Of course, the observable portion of the sky is limited by the acceptance region of experimental instruments and as we consider the results of [7], we adopt their restrictions on the galactic coordinates¹ via $|l| < 180^{\circ}$ and $|b| < 10^{\circ}$ such that the integral boundaries have to be chosen appropriately. Finally, by choosing a dark matter density profile ρ_{DM} , the resulting functions $J(l,b)$ are in most cases not given in terms

¹In fact, [7] uses the restriction $|b| < 5^{\circ}$ to exclude the region of the galactic disk. However, they mask additional pixel with higher latitudes but not as a whole band. With respect to their Fig. 20 which shows all masked pixels, we chose the given restriction for the purpose of this thesis.

Dark matter halo	\bar{J}	$\Delta\Omega$
NFW	2.0856	10.3842
Einasto	2.0981	
Isothermal	2.1132	
Burkert	2.0576	
Moore	2.0930	

Table 3.2.1: Summary of the quantities \bar{J} and $\Delta\Omega$ related to the averaging process of Eq. 3.2.2 in the case of decaying dark matter where we have taken into consideration five dark matter density profiles. The necessary functions $J(l, b)$ were taken from [2].

of known functions but the authors of [48] provide them as interpolating functions on their website [2]. By the virtue of these data, we performed the averaging process numerically via MATLAB and state the used script in Lst. D.1 of Appendix D.1. In Tab. 3.2.1 we summarize our results of \bar{J} and $\Delta\Omega$ for the relevant density profiles. After the averaging procedure, the final differential gamma-ray flux reads

$$\frac{d\Phi_\gamma}{dT} = \frac{r_\odot \rho_\odot}{4\pi m_{\text{DM}}} \Delta\Omega \bar{J} \sum_f \Gamma_f \frac{dN_\gamma^f}{dT}. \quad (3.2.3)$$

3.2.2 The Propagation of Charged Particles inside the Milky Way

In contrast to neutral particles, a proper description of the propagation of charged particles (and antiparticles) has to incorporate a large number of intragalactic effects and phenomena that are mainly connected to electromagnetic interactions. These effects make it very unlikely that any extragalactic charged particle will traverse the Earth's atmosphere at some time. Thus, unlike gamma-ray photons, the only sources of charged antiparticle cosmic rays lie inside our own galaxy. In this sense, we have to understand the structure of the Milky Way and the electromagnetic processes having an effect on the propagation inside of it.

3.2.2.1 The Structure of the Milky Way

The Milky Way is believed to be a barred spiral galaxy [76] where our solar system is situated in the vicinity of the arm structure known as the Orion-Cygnus arm.

Moreover, as mentioned in the previous section, the Sun is approximately $r_{\odot} = 8.33$ kpc away from the galactic center. Among the the constituing parts of the Milky Way there are several of major importance to the propagation of charged particles. In the following we will, therefore, briefly discuss the relevance of particular regions of our galaxy.

The galactic center In its central region the Milky Way hosts a dense, nearly spheroidal bulge of mostly old stars that shows a larger vertical extension than the rest of the galaxy. The spheroidal shape is disturbed by an elongated bar structure with a radius (half-length) of approximately 4.4 kpc [43]. Moreover, an intense radio source called Sagittarius A* is located in the very center of the galaxy. Studying the motion of the nearby stellar material, the occurrence of this radio source is best explained by the existence of a super massive black hole in the central region [80, 95]. For the purposes of charged particle propagation the galactic center is treated in the same way as the galactic disk.

The galactic disk The galactic disk harbors the majority of the interstellar medium and star-forming regions of the Milky Way and assumes the highest importance in the sense of indirect searches and particle propagation. The disk itself possesses a radius of approximately 25 kpc and a thickness of about 350 pc in the region called thin disk. Furthermore, the galactic disk features spiral arms where the best-fitting model is a four-arm logarithmic-spiral structure [63]. Indeed, determining the actual spiral arm structure of the Milky Way is tedious since we are situated inside the galactic plane which prevents any top view on the galaxy.

There are multiple phenomena influencing charged particle and antiparticle propagation inside the disk:

- Annihilation processes on the interstellar medium,
- energy losses due to inelastic, (non-annihilating) scatterings on the interstellar medium,
- reaccelerations due to plasma shock waves and magnetic inhomogeneities which are known as first and second order Fermi accelerations [112],
- an outflow of low-energy particles from the galactic disk due to a stabilizing galactic wind [103].

The stellar halo This galactic component surrounds the galactic disk, is spherically symmetric with a radius of about 50 kpc and contains old stars and gravi-

tationally bound globular clusters of which about 90% are located in the vicinity of the galactic center [43]. The halo does not include active star formation regions as most of its gas is not cool enough to collapse. There is, however, an additional gaseous halo of hot gas with temperatures between $1 \cdot 10^6$ K and $2.5 \cdot 10^6$ K and of a mass equal to the one of the Milky Way itself that extends far beyond the reach of the stellar halo [85]. Nevertheless, both types of halos are of minor importance to the propagation of charged particles and can be disregarded.

The dark matter halo This region of the Milky Way was previously discussed in Sec. 2.4. Apart from the fact that all dark matter cosmic rays originate from this halo, it is of no further importance to the propagation of the dark matter decay products.

The galactic magnetic field Several observations of the galactic disk, for example measurements relying on Faraday rotation, revealed the existence of a magnetic field of the Milky Way [41, 112]. Besides, more advanced techniques based on synchrotron radiation originating in regions far above the galactic disk seem to indicate that the magnetic field is also present in the Milky Way's outer layers [27]. In this sense, the magnetic field is not a special region of the galaxy, it rather penetrates all of its components.

The galactic magnetic field features two distinct components where the first one is homogeneous and following the direction of the spiral arms whereas the second one is highly inhomogeneous and turbulent [33]. This turbulent part of the magnetic field influences the propagation of charged particles by so-called Alfvén waves, i.e. waves of the irregularities of the magnetic field, which effectively cause a random-walk-like path of low-energy particles [104] to which, in this situation, decay products of dark matter belong. We will see in the subsequent section that this random walk is modeled by a diffusion equation where the diffusion coefficient is position-dependent and completely unknown .

3.2.2.2 The Diffusive Transport Equation

The irregularities and turbulences of the galactic magnetic field lead to a complex propagation behavior of charged cosmic rays on their way to the Earth, i.e., these effects generate a random-walk of the respective particle which was recognized to be treatable with a diffusion equation. This diffusion equation is known as the transport

equation of the energy and space distribution of the number density $f := dn/dT$ of any species of charged cosmic rays (T being the kinetic energy of the particle) and it is usually given in the general form [35, 38]

$$\frac{\partial f}{\partial t} - \nabla \left[\mathcal{K}(T) \nabla f - \vec{V}_C(\vec{r}) f \right] - \frac{\partial}{\partial T} \left[b(T, \vec{r}) f - \mathcal{K}_{EE}(T) \frac{\partial f}{\partial T} \right] = Q(T, \vec{r}). \quad (3.2.4)$$

In principle, all astrophysical phenomena of the Milky Way as presented beforehand are reflected in some of the terms in Eq. 3.2.4.

Before we will work out the effect of each term separately, we describe a simplifying model that is usually applied throughout the literature, namely the two-zone diffusion model introduced in [103]. In this model the Milky Way's diffusive halo is divided in two regions: the thin gaseous galactic disk with a height of $2h = 200$ pc and the magnetic halo placed beneath and above the galactic disk with a vertical half-thickness L considered as a free parameter. Furthermore, this construction is thought to be located inside a cylinder of radius $R = 20$ pc that is centered at the galactic plane. Conveniently, one uses cylindrical coordinates (r, φ, z) to describe the spatial dependencies.

The boundary conditions are set as follows: The number density of a particular species of charged cosmic rays must vanish at $z = \pm L$ and $r = R$ [46]. Moreover, only those dark matter decays contribute to a cosmic ray flux that take place inside the part of the dark matter halo lying inside the cylinder of the model. Since the dark matter halo of the Milky Way exceeds the dimensions of the two-zone model's cylinder, a certain fraction of dark matter decays is lost. For example, the authors of [111] tried to fix this problem by introducing a model that extends to the whole dark matter halo with the result that the uncertainties on the parameters of the two-zone diffusion model dominate the corrections due to the dark matter halo inclusion.

Having defined the framework in which we will treat the transport equation, we now elaborate on the occurring terms.

1. The first term on the left-hand side of the transport equation is conveniently disregarded because, usually, the number densities of cosmic rays are considered in steady state.
2. The second term in rectangular brackets contains two important processes: The function $\mathcal{K}(T)$ is the energy-dependent diffusion coefficient of the transport equation describing the result of numerous deflections of a particle due

to the magnetic field. The coefficient is commonly parameterized as follows

$$\mathcal{K}(T) = \mathcal{K}_0 \beta \left(\frac{\mathcal{R}}{\text{GV}} \right)^\delta$$

introducing a normalization constant \mathcal{K}_0 and a constant spectral index δ as well as the cosmic ray particle's beta factor $\beta = v/c$ and its rigidity $\mathcal{R} = pc/(Ze)$ involving the momentum p and proton number Z . This diffusion coefficient is additionally assumed to be constant inside the whole diffusive cylinder which explains the lack of a spatial dependence.

The second term in the bracket describes a convective process that emerges because of the galactic wind in the Milky Way's disk. It tends to push the cosmic ray particles vertically outwards the disk and in the two-zone model we simplify $\vec{V}_C(\vec{r}) = \text{sign}(z) V_C \hat{z}$, i.e. we take the velocity V_C of the galactic wind to be constant [48].

3. In general, the third term refers to a number of energy loss and reacceleration processes taking place inside the galactic disk. Applying the two-zone model to the first contribution, we can rewrite it as $b(T, \vec{r}) = 2h\delta(z)b(T)$. The function $b(T)$ then accounts for various energy loss processes that affect the respective species of cosmic rays. We will later specify the contributions to this function in the case of antiprotons.

The second term inside the derivative describes the effects of the drift of the magnetic field's Alfvén waves into the central region of the Milky Way on charged cosmic rays. These drifts possess a characteristic velocity V_a and lead to small diffusive reaccelerations of the particles because of second order Fermi accelerations. Eventually, these reaccelerations induce a diffusion in the particle's energy space whose strength is dependent on the value of the diffusion coefficient $\mathcal{K}(T)$, the particle's total energy E and its velocity β as parameterized by [103]

$$\mathcal{K}_{EE}(T) = \frac{2}{9} V_a^2 \frac{E^2 \beta^4}{\mathcal{K}(T)}.$$

The meaning of this parameterization can be paraphrased as follows: The more efficiently cosmic ray particles diffuse in space, the fewer collisions occur and the weaker is the energy diffusion [38].

In the two-zone diffusion model, the left-hand side of the transport equation contains then five free parameters δ , \mathcal{K}_0 , V_C , V_a and L . Appropriate estimates of their values

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parameter set	L [kpc]	\mathcal{K}_0 [kpc ² /Myr]	δ	V_C [km/s]	V_a [km/s]
MIN	1	0.0016	0.85	13.5	22.4
MED	4	0.0112	0.70	12	52.9
MAX	15	0.0765	0.46	5	117.6

Table 3.2.2: Parameters of the transport equation 3.2.4 in the two-zone diffusion model in the case of cosmic ray antiprotons where L denotes the half-thickness of the magnetic halo of the two-zone model, \mathcal{K}_0 denotes the normalization and δ denotes the spectral index of the diffusion coefficient, V_C refers to the speed of the convective wind and V_a yields the speed of the Alfvén waves of the galactic magnetic field [38].

can be found by tuning them, for instance, to the fluxes of astrophysical primary and secondary cosmic rays after their propagation. In fact, the boron-to-carbon ratio (B/C) was found to be a suitable channel that is sensitive to the parameters of the galactic propagation [103]. As a result of the B/C studies, three parameter sets called MIN, MED and MAX, displayed in Tab. 3.2.2, were singled out which all reproduce the experimental observations of the boron-to-carbon ratio but which refer to quite distinct realizations in nature: The MIN and MAX set can clearly not describe the physical reality inside the Milky Way since they are quite extreme. They should rather be considered as lower or upper limits on the range of the individual parameters. Nevertheless, we will use all three sets in this thesis and show results with respect to each realization.

It should be noted that the values in Tab. 3.2.2 only apply to antiprotons (and antideuterons) since not all terms in the transport equation are present in the case of positrons.

What is left to discuss, is the right-hand side of the transport equation: The function $Q(T, \vec{r})$ is a short-hand notation for a number of source and sink terms with respect to a specific species of cosmic rays. In general, it encompasses the astrophysical background sources as well as the hypothetical dark matter source term and, in addition, several annihilation reactions. Since we want to focus on the study of antiprotons and antideuterons in this thesis, the subsequent sections elaborate on the solution of the transport equation with respect to these two cosmic ray channels. Furthermore, we want to treat the astrophysical and the dark matter contribution separately.

3.2.2.3 Galactic Propagation of Antiprotons of Astrophysical Origin

It is our aim to find a theoretical prediction for the astrophysical antiproton background flux after the galactic propagation according to Eq. 3.2.4. To this end, we need to specify the energy losses paraphrased by the function $b(T)$ in the transport equation² as well as all source and sink terms on its right-hand side.

Sink term The sink term on the right-hand side of the transport equation accounts for the possibility of the annihilation of antiprotons on the interstellar medium. In the two-zone model, such a term reads

$$Q_{\bar{p}}^{\text{ann}}(z, T) = -2h\delta(z)\Gamma^{\text{ann}},$$

where $\delta(z)$ ensures the annihilations to take place only in the thin galactic disk. The annihilation rate Γ^{ann} includes annihilations on hydrogen and helium according to

$$\Gamma^{\text{ann}} = \left(n_{\text{H}} + 4^{2/3} n_{\text{He}} \right) \sigma_{\bar{p}\text{p}}^{\text{ann}} v_{\bar{p}}$$

with $n_{\text{H}} = 0.9 \text{ cm}^{-3}$ and $n_{\text{He}} = 0.1 \text{ cm}^{-3}$ denoting the interstellar medium hydrogen or helium densities respectively. Besides, $v_{\bar{p}}$ is the velocity of the incoming antiproton and $\sigma_{\bar{p}\text{p}}^{\text{ann}}$ refers to the annihilation cross-section of the process. The factor $4^{2/3}$ in front of the helium number density accounts in an effective way for the different geometrical cross-section of helium. In principle, antiprotons can collide elastically on interstellar hydrogen or helium but since such interactions mostly produce scatterings in the forward direction, there is no effect in form of sources or sinks [38].

Source term As already stated in Sec. 3.1.2.2 the main astrophysical production mechanism of antiprotons is due spallation of primary proton or helium nuclei cosmic rays on interstellar hydrogen or helium. The resulting source term of the proton-hydrogen spallation on the transport equation's right-hand side can be casted in the following form

$$Q_{\bar{p}}^{\text{sec}}(E_{\bar{p}}, \vec{r}) = 2h\delta(z) \int_{E_{\bar{p}}}^{\infty} \frac{d\sigma(pH \rightarrow \bar{p}X)}{dE_{\bar{p}}} (E_{\text{p}} \rightarrow E_{\bar{p}}) n_{\text{H}}(\vec{r}) v_{\text{p}} f_{\text{p}}(E_{\text{p}}, \vec{r}) dE_{\text{p}}, \quad (3.2.5)$$

²Usually, all of these energy losses are neglected in the case of antiprotons. Nevertheless, the authors of [38] explicitly included these terms to account for the upcoming results of the AMS-02 satellite.

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where $d\sigma(pH \rightarrow \bar{p}X)/dE_{\bar{p}}$ denotes the differential cross-section of this specific spallation process with respect to the antiproton's total energy $E_{\bar{p}}$, $f_p(E_p, \vec{r})$ refers to the proton density inside the magnetic halo, v_p is the protons velocity and E_p is the threshold energy of this process which was discussed previously. The exact treatment and determination of the differential cross-section and proton density are given in [38] as well as the corresponding terms for the spallation of protons on helium or the spallation of helium nuclei on interstellar matter.

In addition to the direct production of antiprotons, collision of primary cosmic rays with the interstellar medium also generate a non-negligible flux of antineutrons which, of course, are unstable and decay into antiprotons on their way through the galaxy. Assuming isospin symmetry, the antineutron production rates are supposed to be equal to their corresponding antiproton counterparts such that the antiproton source terms have to be multiplied with a factor of 2. Nonetheless, as pointed out in [99], this simple reasoning seems not to hold true which fact is taken into consideration by introducing a normalization constant A in front of the astrophysical source term of antiprotons in Eq. 3.2.5.

Finally, there is a third source term reflecting the possibility of inelastic, non-annihilating interactions of secondary astrophysical antiprotons with the interstellar medium which was pointed out in Sec. 3.1.2.2. The effect of such interactions is a mere reinjection of the antiprotons into the flux with now lower kinetic energies. These antiprotons are called tertiary antiprotons and their production source term is given by

$$Q_{\bar{p}}^{\text{ter}}(E_{\bar{p}}, \vec{r}) = 2h\delta(z) \left[\int_{E_p}^{\infty} \frac{d\sigma(\bar{p}p \rightarrow \bar{p}X)}{dE_{\bar{p}}} (E'_p \rightarrow E_{\bar{p}}) n_{\text{H}}(\vec{r}) v'_p f_p(E'_p, \vec{r}) dE'_p \right. \\ \left. - \sigma_{\bar{p}p \rightarrow \bar{p}X}(E_{\bar{p}}) n_{\text{H}}(\vec{r}) v_p f_p(E_{\bar{p}}, \vec{r}) \right],$$

where $d\sigma(\bar{p}p \rightarrow \bar{p}X)/dE_{\bar{p}}$ denotes the differential cross-section of the antiprotons' inelastic, non-annihilating interactions with the interstellar matter and, again, the further treatment is given in [38]. In general, the term in the second line dominates at high energies whereas the term in the first line has its largest impact on low-energy antiprotons such that the overall antiproton flux is shifted towards lower energies.

Energy loss terms In the case of antiprotons mainly three distinct processes lead to an energy loss. On one side, high-energy antiprotons are able to ionize neutral molecules inside the interstellar medium and suffer from these ionization energy losses and, on the other side, Coulomb energy losses might occur through antiproton collisions on the totally ionized plasma of the interstellar medium. In the first case, the relevant molecules are hydrogen and helium whereas in the second process mainly thermal electrons inside the plasma are of importance. Explicit formulæ of the corresponding energy loss rate $b(T)$ are provided in [119].

The third source of energy losses originates from the convection of antiprotons in the two-zone model due to the galactic wind because the antiproton cosmic ray density must be conserved in phase-space. The corresponding energy loss rate reads [38]

$$b_{\text{adiab}}(T) = -\frac{V_C p^2}{3h E},$$

where momentum and total energy of the antiproton is denoted by p or E , respectively.

Having gathered together all ingredients of the transport equation specified to the case of antiprotons, their propagated fluxes for the three parameter sets MIN, MED and MAX are found by numerical simulations. These solutions are given in [38] in terms of a fit function that reproduces the numerical results in the kinetic energy range from 0.2 GeV to 800 GeV with an uncertainty of only 5%. We restate here their fit function and its parameters in Tab.3.2.3 to have a concise reference for further analyses. It is given by

$$\log_{10}(\Phi_{\bar{p}}^{\text{bkgrd}}(T)) = \sum_{n=0}^8 a_n \left[\log_{10} \left(\frac{T}{\text{GeV}} \right) \right]^n. \quad (3.2.6)$$

We want to state two concluding remarks: At first, Eq.3.2.6 is calculated assuming $A = 1$, i.e. the production cross-section of antiprotons and antineutrons due to spallations on the interstellar matter are equal and secondly, this solution of the transport equation is only valid until the antiprotons enter the reach of the Sun. Inside the heliosphere an additional effect explained in Sec.3.2.3 has to be taken into consideration.

parameter set	a_0	a_1	a_2	a_3	a_4	a_5	a_6	a_7	a_8
MIN	-1.5116	0.37991	-0.69686	-0.92051	0.17873	0.34161	-0.19910	0.04154	-0.00309
MED	-1.5079	0.34279	-0.71347	-0.89053	0.18914	0.32518	-0.19223	0.04022	-0.00299
MAX	-1.6192	0.34986	-0.69943	-0.86758	0.19016	0.30858	-0.18192	0.03777	-0.00279

Table 3.2.3: Coefficients of the fit function Eq. 3.2.6 determining the propagated flux of antiprotons of the astrophysical background in the two-zone diffusion model for three distinct parameter sets MIN, MED and MAX [38].

3.2.2.4 Antiproton Propagation for the Dark Matter Contribution

Finding the propagated flux of antiprotons from dark matter decays can be done completely analogously to the case of the astrophysical background by changing only the source term to

$$Q_{\bar{p}}^{\text{DM}}(\vec{r}, T) = \frac{\rho_{\text{DM}}(\vec{r})}{m_{\text{DM}}} \sum_f \Gamma_f \left(\frac{dN_{\bar{p}}}{dT} \right)_f. \quad (3.2.7)$$

We adopt here the notation of the photon fluxes such that the sum runs over all decay channels f with partial decay width Γ_f of the dark matter particle that produces antiprotons and $(dN_{\bar{p}}/dT)_f$ is the respective antiproton spectrum per decay event. This approach was chosen in [38] where the authors provide the numerical results of their simulations. Unfortunately, the source term in Eq. 3.2.7 depends on the knowledge of the spectra of antiprotons in certain dark matter decay channels. Since we will examine trilinear decays which are not part of the canonical decay channels usually investigated in the literature, there is no result available that would be suitable for our purposes.

In order to, nonetheless, solve the transport equation, we make a few additional assumptions, namely: The energy losses introduced in the case of the astrophysical antiproton background are all negligible, the tertiary production of antiprotons is considered as a sink term, i.e. any inelastic, non-annihilating scattering of antiprotons on the interstellar matter is removing the antiprotons from the flux and eventually, there are no reaccelerations due to Alfvén waves.³ These simplifications applied to the transport equation in the two-zone diffusion model leads to an analytic solution [104] which can be universally used for any dark matter decay channel if the respective antiproton spectrum is known. This solution reads [48]

$$\frac{d\Phi_{\bar{p}}^{\text{DM}}(T)}{dT} = \frac{v_{\bar{p}}}{4\pi} \frac{\rho_{\odot}}{m_{\text{DM}}} R(T) \sum_f \left(\frac{dN_{\bar{p}}}{dT} \right)_f \Gamma_f \quad (3.2.8)$$

³These two assumptions are actually very common in the available literature.

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and is, again, only valid until the antiproton reaches the boundary of the Sun's heliosphere. The antiproton's velocity is given by

$$v_{\bar{p}} = c \sqrt{1 - \frac{m_{\bar{p}}^2}{(T + m_{\bar{p}})^2}}. \quad (3.2.9)$$

The function $R(T)$ contains all astrophysical input and depends on the chosen parameter set of the two-zone model and on the choice of the dark matter density profile in the Milky Way ρ_{DM} . The function $R(T)$ is formally given by

$$R(T) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} J_0 \left(\zeta_n \frac{r_{\odot}}{R} \right) \exp \left[-\frac{V_C L}{2\mathcal{K}(T)} \right] \frac{y_n(L)}{A_n \sinh(S_n L/2)},$$

with

$$y_n(z) = \frac{4}{J_1(\zeta_n)^2 R^2} \int_0^R r J_0 \left(\zeta_n \frac{r}{R} \right) \int_0^z \exp \left[-\frac{V_C(z-z')}{2\mathcal{K}(T)} \right] \times \\ \times \sinh \left[S_n(z-z')/2 \right] \left(\frac{\rho_{\text{DM}}(r, z')}{\rho_{\odot}} \right)^2 dz' dr$$

and the coefficients

$$S_n = \left(\frac{V_C^2}{\mathcal{K}(T)^2} + 4 \frac{\zeta_n^2}{R^2} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}, \\ A_n = 2h\Gamma^{\text{ann}} + V_C + \mathcal{K}(T) S_n \coth(S_n L/2)$$

account for the effects of the diffusion processes. Here J_i denotes the i -th Bessel function of the first kind and ζ_n refers to the n -th root of the Bessel function J_0 . Computing the function $R(T)$ is extremely cumbersome since it involves infinite sums. Therefore, the authors of [48] provide a fit function for $R(T)$ with respect to a particular parameter set and dark matter density profile. These fit functions seem to reproduce the analytic results in the range of 0.1 GeV to 100 TeV with an error of about 6%. Thus, we will adopt in this theses their fit function

$$\log_{10} \left[\frac{R(T)}{1 \cdot 10^6 \text{ yr}} \right] = \sum_{n=0}^5 a_n \kappa^n \quad (3.2.10)$$

with $\kappa = \log_{10}(T/\text{GeV})$ and coefficients stated in Tab. 3.2.4 for all relevant cases.

3.2 Deriving Theoretical Predictions for Cosmic Ray Fluxes

density profile	parameter set	a_0	a_1	a_2	a_3	a_4	a_5
NFW	MIN	0.9175	0.6429	-0.3121	-0.0910	0.0406	-0.0039
	MED	1.7507	0.3892	-0.3101	-0.0070	0.0151	-0.0016
	MAX	2.4353	-0.1549	-0.1004	0.0144	-0.0007	-0.0000
Einasto	MIN	0.9177	0.6436	-0.3130	-0.0904	0.0404	-0.0039
	MED	1.7554	0.3959	-0.3096	-0.0082	0.0154	-0.0017
	MAX	2.4466	-0.1543	-0.1007	0.0144	-0.0007	-0.0000
Isothermal	MIN	0.9171	0.6434	-0.3134	-0.0903	0.0404	-0.0039
	MED	1.7450	0.3770	-0.3128	-0.0033	0.0142	-0.0016
	MAX	2.4095	-0.1580	-0.0988	0.0139	-0.0006	-0.0000
Burkert	MIN	0.9165	0.6419	-0.3141	-0.0898	0.0403	-0.0039
	MED	1.7352	0.3616	-0.3150	0.0006	0.0132	-0.0015
	MAX	2.3956	-0.1570	-0.0998	0.0144	-0.0007	0.0000
Moore	MIN	0.9179	0.6431	-0.3132	-0.0902	0.0404	-0.0038
	MED	1.7534	0.3933	-0.3095	-0.0077	0.0153	-0.0017
	MAX	2.4430	-0.1541	-0.1001	0.0144	-0.0009	0.0000

Table 3.2.4: Coefficients of the fit function describing the solution $R(T)$ of the transport equation for antiprotons for different dark matter density profiles and parameter sets of propagation. The values are taken from [48].

3.2.2.5 Antideuteron Propagation for the Dark Matter Contribution

The description of the propagation of antideuterons, based on the transport equation, very much coincides with the one of antiprotons. In fact, we only need to change the source term on the right-hand side of this equation to

$$Q_{\bar{d}}^{\text{DM}}(\vec{r}, T) = \frac{\rho_{\text{DM}}(\vec{r})}{m_{\text{DM}}} \sum_f \Gamma_f \left(\frac{dN_{\bar{d}}}{dT} \right)_f,$$

where $\left[\frac{dN_{\bar{d}}}{dT} \right]_f$ denotes the injection spectrum of the antideuterons with respect to the decay channel f . Having gathered all information that is necessary for the source term, the transport equation needs only a few minor changes with respect to the propagation of antiprotons, namely: We have to replace the mass, velocity and momentum of the antiproton with the corresponding quantity of the antideuteron. Moreover, dark matter antideuterons are also able to react with interstellar hydrogen and helium via annihilations or inelastic, non-annihilating scatterings. Thus, we need to insert the expected cross-section for these processes which are far less known than the corresponding antiproton cross-sections. As a satisfying approxima-

3 Indirect Searches for Dark Matter

density profile	parameter set	a_0	a_1	a_2	a_3	a_4	a_5
NFW	MIN	1.0097	0.4282	-0.3575	-0.0378	0.0297	-0.0033
	MED	1.7536	0.2154	-0.2937	0.0116	0.0098	-0.0013
	MAX	2.3010	-0.1861	-0.0833	0.0155	-0.0026	0.0003
Einasto	MIN	1.0097	0.4282	-0.3575	-0.0378	0.0297	-0.0033
	MED	1.7591	0.2216	-0.2935	0.0107	0.0100	-0.0013
	MAX	2.3119	-0.1852	-0.0835	0.0155	-0.0026	0.0002
Isothermal	MIN	1.0097	0.4282	-0.3575	-0.0378	0.0297	-0.0033
	MED	1.7445	0.2035	-0.2936	0.0138	0.0091	-0.0012
	MAX	2.2758	-0.1893	-0.0818	0.0151	-0.0026	0.0002
Burkert	MIN	1.0097	0.4282	-0.3575	-0.0378	0.0297	-0.0033
	MED	1.7291	0.1891	-0.2922	0.0156	0.0085	-0.0011
	MAX	2.2631	-0.1893	-0.0826	0.0157	-0.0027	0.0003
Moore	MIN	1.0097	0.4282	-0.3575	-0.0378	0.0297	-0.0033
	MED	1.7564	0.2193	-0.2931	0.0110	0.0099	-0.0013
	MAX	2.3085	-0.1848	-0.0830	0.0153	-0.0028	0.0003

Table 3.2.5: Coefficients of the fit function describing the solution $R_{\bar{d}}(T)$ of the transport equation for antideuterons for different dark matter density profiles and parameter sets of propagation. The values are taken from [48].

tion, it is assumed that the antideuteron cross-sections are two times the respective antiproton values [39].

These adjustments lead to a slightly changed analytic solution of the transport equation which yields the following flux of antideuterons:

$$\frac{d\Phi_{\bar{d}}^{\text{DM}}(T)}{d(T/n)} = \frac{v_{\bar{d}}}{4\pi} \frac{\rho_{\odot}}{m_{\text{DM}}} R_{\bar{d}}(T/n) \sum_f \left(\frac{dN_{\bar{d}}}{d(T/n)} \right)_f \Gamma_f. \quad (3.2.11)$$

It is a common approach in the literature to state these fluxes in terms of kinetic energy per nucleon as denoted by T/n with n referring to the number of nucleons, i.e. $n = 2$ in the case of antideuterons. Again, the function $R_{\bar{d}}(T/n)$ contains all astrophysical input and is given by the authors of [48] in terms of the fit function

$$\log_{10} \left[\frac{R_{\bar{d}}(T/n)}{1 \cdot 10^6 \text{ yr}} \right] = \sum_{n=0}^5 a_n \kappa_d^n \quad (3.2.12)$$

with $\kappa_d := \log_{10}[(T/n)/\text{GeV}]$ and the values of the coefficients are reported in Tab. 3.2.5.

However, the crucial task considering indirect searches with antideuterons is the determination of their energy spectra $dN_{\bar{d}}/dT$ per decay event. As mentioned beforehand, the formation of antideuterons is described within the coalescence model which permits, irrespective of the underlying microscopic formation mechanism, the merging of an antiproton and an antineutron whenever the magnitude of their three-momentum difference is smaller than a maximal momentum p_0 . Such a condition is easily implemented on an event-by-event basis in Monte Carlo simulations of dark matter decays. Nonetheless, the coalescence model had been developed before Monte Carlo simulations became available such that there are approaches taking the individual energy spectra of antiprotons and antineutrons into account: A common approximation is the isotropic (or factorized) approach, where it is assumed that the distributions of final state antiprotons and antineutrons are spherically symmetric and uncorrelated in momentum space [42]. From this assumption one then derives the antideuteron energy spectrum which depends on the product of the antiprotons' and antineutrons' energy spectra according to [21, 39, 88]

$$\left. \left(\frac{dN_{\bar{d}}}{dT} \right) \right|_{T=T_{\bar{d}}} = \frac{p_0^3}{6} \frac{m_{\bar{d}}}{m_{\bar{p}}m_{\bar{n}}} \frac{1}{\sqrt{T_{\bar{d}}^2 + 2T_{\bar{d}}m_{\bar{d}}}} \left. \left(\frac{dN_{\bar{p}}}{dT} \right) \right|_{T_{\bar{p}}=\frac{T_{\bar{d}}}{2}} \left. \left(\frac{dN_{\bar{n}}}{dT} \right) \right|_{T_{\bar{n}}=\frac{T_{\bar{d}}}{2}}. \quad (3.2.13)$$

We will use this method to determine the antideuteron spectra, albeit it is well-known that it produces qualitatively wrong results that heavily underestimate the real antideuteron yields in high-energy processes [21]. A simple argument, why it must be qualitatively wrong, is the following: Since only the product of antiproton and antineutron spectra is taken into consideration, it follows that nucleons from distinct dark matter decays can form an antideuteron which is certainly impossible for a very-long lived dark matter particle. Nevertheless, this approach is sufficient for our purposes, as we want to provide prospects on the sensitivity of the antideuteron cosmic ray channel to hypothetic signals from the minimal dark matter model we discuss later.

Finally, we need to fix the value of the coalescence momentum p_0 . In principle, its value is determined via Monte Carlo simulations of antideuteron formation in certain processes where experimental data are available to test and tune this parameter. As discussed in [54, 57] the best fit results of p_0 heavily depend on the event generator (PYTHIA6, PYTHIA8 or HERWIG++) used to simulate the processes as well as on the chosen realization of the coalescence model, i.e. whether the event-by-event analysis or the isotropic model was applied. We will use $p_0 = 141_{-16}^{+14}$ MeV as reported in

[57] where the calibration of p_0 was done with respect to the ALEPH measurements [117] of the antideuteron yield in e^+e^- -collisions at the Z^0 -resonance. However, this result relies on the event generator PYTHIA6 which is the previous version of PYTHIA8 that we want to work with. Unfortunately, in the literature there seems to be no dedicated study of the isotropic model using PYTHIA8, only results based on event-by-event analyses are available. Nevertheless, by crosschecking the results found in [70, 97, 89] from event-by-event approaches using PYTHIA6 or PYTHIA8 we observe that both event generators produce compatible best fit values of p_0 . In this sense, we do not introduce large errors by adopting a coalescence momentum derived from PYTHIA6 studies.

3.2.3 Propagation of Charged Particles inside the Heliosphere

A last ingredient is necessary to find a charged particle's flux at the Earth's position. The transport equation's solution is only valid until the cosmic rays reach the heliosphere. Henceforth, the charged particles of the Sun's solar wind decelerate the cosmic ray particles where low-energetic particles, i.e. $\lesssim 10$ GeV, are more severely affected. This phenomenon is called solar modulation and usually solved in the charge-independent "force-field-approximation" [81, 82]. This description involves the propagated cosmic ray fluxes at the heliospheric boundary $d\Phi_{\text{LIS}}/dT$ to obtain the flux at the Earth's position $d\Phi_{\oplus}/dT$ given by [38]

$$\frac{d\Phi_{\oplus}(T)}{dT} = \frac{d\Phi_{\text{LIS}}\left(T + \frac{|Z|e\phi_{\text{F}}}{A_m}\right)}{dT} \frac{T(T+2m)}{\left(T + m + \frac{|Z|e\phi_{\text{F}}}{A_m}\right)^2 - m^2}, \quad (3.2.14)$$

where m denotes the charged particle's mass, A_m its mass number, $|Z|e$ the absolute value of its electric charge and ϕ_{F} the force-field potential in units of GV which parameterizes all solar modulation effects on the cosmic rays. The value of this quantity, also called Fisk potential, heavily depends on the solar activity. Therefore, it must be chosen according to the operation period of the respective experiment whose data are used for indirect searches. For instance, the PAMELA satellite operated during the end of the 2000s where a phase of minimal solar activity was reached. Therefore, a value of $\phi_{\text{F}} = 0.5$ GeV should be used [48]. Moreover, a maximum of solar activity is characterized by a value of $\phi_{\text{F}} = 1.3$ GeV and a transient period by $\phi_{\text{F}} = 0.7$ GeV [61].

3.2 Deriving Theoretical Predictions for Cosmic Ray Fluxes

parameter set	ϕ_F [GV]	A
MIN	0.74	1.22
MED	0.70	1.24
MAX	0.38	1.25

Table 3.2.6: Best fit values with respect to the 2013 PAMELA data [12] for the Fisk potential and normalization of the astrophysical antiproton background as computed in [38].

By invoking Eq. 3.2.14, solar modulation can easily be applied to the antiproton fluxes derived in the previous sections as they represent the necessary fluxes at the heliospheric boundary. Nevertheless, the suitable choice of the Fisk potential is still a problem. We solve this problem by adopting the findings of [38]: The authors fitted the results of their astrophysical background to the PAMELA data [12] by using solar modulation as given above and declaring ϕ_F as well as A (c.f. Sec. 3.2.2.3) as free parameters. We will use their reported best-fit values of these parameters, presented in Tab. 3.2.6, to reproduce their antiproton background solutions and to fix the Fisk potential that is used in the case of dark matter contributions.

All studies with respect to antideuteron channel will be conducted with a value of $\phi_F = 0.5$ GeV since we include the astrophysical background of antideuterons given in [89] which was derived using this choice of Fisk potential.

4 A Minimal Model of Decaying Dark Matter

This chapter introduces a quite general model of unstable dark matter that is different from the usual approaches summarized in Sec. 2.3. We elucidate the consequences of the dark matter's instability in terms of possible interactions with ordinary standard model matter and calculate total and differential decay widths of R -parity violating trilinear decays. Additionally, we state already existing results about the cosmological history of this model.

4.1 The Model Lagrangian and its Interactions

Dark matter models do not necessarily have to feature a completely stabilized dark matter particle since there is no evidence for a general principle guaranteeing such a stability. As a matter of fact, this stability is in many cases achieved by an unbroken symmetry of the underlying theory such as the conservation of electric charge that leads to a stable electron [74]. However, even without such unbroken symmetries, the dark matter particle of the specific model must be very long-lived exceeding even cosmological timescales in order to account for the observed dark matter density in the universe and to yield signals in accordance with astrophysical observations. Establishing such a very long-lived particle implies in return that its couplings to ordinary matter must be very weak. Due to the fact that no stabilizing symmetry is necessary, the dark matter particle might interact with standard and non-standard model particles as a single state.

A viable realization of a decaying dark matter candidate was outlined in [22] where the authors introduced a rather minimal theory¹, featuring a standard model singlet

¹It should be noted that this model shares many similarities with a decaying dark matter model introduced in [73, 74, 75]. We will make use of this fact by comparing our results to the corresponding ones given in these references.

Majorana dark matter particle ψ and a heavy scalar particle Σ_f which is supposed to be charged under at least one of the standard model's gauge groups and which possesses a mass m_Σ much larger than the mass of the dark matter particle m_ψ . For simplicity, the couplings between these two additional particles and the content of the standard model are of a renormalizable Yukawa-type depending on the choice of the scalar particle's quantum numbers:

$$L_{\text{eff}} = \lambda_{\psi f L} \bar{\psi} f_L \Sigma_f^\dagger + \lambda_{\psi f R} \bar{\psi} f_R \Sigma_f^\dagger + \text{h.c.} \quad (4.1.1)$$

To be more precise, the subscript f on Σ_f indicates that the quantum numbers of this heavy scalar depend on those of the standard model chiral fermion f which shall interact with the dark sector and can be chosen arbitrarily. The chirality of this fermion is respected via the couplings in Eq. 4.1.1 that do not have to coincide necessarily. In accordance with the minimality principle, only one scalar Σ_f is introduced which, hence, demands the appearance of only one of the chirality couplings $\lambda_{\psi f L}$ or $\lambda_{\psi f R}$ at a time depending on the scalar's $SU(2)$ quantum numbers. As another consequence, the dark matter particle either couples to quarks or to leptons according to whether the scalar carries color or electroweak charge. Besides, this feature gives rise to a classification of possible model realizations into hadronic or leptonic dark matter models.

Since no stabilizing symmetry was introduced, the scalar will decay into two standard model fermions according to a handful of operators depending on its quantum numbers [23]. By denoting the quantum numbers of the scalar field as ordered tuples with respect to the standard model's symmetry group $SU(3)_C \times SU(2)_L \times U(1)_Y$, the effective Lagrangians reads

$$\begin{aligned} L_{\text{eff}} &= \lambda'_q \bar{d} l \Sigma_q + \text{h.c.} & \Sigma_q &= \left(3, 2, \frac{1}{3}\right) \\ L_{\text{eff}} &= \lambda''_u \bar{d} d^c \Sigma_u^\dagger + \text{h.c.} & \Sigma_u &= \left(3, 1, \frac{4}{3}\right) \\ L_{\text{eff}} &= \lambda'_{d,1} \bar{q} l^c \Sigma_d + \lambda'_{d,2} \bar{u} e^c \Sigma_d + \lambda''_{d,1} \bar{u} d^c \Sigma_d^\dagger + \lambda''_{d,2} \bar{q} q^c \Sigma_d^\dagger + \text{h.c.} & \Sigma_d &= \left(3, 1, -\frac{2}{3}\right) \\ L_{\text{eff}} &= \lambda_l \bar{e} l \Sigma_l + \lambda'_{l,1} \bar{d} q \Sigma_l + \lambda'_{l,2} \bar{u} q \tilde{\Sigma}_l + \text{h.c.} & \Sigma_l &= (1, 2, -1) \\ L_{\text{eff}} &= \lambda_e \bar{l} l^c \Sigma_e + \text{h.c.} & \Sigma_e &= (1, 1, -2), \end{aligned} \quad (4.1.2)$$

where q and l represent the standard model $SU(2)_L$ left-handed doublets as well as u , d and e the SM $SU(2)_L$ right-handed singlets, the superscript c indicates the charge conjugated field with the charge conjugation matrix C , e.g. $d^c = C(\bar{d})^T$ and $\tilde{\Sigma}_f = i\sigma_2 \Sigma_f^*$.

Although Eq. 4.1.2 allows several operators for a certain choice of quantum numbers, due to the minimality principle, we assume that only one of these is present at a time and we assume no flavor-mixing given a particular operator. Hence, we have only hadronic models (Σ_q , Σ_u and Σ_d) or leptonic models (Σ_l and Σ_e). Besides, all flavor indices are suppressed even though operators containing products $\bar{q}q^c$ and $\bar{l}l^c$ must be antisymmetric in flavor and they must vanish in case of a single generation. Since the scalar field carries non-vanishing standard model charges, it does also couple to the respective standard model gauge bosons and couplings to the Higgs boson could be present, additionally. Nonetheless, we neglect all interaction schemes with the Higgs boson and the possibility that the neutral component of Σ_l could acquire a non-vanishing vacuum expectation value [62].

By minimality, the model's setting is fully characterized by four distinct parameters: The mass of the dark matter particle m_ψ , the mass of the heavy scalar m_Σ , the coupling λ_ψ and the scalar's coupling λ . In the following, we will keep this notation, i.e. the Yukawa coupling of Eq. 4.1.1 is always denoted by λ_ψ whereas the respective Yukawa coupling of Eq. 4.1.2 is referred to as λ . Any deviation from this notation will be stated clearly.

R -parity The designation of primes to the Yukawa-couplings in Eq. 4.1.2 is not arbitrary but motivated by a quantity of supersymmetric theories. As we do not intend to give an introduction to supersymmetry, we refer to suitable coherent reviews in [28, 102].

Among all standard model interactions, there is no process that violates the difference ($B - L$) of baryon number B and lepton number L which we used beforehand, for instance, to derive statements about the threshold of antiproton production in cosmic ray spallations on the interstellar medium. In fact, this conservation is pure coincidence because it was not an assumption of the standard model. In the minimal supersymmetric standard model (MSSM) this conservation is not guaranteed and can be violated which would lead to proton decays [66, 67]. In order to avoid these peculiarities, the supersymmetric theory at hand is enlarged by a multiplicatively conserved quantity, the so-called R -parity. This parity is assigned to the full

particle content of the theory and it is given as a multiplicative quantum number

$$R_p = (-1)^{3(B-L)+2s},$$

where s denotes the spin of the respective particle. In the MSSM each standard model particle has even R -parity ($R_p = +1$) whereas each supersymmetric partner is assigned odd R -parity ($R_p = -1$). Thus, any supersymmetric particle cannot decay into standard model particles alone and their production by standard model particles happens only pairwise. This has far reaching consequences, like the stability of the lightest supersymmetric particle which is supposed to be a viable dark matter candidate if it is electrically neutral.

In full generality, supersymmetric theories contain R -parity violating (RPV) operators. Even the simplest example of the MSSM features a superpotential $W_{\cancel{R_p}}$ with gauge invariant and renormalizable but yet R -parity violating operators [102]

$$W_{\cancel{R_p}} = \frac{1}{2}\lambda_{ijk}L^iL^j(E^c)^k + \lambda'_{ijk}L^iQ^j(D^c)^k + \frac{1}{2}\lambda''_{ijk}(U^c)^i(D^c)^j(D^c)^k + \mu_i H_u L^i.$$

In this superpotential summing over the generation indices $i, j, k = 1, 2, 3$ and over the suppressed gauge indices is understood. Furthermore, the couplings λ_{ijk} must be antisymmetric in the first two indices and the couplings λ''_{ijk} must be antisymmetric in the last two indices due to gauge invariance. Obviously, all terms containing a coupling λ_{ijk} , λ'_{ijk} or μ_i must violate the lepton number whereas terms connected to λ''_{ijk} violate baryon number. These R -parity violating couplings are severely constrained by the non-observation of proton decays where the present lower bound on its lifetime τ_p is $\tau_p > 2.1 \cdot 10^{29}$ yr [108]. As a consequence, either all baryon number or all lepton number violating terms are absent, or they are extremely small and suppressed.

A comparison of the RPV superpotential and the operators in Eq. 4.1.2 reveals some similarities, i.e. our minimal model includes RPV interactions and the Yukawa couplings are named such that they indicate the term in the superpotential which might be their origin in a supersymmetric theory. Nonetheless, we want to stress that the minimal decaying dark matter model as introduced above is not supersymmetric, it is rather inspired by supersymmetry.

4.2 Calculation of Differential Decay Rates

The Lagrangian of the minimal model leads to a set of trilinear R -parity violating decays of the dark matter particle ψ because of the restriction $m_\psi \ll m_\Sigma$ that causes an off-shell scalar. In the following we want to investigate a subset of these decays which provide promising prospects with respect to indirect searches in the antiproton, gamma-ray and antideuteron channels. In particular, within the hadronic models the set of the dark matter's daughter particles includes at least two quarks such that we expect a sizable antiproton yield after the hadronization of the decay products. From the amount of available operators, we fix the scalar field to be Σ_d and choose the operators linked to the Yukawa couplings $\lambda'_{d,1}$ as well as $\lambda''_{d,1}$ in Eq. 4.1.2. By limiting ourselves to these two operators, we do not lose any additional decay mode of the hadronic models which are formally given by

$$\begin{aligned}\psi &\longrightarrow \bar{u}dl^+ \left(u\bar{d}l^- \right), \\ \psi &\longrightarrow udd \left(\bar{u}\bar{d}\bar{d} \right), \\ \psi &\longrightarrow d\bar{d}\nu \left(d\bar{d}\bar{\nu} \right),\end{aligned}$$

where l denotes an arbitrary charged lepton and ν , due to the exclusion of flavor-mixing, denotes the corresponding neutrino of the same generation. This reasoning also applies to the down-type quark d and the corresponding up-type quark u .

To study the implications of these dark matter decays on the cosmic ray channels in question, we need the energy spectra dN/dE of the respective particles. This task is simple as long as the considered final state particle is a direct decay product because in this case

$$\frac{dN}{dE} = \frac{1}{\Gamma} \frac{d\Gamma}{dE}, \quad (4.2.1)$$

where Γ denotes the decay rate of the decay channel and $d\Gamma/dE$ denotes the corresponding differential decay rate.

For a two- and three-body decay, this differential decay rate can be calculated analytically. But in fact, none of the direct daughter particles of these decay modes include a cosmic ray channel we want to consider with respect to indirect searches. Nonetheless, we will perform the calculations of the differential and total decay rates of these processes since they are, on one side, a useful tool to check the consistency of the machinery accomplishing the hadronization of the decay events (which we discuss later) and, on the other side, we will need the total decay rates Γ_ψ to translate

Figure 4.2.1: Tree-level Feynman diagrams contributing to the decay $\psi \rightarrow udd$ involving one up and two down quarks. Diagrams (a) and (b) reflect the interchanging of the two down quarks leading to interference terms. Furthermore, we depict the definitions of momenta p , k_1 , k_2 and k_3 together with the fermion flow. Likewise, the color algebra is respected via Greek subscripts and spin states are denoted as r , t_1 , t_2 and t_3 .

lifetime constraints τ_ψ on the dark matter particle via

$$\tau_\psi = \frac{1}{\Gamma_\psi}$$

into constraints on the parameters of the underlying model configuration.

The crucial ingredient to conduct the calculation of decay rates is the set of Feynman rules that are derived from the model's Lagrangian according to the choice of operators we made. These Feynman rules are explicitly stated in Appendix C.1. Moreover, we will only consider tree-level Feynman diagrams contributing to the respective decay channel. Subsequently, we show the calculation for the decay $\psi \rightarrow udd$ ($\bar{u}d\bar{d}$) in detail and solely present the results for the remaining channels; their explicit derivations are, nonetheless, given in Appendix C.3.

4.2.1 The Decay Mode $\psi \rightarrow udd$

There are two tree-level diagrams contributing to this particular decay channel where the second one is derived from the first one by exchanging the two indistinguishable down-type quarks of the same generation. Fig. 4.2.1 depicts these diagrams including the definitions of momenta and spins used in the subsequent calculations.

We denote by $i\mathcal{M}_a$ the amplitude corresponding to the diagram in Fig. 4.2.1a and denote by $i\mathcal{M}_b$ the respective amplitude of Fig. 4.2.1b. These amplitudes are then

read off using the Feynman rules stated in Appendix C.1 which yields

$$i\mathcal{M}_a = \frac{i\lambda_{\psi dR}\lambda''_{d,1}\varepsilon_{\alpha\gamma\beta}}{(p-k_1)^2 - m_\Sigma^2} [\bar{u}_\alpha(k_1; t_1) P_L u(p; r)] [\bar{u}_\gamma(k_2; t_2) P_L \gamma^0 C u_\beta^*(k_3; t_3)], \quad (4.2.2)$$

$$i\mathcal{M}_b = \frac{i\lambda_{\psi dR}\lambda''_{d,1}\varepsilon_{\beta\gamma\alpha}}{(p-k_3)^2 - m_\Sigma^2} [\bar{u}_\beta(k_3; t_3) P_L u(p; r)] [\bar{u}_\gamma(k_2; t_2) P_L \gamma^0 C u_\alpha^*(k_1; t_1)]. \quad (4.2.3)$$

The total amplitude is obtained by taking the sum of the single amplitudes in Eqs. 4.2.2 and 4.2.3. However, respecting the odd permutation of the down-type quark while going from $i\mathcal{M}_a$ to $i\mathcal{M}_b$, there must be a relative minus sign in this sum, i.e.:

$$i\mathcal{M} = i\mathcal{M}_a - i\mathcal{M}_b. \quad (4.2.4)$$

The squared amplitude of this process can be written as follows

$$|\mathcal{M}|^2 = |\mathcal{M}_a|^2 + |\mathcal{M}_b|^2 - 2\Re(\mathcal{M}_a\mathcal{M}_b^*). \quad (4.2.5)$$

For the further treatment of the squared matrix element, we rewrite the single squared amplitudes in terms of traces over the spinor indices which we exemplify on $\mathcal{M}_a\mathcal{M}_b^*$ by using the short-hand notation introduced in Eq. C.2.2 in Appendix C.2 and the identities listed in Appendix B.3:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{M}_a\mathcal{M}_b^* &= \frac{|\lambda_{\psi dR}|^2 |\lambda''_{d,1}|^2 \varepsilon_{\alpha\gamma\beta} \bar{\varepsilon}_{\beta'\gamma'\alpha'}}{(s_1 - m_\Sigma^2)(s_3 - m_\Sigma^2)} [\bar{u}_\alpha(k_1; t_1) P_L u(p; r)] [\bar{u}_\gamma(k_2; t_2) P_L \gamma^0 C u_\beta^*(k_3; t_3)] \times \\ &\quad \times [\bar{u}_{\gamma'}(k_2; t_2) P_L \gamma^0 C u_{\alpha'}^*(k_1; t_1)]^\dagger [\bar{u}_{\beta'}(k_3; t_3) P_L u(p; r)]^\dagger \\ &= \frac{|\lambda_{\psi dR}|^2 |\lambda''_{d,1}|^2 \varepsilon_{\alpha\gamma\beta} \bar{\varepsilon}_{\beta'\gamma'\alpha'}}{(s_1 - m_\Sigma^2)(s_3 - m_\Sigma^2)} [\bar{u}_\alpha(k_1; t_1) P_L u(p; r)] [\bar{u}_\gamma(k_2; t_2) P_L \gamma^0 C u_\beta^*(k_3; t_3)] \times \\ &\quad \times [u_{\alpha'}^T(k_1; t_1) C^\dagger \gamma^0 P_L \gamma^0 u_{\gamma'}(k_2; t_2)] [u^\dagger(p; r) P_L \gamma^0 u_{\beta'}(k_3; t_3)] \\ &= \frac{|\lambda_{\psi dR}|^2 |\lambda''_{d,1}|^2 \varepsilon_{\alpha\gamma\beta} \bar{\varepsilon}_{\beta'\gamma'\alpha'}}{(s_1 - m_\Sigma^2)(s_3 - m_\Sigma^2)} [\bar{u}_\alpha(k_1; t_1) P_L u(p; r)] [\bar{u}_\gamma(k_2; t_2) P_L \gamma^0 C u_\beta^*(k_3; t_3)] \times \\ &\quad \times [u_{\alpha'}^T(k_1; t_1) C P_R u_{\gamma'}(k_2; t_2)] [\bar{u}(p; r) P_R u_{\beta'}(k_3; t_3)] \\ &= \frac{|\lambda_{\psi dR}|^2 |\lambda''_{d,1}|^2 \varepsilon_{\alpha\gamma\beta} \bar{\varepsilon}_{\beta'\gamma'\alpha'}}{(s_1 - m_\Sigma^2)(s_3 - m_\Sigma^2)} [\bar{u}_\alpha(k_1; t_1) P_L u(p; r)] [\bar{u}(p; r) P_R u_{\beta'}(k_3; t_3)] \times \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \times \left[u_{\beta}^{\dagger}(k_3; t_3) C^T (\gamma^0)^T P_L^T (\bar{u}_{\gamma}(k_2; t_2))^T \right]^T \left[u_{\gamma'}^T(k_2; t_2) P_R^T C^T u_{\alpha'}(k_1; t_1) \right]^T \\
 & = \frac{|\lambda_{\psi dR}|^2 |\lambda_{d,1}''|^2 \varepsilon_{\alpha\gamma\beta} \bar{\varepsilon}_{\beta'\gamma'\alpha'}}{(s_1 - m_{\Sigma}^2) (s_3 - m_{\Sigma}^2)} \text{tr} \left[\bar{u}_{\alpha}(k_1; t_1) P_L u(p; r) \bar{u}(p; r) P_R u_{\beta'}(k_3; t_3) \times \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \times \bar{u}_{\beta}(k_3; t_3) P_L C (u_{\gamma'}(k_2; t_2) \bar{u}_{\gamma}(k_2; t_2))^T C P_R u_{\alpha'}(k_1; t_1) \right].
 \end{aligned} \tag{4.2.6}$$

Analogously, we rearrange the two remaining single squared amplitudes and obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 |\mathcal{M}_a|^2 & = \frac{|\lambda_{\psi dR}|^2 |\lambda_{d,1}''|^2 \varepsilon_{\alpha\gamma\beta} \bar{\varepsilon}_{\alpha'\gamma'\beta'}}{(s_1 - m_{\Sigma}^2)^2} \text{tr} \left[u_{\alpha'}(k_1; t_1) \bar{u}_{\alpha}(k_1; t_1) P_L u(p; r) \bar{u}(p; r) P_R \right] \times \\
 & \quad \times \text{tr} \left[u_{\gamma'}(k_2; t_2) \bar{u}_{\gamma}(k_2; t_2) P_L C (u_{\gamma'}(k_2; t_2) \bar{u}_{\gamma}(k_2; t_2))^T C P_R \right],
 \end{aligned} \tag{4.2.7}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 |\mathcal{M}_b|^2 & = \frac{|\lambda_{\psi dR}|^2 |\lambda_{d,1}''|^2 \varepsilon_{\beta\gamma\alpha} \bar{\varepsilon}_{\beta'\gamma'\alpha'}}{(s_3 - m_{\Sigma}^2)^2} \text{tr} \left[u_{\beta'}(k_3; t_3) \bar{u}_{\beta}(k_3; t_3) P_L u(p; r) \bar{u}(p; r) P_R \right] \times \\
 & \quad \times \text{tr} \left[u_{\gamma'}(k_2; t_2) \bar{u}_{\gamma}(k_2; t_2) P_L C (u_{\alpha'}(k_1; t_1) \bar{u}_{\alpha}(k_1; t_1))^T C P_R \right].
 \end{aligned} \tag{4.2.8}$$

Finally, we need to perform the color sum and the spin-averaging of the total squared amplitude to be able to calculate the decay rates. The color sum is obtained by applying the relation governing the color triplet $SU(3)$ -tensor $\varepsilon_{\alpha\beta\gamma}$, namely:

$$\sum_{\alpha, \beta, \gamma=1}^3 \varepsilon_{\alpha\beta\gamma} \bar{\varepsilon}_{\alpha\beta\gamma} = 6$$

and by applying the antisymmetry of this symbol. Spin-averaging is conducted according to Eq. B.3.23 plus an additional factor of $1/2$ accounting for the incoming spin of the dark matter ψ . Furthermore, we make use of the orthogonality of the projection operators P_L and P_R and invoke the identities of the charge conjugation matrix in Eqs. B.3.16 and B.3.17. The outcome of these manipulations read

$$\langle \mathcal{M}_a \mathcal{M}_b^* \rangle = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\text{color}} \sum_{r, t_1, t_2, t_3} \mathcal{M}_a \mathcal{M}_b^*$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= -\frac{3|\lambda_{\psi dR}|^2|\lambda''_{d,1}|^2}{(s_1 - m_\Sigma^2)(s_3 - m_\Sigma^2)} \text{tr} [\not{k}_1 \not{p} P_R \not{k}_3 \not{k}_2], \\
 \langle |\mathcal{M}_a|^2 \rangle &= \frac{3|\lambda_{\psi dR}|^2|\lambda''_{d,1}|^2}{(s_1 - m_\Sigma^2)^2} \text{tr} [\not{k}_1 \not{p} P_R] \text{tr} [\not{k}_2 \not{k}_3 P_R], \\
 \langle |\mathcal{M}_b|^2 \rangle &= \frac{3|\lambda_{\psi dR}|^2|\lambda''_{d,1}|^2}{(s_3 - m_\Sigma^2)^2} \text{tr} [\not{k}_3 \not{p} P_R] \text{tr} [\not{k}_2 \not{k}_1 P_R].
 \end{aligned} \tag{4.2.9}$$

The remaining traces are evaluated with respect to the summary of identities given in Eq. B.3.24, eventually yielding

$$\begin{aligned}
 \langle |\mathcal{M}|^2 \rangle &= 12|\lambda_{\psi dR}|^2|\lambda''_{d,1}|^2 \left\{ \frac{(p \cdot k_1)(k_2 \cdot k_3)}{(s_1 - m_\Sigma^2)^2} + \frac{(p \cdot k_3)(k_1 \cdot k_2)}{(s_3 - m_\Sigma^2)^2} \right. \\
 &\quad \left. - \Re \left[-\frac{\{(p \cdot k_1)(k_2 \cdot k_3) + (p \cdot k_3)(k_1 \cdot k_2) - (p \cdot k_2)(k_1 \cdot k_3) - i\varepsilon_{\mu\nu\sigma\rho} k_1^\mu p^\nu k_3^\sigma k_2^\rho\}}{(s_1 - m_\Sigma^2)(s_3 - m_\Sigma^2)} \right] \right\} \\
 &= 12|\lambda_{\psi dR}|^2|\lambda''_{d,1}|^2 \left\{ \frac{(p \cdot k_1)(k_2 \cdot k_3)}{(s_1 - m_\Sigma^2)^2} + \frac{(p \cdot k_3)(k_1 \cdot k_2)}{(s_3 - m_\Sigma^2)^2} \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + \frac{(p \cdot k_1)(k_2 \cdot k_3) + (p \cdot k_3)(k_1 \cdot k_2) - (p \cdot k_2)(k_1 \cdot k_3)}{(s_1 - m_\Sigma^2)(s_3 - m_\Sigma^2)} \right\}.
 \end{aligned} \tag{4.2.10}$$

Due to the mentioned relation between the minimal model and RPV supersymmetric models, we can cross-check the final squared and averaged matrix element with prior calculations in [31]. The authors of this paper derived amplitudes for trilinear neutralino decays with explicit R -parity violation. Applying the due changes and simplifications to accommodate their model to our much simpler version, we find our results confirmed. Nonetheless, we disagree in the sign of the interference term having a plus instead of a minus sign as stated by Baltz and Gondolo. In fact, the matrix element generator MADGRAPH5 supports our result which was further encouraged by a discussion with the developers of this program. Since we cannot clearly trace back the origin of this sign discrepancy we take our matrix element as the correct one.

Now, Eq. 4.2.10 is inserted into the general formula for the decay rate stated in Eq. C.2.4 in Appendix C.2. To this end, we turn to the rest frame of the decaying dark matter particle which simplifies the appearing terms. Furthermore, we apply the following approximations:

4 A Minimal Model of Decaying Dark Matter

1. $s_1 = (p - k_1)^2 \leq m_\psi^2 \ll m_\Sigma^2$ and likewise $s_3 \ll m_\Sigma^2$, such that we drop the dependence on s_1 and s_3 in the denominators of Eq. 4.2.10.
2. We assume the final state quarks to be massless which is a good approximation in the case of first and second generation quarks but it fails for the respective decay into top and bottom quarks unless the dark matter particle is very heavy.

At first, we want to calculate the total decay rate of this process, hence, we have to express the squared amplitude in terms of s_1 and s_3 in order to make use of Eq. C.2.5. To do so, we observe that by the virtue of our approximations and assumptions

$$\begin{aligned} p \cdot k_1 &= \frac{1}{2} (m_\psi^2 - s_1), & k_2 \cdot k_3 &= \frac{1}{2} s_1, \\ p \cdot k_3 &= \frac{1}{2} (m_\psi^2 - s_3), & k_1 \cdot k_2 &= \frac{1}{2} s_3, \\ p \cdot k_2 &= \frac{1}{2} (s_1 + s_3), & k_1 \cdot k_3 &= \frac{1}{2} (m_\psi^2 - s_1 - s_3). \end{aligned}$$

Rewriting the squared amplitude yields

$$\begin{aligned} \langle |\mathcal{M}|^2 \rangle &= \frac{6 |\lambda_{\psi dR}|^2 |\lambda''_{d,1}|^2}{m_\Sigma^4} \left\{ s_1 (m_\psi^2 - s_1) + s_3 (m_\psi^2 - s_3) \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \frac{1}{2} (s_1 + s_3) (m_\psi^2 - s_1 - s_3) \right\} \end{aligned}$$

and we can give the boundaries of the kinematic variables according to Eqs. C.2.6 and C.2.12:

$$\begin{aligned} s_1 &\in [0, m_\psi^2], \\ s_3 &\in [0, m_\psi^2 - s_1]. \end{aligned}$$

Putting everything together, we find

$$\begin{aligned} \Gamma(\psi \longrightarrow udd) &= \frac{1}{(2\pi)^3} \frac{1}{32m_\psi^3} \int_0^{m_\psi^2} \int_0^{m_\psi^2 - s_1} \langle |\mathcal{M}|^2 \rangle ds_3 ds_1 \\ &= \frac{3 |\lambda_{\psi dR}|^2 |\lambda''_{d,1}|^2 m_\psi^5}{128 (2\pi)^3 m_\Sigma^4}. \end{aligned} \tag{4.2.11}$$

In order to derive the differential decay rates with respect to the down-type, resp. up-type quark, we have to explicitly evaluate the most general form of the decay

rate formula

$$d\Gamma = \frac{(2\pi)^4}{2m_\psi} \langle |\mathcal{M}|^2 \rangle \delta^{(4)}(p^\mu - k_1^\mu - k_2^\mu - k_3^\mu) \frac{d^3k_1}{(2\pi)^3 2\omega_1} \frac{d^3k_2}{(2\pi)^3 2\omega_2} \frac{d^3k_3}{(2\pi)^3 2\omega_3},$$

where we have rewritten the four-momenta of the involved particles in the rest frame of the dark matter as

$$p^\mu = \begin{pmatrix} m_\psi \\ \vec{0} \end{pmatrix}, \quad k_1^\mu = \begin{pmatrix} \omega_1 := |\vec{k}_1| \\ \vec{k}_1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad k_2^\mu = \begin{pmatrix} \omega_2 := |\vec{k}_2| \\ \vec{k}_2 \end{pmatrix}, \quad k_3^\mu = \begin{pmatrix} \omega_3 := |\vec{k}_3| \\ \vec{k}_3 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Moreover, using $(k_2 \cdot k_3) = 1/2(k_2 + k_3)^2 = 1/2(p - k_1)^2 = 1/2m_\psi(m_\psi - 2\omega_1)$ and the corresponding relations with permuted indices, the squared amplitude reads

$$\begin{aligned} \langle |\mathcal{M}|^2 \rangle &= \frac{12 |\lambda_{\psi dR}|^2 |\lambda''_{d,1}|^2}{m_\Sigma^4} \left\{ m_\psi^2 \omega_1 (m_\psi - 2\omega_1) + m_\psi^2 \omega_3 (m_\psi - 2\omega_3) \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \frac{1}{2} m_\psi^2 \omega_2 (m_\psi - 2\omega_2) \right\}. \end{aligned}$$

Our first goal is it to find $d\Gamma/d\omega_2$ (the differential decay rate with respect to the up-type quark) and to this end the last integration must be the one over d^3k_2 . Furthermore, we observe that the squared amplitude contains only one term explicitly depending on ω_2 . Thus, the order of integration over d^3k_3 and d^3k_1 does not play a role for this term. The situation changes a bit when we consider the remaining two terms that either depend on ω_1 or ω_3 but not on both at the same time. Thus, to simplify the calculations, we first integrate each particular term over the momentum it does not depend on. Moreover, with respect to $d\Gamma/d\omega_2$, both results are then completely identical, such that we suppress this minor subtlety. In this sense, we start integrating over d^3k_3 eliminating the spatial part of the delta distribution

$$\int \frac{\langle |\mathcal{M}|^2 \rangle}{\omega_3} \delta^{(4)}(p^\mu - k_1^\mu - k_2^\mu - k_3^\mu) d^3k_3 = \frac{\langle |\mathcal{M}|^2 \rangle}{\omega_3} \delta(m_\psi - \omega_1 - \omega_2 - \omega_3)$$

with $\omega_3 = |\vec{k}_3| = |\vec{k}_1 + \vec{k}_2| = \sqrt{|\vec{k}_1|^2 + |\vec{k}_2|^2 + 2\vec{k}_1 \cdot \vec{k}_2} =: \sqrt{\omega_1^2 + \omega_2^2 + 2\omega_1\omega_2 \cos\theta}$ such that θ denotes the angle between the three-momenta \vec{k}_1 and \vec{k}_2 . Afterwards we continue with the integration over $d^3k_1 = \omega_1^2 d\omega_1 d(\cos\theta) d\phi$ via a transformation into spherical coordinates where the polar axis is kept along the direction of \vec{k}_2 . Since all terms are independent of ϕ , we obtain a factor of 2π through integra-

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tion and turn to the integral over $d(\cos\theta)$. Let $x := \cos\theta$ and, hence, $\delta(f(x)) := \delta\left(m_\psi - \omega_1 - \omega_2 - \sqrt{\omega_1^2 + \omega_2^2 + 2\omega_1\omega_2 x}\right)$. We apply the standard formula

$$\delta(f(x)) = \sum_{x_0 \text{ root of } f(x)} \frac{\delta(x - x_0)}{|f'(x_0)|}$$

to perform the integration. With $\omega_0 := \omega_3(x_0)$ we obtain $f'(x_0) = -\omega_2\omega_1/\omega_0$ and, thus

$$\delta(f(x)) \frac{\langle |\mathcal{M}|^2 \rangle dx}{\omega_3(x)} = \delta(x - x_0) \frac{\langle |\mathcal{M}|^2 \rangle dx}{\omega_2\omega_1}.$$

This relation can now be used to obtain

$$\begin{aligned} d\Gamma &= \frac{1}{(4\pi)^4 m_\psi} \frac{d^3 k_2}{\omega_2} d\omega_1 \omega_1 \int_{-1}^1 \delta(x - x_0) \frac{\langle |\mathcal{M}|^2 \rangle dx}{\omega_2\omega_1} \\ &= \frac{1}{(4\pi)^4 m_\psi} \frac{d^3 k_2}{\omega_2^2} d\omega_1 \langle |\mathcal{M}|^2 \rangle \end{aligned}$$

which is only true and non-zero, if $-1 \leq x_0 \leq 1$ or equivalently $\omega_3^- \leq \omega_3(x_0) \leq \omega_3^+$ with

$$\omega_3^\pm =: \sqrt{\omega_1^2 + \omega_2^2 \pm 2\omega_1\omega_2} = |\omega_1 \pm \omega_2|.$$

Since, by the action of the δ -distribution, we have $\omega_3(x_0) = m_\psi - \omega_1 - \omega_2$, it follows that

$$|\omega_1 - \omega_2| \leq m_\psi - \omega_1 - \omega_2 \leq \omega_1 + \omega_2.$$

Adding $\omega_1 + \omega_2$ to all terms and dividing by 2 yields then

$$\frac{1}{2} (|\omega_1 - \omega_2| + \omega_1 + \omega_2) \leq \frac{m_\psi}{2} \leq \omega_1 + \omega_2$$

from which we read off that the left-hand side of the inequality is the greater of ω_1 and ω_2 providing us with the upper bound of both variables, namely

$$\omega_1 \leq \frac{m_\psi}{2} \quad \text{and} \quad \omega_2 \leq \frac{m_\psi}{2}.$$

The right-hand side of the inequality yields the lower bound of ω_1 , i.e. $(m_\psi/2 - \omega_2) \leq \omega_1$. Thus, we can perform the remaining integration and obtain

$$\begin{aligned} d\Gamma &= \frac{12 |\lambda_{\psi dR}|^2 |\lambda''_{d,1}|^2 d^3 k_2}{(4\pi)^4 m_\psi m_\Sigma^4 \omega_2^2} \int_{\frac{m_\psi}{2} - \omega_2}^{\frac{m_\psi}{2}} \left[2m_\psi^2 \omega_1 (m_\psi - 2\omega_1) - \frac{1}{2} m_\psi^2 \omega_2 (m_\psi - 2\omega_2) \right] d\omega_1 \\ &= \frac{6m_\psi |\lambda_{\psi dR}|^2 |\lambda''_{d,1}|^2 d^3 k_2}{(4\pi)^4 m_\Sigma^4} \left(m_\psi - \frac{2}{3} \omega_2 \right), \end{aligned}$$

where the factor of 2 in front of the ω_1 -depending term accounts for the previous discussion of the order of integrations. Finally, we express $d^3 k_2$ in spherical coordinates and integrate over the full solid angle with a resulting factor of 4π , such that

$$\frac{d\Gamma(\psi \longrightarrow udd)}{d\omega_2} = \frac{3 |\lambda_{\psi dR}|^2 |\lambda''_{d,1}|^2}{4(2\pi)^3 m_\Sigma^4} m_\psi \omega_2^2 \left(m_\psi - \frac{2}{3} \omega_2 \right). \quad (4.2.12)$$

Furthermore, $\omega_2 \in [0, m_\psi/2]$ so that we can integrate over the remaining variable and recover the result of Eq. 4.2.11.

Since the squared amplitude is symmetric under the exchange of particle 1 and 3, the respective differential decay rates are the same and they are derived analogously to the previous case with the due changes in the calculus. Thus, the differential decay rate of a down-type quark reads

$$\frac{d\Gamma(\psi \longrightarrow udd)}{d\omega_1} = \frac{15 |\lambda_{\psi dR}|^2 |\lambda''_{d,1}|^2}{8(2\pi)^3 m_\Sigma^4} m_\psi \omega_1^2 \left(m_\psi - \frac{28}{15} \omega_1 \right). \quad (4.2.13)$$

As a concluding remark, we want to mention that the conjugate process $\psi \longrightarrow \bar{u}\bar{d}\bar{d}$ possesses the same decay rate and, additionally, its differential decay rates also coincide with the previous findings since this decay is CP -invariant. Thus, the total decay rate of the dark matter particle ψ with respect to the operator $\lambda''_{d,1} \bar{u} d^c \Sigma_d^\dagger$ is given by

$$\Gamma_{\text{tot}} = 2\Gamma(\psi \longrightarrow udd) = \frac{3 |\lambda_{\psi dR}|^2 |\lambda''_{d,1}|^2 m_\psi^5}{64(2\pi)^3 m_\Sigma^4} \quad (4.2.14)$$

and it holds that

$$\text{BR}(\psi \longrightarrow udd) = \text{BR}(\psi \longrightarrow \bar{u}\bar{d}\bar{d}) = \frac{1}{2}. \quad (4.2.15)$$

Figure 4.2.2: Tree-level Feynman diagrams contributing to the decay $\psi \rightarrow ude$ in (a) and $\psi \rightarrow dd\nu$ in (b) involving first generation quarks. Furthermore, we depict the definitions of momenta p , k_1 , k_2 and k_3 together with the fermion flow. Likewise, the color algebra is respected via Greek subscripts and spin states are denoted as r , t_1 , t_2 and t_3 .

4.2.2 The Decay Modes $\psi \rightarrow \bar{u}dl^+$ and $\psi \rightarrow d\bar{d}\nu$

Choosing the operator $\lambda'_{d,1}\bar{q}l^c\Sigma_d$, opens two distinct decay signatures of the dark matter particle because q and l denote $SU(2)$ -doublets. These signatures are $\psi \rightarrow \bar{u}dl^+$ and $\psi \rightarrow d\bar{d}\nu$ as well as their corresponding conjugated versions. In contrast to the previous discussion of $\psi \rightarrow udd$, there is only one Feynman diagram associated to each decay mode which is depicted in Fig. 4.2.2.

Applying again the Feynman rules of the minimal model leads, eventually, to the following squared and averaged amplitude

$$\langle |\mathcal{M}|^2 \rangle = \frac{6 |\lambda_{\psi dR}|^2 |\lambda'_{d,1}|^2}{(s_1 - m_\Sigma^2)^2} (p \cdot k_1) (k_2 \cdot k_3)$$

which is valid for both decay channels. Without any ambiguities, this result is confirmed by the calculations of Baltz and Gondolo [31] because no interference term is present.

The derivation of (differential) decay rates follows the same steps as in the previous example and are explicitly spelled out in Appendix C.3. Besides, we make use of

the same assumptions and simplifications, such that we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}\Gamma(\psi \longrightarrow \bar{u}dl^+) &= \frac{|\lambda_{\psi dR}|^2 |\lambda'_{d,1}|^2 m_\psi^5}{256 (2\pi)^3 m_\Sigma^4} \\ &= \Gamma(\psi \longrightarrow d\bar{d}\nu).\end{aligned}\tag{4.2.16}$$

As there are four decay channels in total, we find for the total decay rate of the dark matter particle and the branching fractions

$$\Gamma_{\text{tot}} = 4\Gamma(\psi \longrightarrow \bar{u}dl^+) = \frac{|\lambda_{\psi dR}|^2 |\lambda'_{d,1}|^2 m_\psi^5}{64 (2\pi)^3 m_\Sigma^4}\tag{4.2.17}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}\text{BR}(\psi \longrightarrow \bar{u}dl^+) &= \text{BR}(\psi \longrightarrow u\bar{d}l^-) = \frac{1}{4}, \\ \text{BR}(\psi \longrightarrow d\bar{d}\nu) &= \text{BR}(\psi \longrightarrow d\bar{d}\bar{\nu}) = \frac{1}{4}.\end{aligned}\tag{4.2.18}$$

4.3 Cosmological History

Creating a viable dark matter model does not end with stating its Lagrangian, this step should rather be seen as the starting point of further analyses. In fact, there is no general statement that guarantees any combination of the four characterizing parameters to yield a model that is able to generate a non-vanishing abundance of the dark matter candidate ψ in the early universe. Moreover, if a sizable amount of dark matter was produced, could it account for the right dark matter relic density coinciding with the observations?

An answer to this question can be derived from a further investigation of the coupling λ_ψ . It is the only mediator between the dark matter ψ and ordinary matter, thus, this coupling determines the efficiency of annihilations and scatterings that keep the dark matter in the thermal equilibrium of the early universe. As a consequence there are two main scenarios which give rise to distinct mechanisms generating the necessary abundance of dark matter: In cases where $\lambda_\psi \geq 10^{-7}$ the usual thermal production as described in Sec. 2.1.2 can be applied, in the opposite case where $\lambda_\psi \leq 10^{-7}$ the dark matter particle ψ is too feebly interacting with ordinary matter to remain in a stable thermal equilibrium.

On the other side, the scalar field Σ_f carries at least one of the standard model charges. Consequently, its interactions with the corresponding gauge bosons will induce efficient annihilations and scatterings such that the scalar is in thermal equilibrium until its freeze-out. The mutual dependence of the number densities of dark matter and scalar according to Eq. 4.1.1 opens the possibility of two distinct non-thermal paradigms to generate the correct dark matter abundance: the freeze-in [86] and SuperWIMP production [68, 69].

Freeze-in This paradigm describes the production of a feebly interacting, massive particle (FIMP) in the following way: Let X be a long-lived particle which is only feebly coupled to a thermal bath consisting of a set of particles in equilibrium at temperature T well above the weak scale by virtue of renormalizable interaction vertices. These interactions may involve more than one particle of the thermal bath and let m denote the mass² of the heaviest particle sharing an interaction vertex with X . These vertices may be quartic or Yukawa interactions such that they are characterized by a dimensionless coupling strength λ , or they may be trilinear interactions where the coupling strength is given by λm . Nonetheless, these coupling strengths fulfill $\lambda \ll 1$ to account for the feeble interactions of X .

Furthermore, the abundance of the particle X at very high temperatures is considered to be negligible. Within this setting, a non-vanishing abundance of X is generated by decays or collisions of the particles in thermal equilibrium as the universe cools down. The most dominant contribution is generated at temperatures $T \sim m$ because of an exponential suppression of the relevant interactions at lower temperatures. Thus, the yield of particle X freezes in at a value of [86]

$$Y_X \sim \lambda^2 \frac{M_{Pl}}{m},$$

where $Y_X = n_X/S$ is the ratio of the number density of particle X and S the entropy density of the thermal plasma. By this, the abundance of X increases with increasing interaction strength.

This mechanism is capable of providing the correct relic density to rather generic dark matter particles. To this end, the FIMP might be the dark matter particle itself or the FIMP, whose abundance has frozen in, subsequently decays into the dark matter particle to generate its abundance. As an example, let the dark matter

²It is usually assumed to be in the range of the weak scale.

be the FIMP particle X interacting with two particles Σ and Ξ of the thermal bath according to the operator $\lambda X \Sigma \Xi$ with the constraint that the mass m_Σ of particle Σ is larger than the sum of the mass of the two remaining ones: $m_\Sigma > m_\Xi + m_X$. Hence, the freeze-in mechanism is dominated by the production of X through decays of Σ . Eventually, the relic abundance of X is then given by [86]

$$\Omega_X h^2 \approx \frac{1.09 \cdot 10^{27} g_\Sigma m_X \Gamma_\Sigma}{g_*^{\frac{3}{2}} m_\Sigma^2} \quad (4.3.1)$$

with g_Σ denoting the internal degrees of freedom of Σ and Γ_Σ denoting its decay rate into particle X as well as g_* being the relativistic degree of freedom of the thermal plasma at the time of dark matter production. This example reflects the situation of the dark matter particle ψ in our minimal model with Σ being the scalar Σ_f .

SuperWIMP The SuperWIMP mechanism generates the abundance of a SuperWIMP particle X which is very weakly interacting with ordinary matter via late decays of particles that received their thermal abundance by freeze-out in the early universe [68, 69]. If we consider one heavy particle Σ with mass m_Σ and relic density $\Omega_\Sigma h^2$ that decays into the particle X , we obtain the expected relic density $\Omega_X h^2$ of X via the relic density of Σ according to

$$\Omega_X h^2 = \frac{m_X}{m_\Sigma} \Omega_\Sigma h^2. \quad (4.3.2)$$

If the parent particle Σ is a WIMP particle, i.e. it received the correct relic density via thermal freeze-out, then the SuperWIMP particle X quite naturally receives the correct relic density itself³.

There is no physical limitation prohibiting any of these two mechanism to account for the relic density of the dark matter particle ψ in our minimal model. Therefore, we expect both mechanism to be active, nonetheless, we have to assume a negligible initial abundance of ψ in the early universe to be able to apply the freeze-in paradigm.

Consequently, since SuperWIMP and freeze-in production take place at distinct epochs of the universe, the total relic density of the dark matter particle can be

³The decays of WIMP particles usually take place long after the Big Bang Nucleosynthesis (BBN) such that electroweak and hadronic byproducts of the WIMP decays might spoil the generated yield of light elements. Thus, the SuperWIMP mechanism must be consistent with BBN predictions and measurements of light elements' abundances [68].

approximated as the sum of both contributions. By applying Eqs. 4.3.1 and 4.3.2 to our model, we obtain the prediction for the dark matter's relic density

$$\begin{aligned}
 \Omega_\psi h^2 &= \Omega_\psi^{\text{FIMP}} h^2 + \Omega_\psi^{\text{SuperWIMP}} h^2 \\
 &\approx \frac{1.09 \cdot 10^{27} g_\Sigma}{g_*^{\frac{3}{2}}} \frac{x \Gamma(\Sigma_f \rightarrow f\psi)}{m_\Sigma} + x \text{Br}(\Sigma_f \rightarrow f\psi) \Omega_{\Sigma_f} h^2 \\
 &\approx x \text{Br}(\Sigma_f \rightarrow f\psi) \left[0.717 \frac{g_\Sigma}{g_*^{\frac{3}{2}}} \left(\frac{1 \text{ s}}{\tau_\Sigma} \right) \left(\frac{1 \text{ TeV}}{m_\Sigma} \right) + \Omega_{\Sigma_f} h^2 \right].
 \end{aligned} \tag{4.3.3}$$

In this formula we used the abbreviation $x := m_\psi/m_\Sigma$ and τ_Σ denotes the lifetime of the scalar field.

In addition, it should be noted that the branching fraction $\text{Br}(\Sigma_f \rightarrow f\psi)$ of the scalar field decaying to dark matter enters in Eq. 4.3.2 because there is more than one open decay channel available. In general, such an approximation needs a validation which comes in this case in form of a numerical treatment of the coupled Boltzmann equations governing the thermal history of the minimal model which was performed in [22].

Eq. 4.3.3 illustrates the influence of the branching fraction $\text{Br}(\Sigma_f \rightarrow f\psi)$ on the cosmological viability of the minimal decaying dark matter model. By tuning this branching fraction, it is possible to achieve the correct cosmological relic density of dark matter, as stated in the Planck results in Sec. 2.2.4, with our dark matter candidate ψ . However, if the scalar's decays into dark matter become too efficient, an overproduction of dark matter might occur.

Although depending both on this branching ratio, note that the freeze-in and SuperWIMP contribution to $\Omega_\psi h^2$ are quite distinct: The expected abundance of dark matter ψ through freeze-in is determined by the efficiency of the decay $\Sigma_f \rightarrow f\psi$ which is controlled by the coupling strength λ_ψ but not by other properties of the scalar field Σ_f . In contrast, the SuperWIMP contribution features the relic density of this scalar field which, thus, introduces additional dependencies on the scalar's mass and charge as well as the couplings λ .

Generally, the relic density $\Omega_{\Sigma_f} h^2$ is expected to be very small for charged scalar fields making the SuperWIMP contribution negligible in the case of light scalar fields [22]. This hypothesis was validated in the same reference for hadronic models with scalar masses in the LHC range, i.e $m_\Sigma \lesssim 3 \text{ TeV}$. Consequently, the only active production paradigm is the freeze-in mechanism which, in return, fixes the value of

the coupling λ_ψ according to

$$\lambda_\psi \simeq 1.59 \times 10^{-12} \frac{1}{\sqrt{x g_\Sigma}} \left(\frac{g_\star}{100} \right)^{\frac{3}{4}} \left(\frac{\Omega_\psi^{\text{FIMP}} h^2}{0.11} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (4.3.4)$$

by demanding the cosmological value, i.e. $\Omega_\psi^{\text{FIMP}} h^2 \stackrel{!}{=} \Omega_c h^2$.

5 Limits on the Minimal Model from Indirect Searches

In the following chapter we apply the previously discussed theoretical means to derive cosmic ray fluxes in the Earth's atmosphere to the minimal decaying dark matter model. To this end, we first describe our approach to determine the required energy spectra of gamma-rays, antiprotons and antineutrons for dark matter masses between 10 GeV and 1 TeV with the help of the multipurpose event generators PYTHIA8 and MADGRAPH5. Subsequently, we compare the generated spectra originating from different operator choices among each other and check their consistency with respect to similar findings in the literature. Following this, we perform the calculation of fluxes from these injection spectra and introduce a way to obtain lower bounds on the dark matter lifetime. In accordance with this method, we present the resulting bounds depending on the cosmic ray channel as well as on the choice of operator and we discuss our limits in the context of existing lifetime bounds in the literature.

5.1 Generation of Decay Spectra

We need to develop a strategy to generate the required energy spectra of the final state particles produced in dark matter decays while varying the dark matter mass in a range from 10 GeV to 1 TeV. Moreover, it is not sufficient to solely simulate the decays but we also have to include the hadronization process of the decay products since photons, antiprotons and antineutrons are not direct daughter particles of our dark matter candidate ψ .

The task of hadronization is covered by multiple Monte Carlo multipurpose-event generators like PYTHIA, HERWIG++ or SHERPA. For our purposes we have chosen the PYTHIA event generator in its version PYTHIA8.210 [118] because this generator

is written in the common language C++ and because of the diverse possibilities PYTHIA8 offers to manipulate its output.

Nevertheless, PYTHIA8 and all other multipurpose event generators feature the major drawback of being designed for collider studies such that single decay events cannot be simulated standalone. Furthermore, PYTHIA8 includes only a limited selection of predefined collision events of usual standard model particles and a few examples of, for instance, supersymmetric interactions or simple extensions of the standard model. Finally, particle decays in PYTHIA8 are usually treated in the isotropic approximation, i.e. the daughter particles are assumed to populate the whole phase space irrespective of the underlying matrix element of the decay process. Only particular decays, such as tau decays, are handled more sophisticated using the information about the matrix element. Thus, we have to accomplish two tasks: On the one side, we have to implement the production of dark matter particles ψ in collision events and on the other side, we have to include dark matter decays whose daughter particles are produced with respect to the underlying matrix element coming from the model Lagrangian.

It turned out, in fact, that the second problem is more involved than the first one. Implementing decay processes with respect to the squared amplitude into PYTHIA is tedious and cumbersome, such that we decided to incorporate a supplementary matrix element generator, namely MADGRAPH5 [20]. We profit from MADGRAPH5 in various aspects:

- This generator is written in PYTHON, such that its syntax is comprehensible.
- The color algebra implemented in MADGRAPH5 can handle the $SU(3)$ -color triplet tensor $\varepsilon_{\alpha\beta\gamma}$ which appears when choosing the operator $\lambda''_{d,1} \bar{u} d^c \Sigma_d^\dagger$.
- The matrix element computed by the MADGRAPH5 algorithms can be passed to a linked event generator, called MADEVENT, which uses this input to generate collision events producing dark matter including the simulation of its subsequent decays based on the matrix element. The resulting events are stored in the so-called “Les Houches Event File Format” (LHE) [19]. PYTHIA8 can read this file format and process the hadronization of the decay events. In this way we circumvent PYTHIA’s decay algorithms and only use it for hadronization while still profiting from the easily accessible output of PYTHIA8.
- Any model available in MADGRAPH5 is given in the Universal FeynRules Output (UFO) [56] which makes the implementation of new models easy. The

UFO files of any new model specify the properties of the appearing particles, the occurring interaction vertices and their associated couplings as well as the parameters of the model. In principle, we could create the necessary UFO files from scratch but we use an automated way to minimize possible sources of errors. To be more precise, we employ the MATHEMATICA[®] package FEYNRULES2.0 [18] which derives the UFO files from the model Lagrangian. Thus, the only input we have to manually insert is the Lagrangian of the minimal decaying dark matter model using MATHEMATICA[®] syntax.

Subsequently, we provide an explicit description of the usage of the individual programs.

5.1.1 Implementation of the Lagrangian with FeynRules

We implement the minimal decaying dark matter model as an extension of the already existing standard model files. In this sense, we only have to specify the additional particles and parameters of the extension in a detached file which is listed in Lst. D.2 in Appendix D.2. Having loaded the FEYNRULES package, we simply translate the Lagrangian given in Eqs. 4.1.1 and 4.1.2 into Mathematica[®] syntax. Additionally, we have to insert the kinetic terms for the dark matter particle ψ and the scalar field Σ_f in order to obtain the correct interaction terms with the standard model gauge bosons. Furthermore, we have to add the full Lagrangian of the standard model to receive a complete description of the extension. In the following we provide an example of the implementation in the case of the operator $\lambda''_{d,1} \bar{u} d^c \Sigma_d^\dagger$ of the scalar field using first generation quarks:

```

1 $FeynRulesPath = SetDirectory["/home/christopher.eckner/Downloads/feynrules-current"];
2 << FeynRules.m
3
4 SetDirectory[$FeynRulesPath << "/Models/MDDM"];
5 LoadModel["SM.fr", "MDDM.fr"];
6
7 LPsiint := lamPsi IndexDelta[color1, color2] anti[psi[spin1]].ProjP[spin1, spin2].d[spin2, color1]
8 sigbar[color2];
9 LPsikin := 1/2 I anti[psi[spin10]].Ga[mu, spin10, spin11].del[psi[spin11], mu];
10 LPsimass := -1/2 Mpsi Mpsi anti[psi[spin12]].psi[spin12];
11 LSigmaint := - lamSig Eps[cc1, cc2, cc3] sigbar[cc3] ubar[spin3, cc2].ProjM[spin3, spin4].CC[d[
12 spin4, cc1]] ;
13 LSigmakin := IndexDelta[green, blue] DC[sigbar[green], nu] DC[sig[blue], nu];
14 LSigmamass := -MSig MSig IndexDelta[white, beige] sigbar[white] sig[beige];
15 LDM := LPsikin + LPsimass + LPsiint + HC[LPsiint] + LSigmakin + LSigmamass + LSigmaint + HC[
16 LSigmaint] ;
17 Lttotal := LSM + LDM;
18
19 CheckHermiticity[Lttotal];
20
21 FeynmanRules[Lttotal, ScreenOutput -> True];

```

20 `WriteUFO[Ltotal];`

The command `WriteUFO[...]` applied to the full Lagrangian creates all necessary UFO files that can be copied into the “models” directory of MadGraph5. In addition, the remaining documentation in case of the operator $\lambda'_{d,1} \bar{q} l^c \Sigma_d$ is displayed in Appendix D.2.

5.1.2 Generating Dark Matter Decays Using MadGraph5

The general guideline is to define a collision process which is available in PYTHIA8 but which is also capable of producing dark matter particles as an outcome. Since we focus on hadronic models, we can make use of the dark matter’s coupling to quarks, especially its couplings to up-, down- or strange-quarks. Any model containing one of these particles coupling to the dark matter candidate ψ opens the proton-proton-collision process $p + p \rightarrow \psi + \psi$ because the parton distribution functions of these three quarks are non-vanishing for protons. Nonetheless, this approach cannot be applied to the case of third generation quarks, i.e. top and bottom quarks. In this situation we still want to use the production in proton-proton-collisions such that we add an interaction vertex of ψ , Σ_d and a down quark d supplementing the actual interaction vertices of interest. In principle, this would open an undesired decay channel of the dark matter particle into a down quark. However, this is not a real problem since we are able to force ψ to decay exclusively into the bottom and top quarks in every generated event. In fact, we explicitly specify the subsequent decay of a generated dark matter particle for any choice of operator and quark generation. This way, we ensure the inclusion of the squared matrix element of the respective decay channel in MADEVENT.

A generic example of the necessary syntax in MADGRAPH5 would be

```
generate process p p > psi psi , (psi > u d d) , (psi > u~ d~ d~)
```

In this example the dark matter particle is denoted by `psi` and we force its decay through a specific channel by setting it in brackets. Here, we demand one of the particles to decay into one up and two down quarks whereas the other one decays into the conjugate particles. Such an approach is quite efficient as we are able to generate two decay events in one single production event. Moreover, this approach respects the branching ratios of the decay channels. To ensure the branching ratios

of the decays associated to the operator $\lambda'_{d,1}\bar{q}l^c\Sigma_d$ we would, for instance, use the following command:

```
generate process p p > psi psi , (psi > u d~ e-), (psi > u~ d e+)
add process p p > psi psi , (psi > d d~ ve), (psi > d d~ ve~)
```

Again, a problem arises when we deal with top and bottom quarks because we want to study the behavior of dark matter decay products as a function of the dark matter mass. Hence, if we set m_ψ below the top quark mass it cannot be produced on-shell yielding four-body decays or five-body decays of ψ .¹ We treat four-body decays like the usual three-body decays since the top quark exclusively decays via $t \rightarrow W^+b$ yielding the processes $\psi \rightarrow W^+bbb$ or $\psi \rightarrow W^-\bar{b}\bar{b}\bar{b}$ which still occur with equal frequencies. If $m_\psi < m_W$ the W -boson itself is off-shell and decays according to its branching ratios which are approximately equal in the case of leptonic modes due to lepton universality but may differ in the case of hadronic modes. To simplify the simulations we assume that $\text{BR}(W \rightarrow l\nu) \approx \frac{1}{3}$ and $\text{BR}(W \rightarrow qq') \approx \frac{2}{3}$. We realize these branching ratios by adding W -boson decays into all three lepton flavors and six hadronic decay modes $W \rightarrow ud, us, ub, cd, cs, cb$ with equal probabilities which is, of course, artificial due to the CKM-suppression of decays non-diagonal in flavor. Nevertheless, we will see in the upcoming analyses that the photon, antiproton or antineutron energy spectra do not differ much between distinct light quark generations.

Finally, we summarize in Tab.5.1.1 all processes we took into consideration for a particular operator choice where we also list the points inside the dark matter mass interval $10 \text{ GeV} \leq m_\psi \leq 1 \text{ TeV}$ we decided to probe for this decay channel. In any case we generated $\sim \mathcal{O}(10^6)$ collision events in order to obtain a sizable number of decay products that eventually yield smooth energy spectra.

5.1.3 Deriving Decay Spectra with Pythia8

Processing the created LHE files with PYTHIA8 requires to set a few parameters:

- We turn off initial state radiation and multi-parton interactions since their inclusion consumes computation time and would only affect the production

¹In any scenario, the top quark decays into Wb . If the chosen dark matter mass is also smaller than the W -boson mass it cannot be produced on-shell, too. Thus, in the end we obtain a five-body decay. If $m_\psi > m_W$ then the gauge boson is on-shell resulting in a four-body decay.

operator	generated processes	covered dark matter masses m_ψ
$\lambda''_{d,1} \bar{u} d^c \Sigma_d^\dagger$	$\psi \longrightarrow udd \left(\bar{u} \bar{d} \bar{d} \right)$	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 10 \text{ GeV} - 100 \text{ GeV} \quad , 5 \text{ GeV steps} \\ 150 \text{ GeV}, 200 \text{ GeV} \\ 250 \text{ GeV}, 500 \text{ GeV} \\ 750 \text{ GeV}, 1 \text{ TeV} \end{array} \right.$
	$\psi \longrightarrow css \left(\bar{c} \bar{s} \bar{s} \right)$	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 10 \text{ GeV} - 100 \text{ GeV} \quad , 5 \text{ GeV steps} \\ 150 \text{ GeV}, 200 \text{ GeV} \\ 250 \text{ GeV}, 500 \text{ GeV} \\ 750 \text{ GeV}, 1 \text{ TeV} \end{array} \right.$
	$\psi \longrightarrow tbb \left(\bar{t} \bar{b} \bar{b} \right)$	200 GeV, 250 GeV, 500 GeV 750 GeV, 1 TeV
	$\psi \longrightarrow W^+ bbb \left(W^- \bar{b} \bar{b} \bar{b} \right)$	100 GeV, 125 GeV, 150 GeV
	$\psi \longrightarrow l^+ \nu_l bbb \left(l^- \bar{\nu}_l \bar{b} \bar{b} \bar{b} \right)$ $\psi \longrightarrow qq' bbb \left(\bar{q} \bar{q}' \bar{b} \bar{b} \bar{b} \right)$	15 GeV, 25 GeV, 50 GeV, 75 GeV
$\lambda'_{d,1} \bar{q} l^c \Sigma_d$	$\psi \longrightarrow u \bar{d} e^- \left(\bar{u} d e^+ \right)$ $\psi \longrightarrow d \bar{d} \nu_e \left(d \bar{d} \bar{\nu}_e \right)$	10 GeV, 15 GeV, 25 GeV, 50 GeV 75 GeV, 100 GeV, 150 GeV, 200 GeV, 250 GeV, 500 GeV, 750 GeV, 1 TeV
	$\psi \longrightarrow u \bar{d} \tau^- \left(\bar{u} d \tau^+ \right)$ $\psi \longrightarrow d \bar{d} \nu_\tau \left(d \bar{d} \bar{\nu}_\tau \right)$	10 GeV, 15 GeV, 25 GeV, 50 GeV 75 GeV, 100 GeV, 150 GeV, 200 GeV, 250 GeV, 500 GeV, 750 GeV, 1 TeV
	$\psi \longrightarrow t \bar{b} \tau^- \left(\bar{t} b \tau^+ \right)$ $\psi \longrightarrow b \bar{b} \nu_\tau \left(b \bar{b} \bar{\nu}_\tau \right)$	200 GeV, 250 GeV, 500 GeV 750 GeV, 1 TeV
	$\psi \longrightarrow W^+ b \bar{b} \tau^- \left(W^- \bar{b} b \tau^+ \right)$ $\psi \longrightarrow b \bar{b} \nu_\tau \left(b \bar{b} \bar{\nu}_\tau \right)$	100 GeV, 125 GeV, 150 GeV
	$\psi \longrightarrow l^+ \nu_l b \bar{b} \tau^- \left(l^- \bar{\nu}_l \bar{b} b \tau^+ \right)$ $\psi \longrightarrow qq' b \bar{b} \tau^- \left(\bar{q} \bar{q}' \bar{b} b \tau^+ \right)$ $\psi \longrightarrow b \bar{b} \nu_\tau \left(b \bar{b} \bar{\nu}_\tau \right)$	15 GeV, 25 GeV, 50 GeV, 75 GeV

Table 5.1.1: Summary of the selected decay modes induced by a particular choice of interaction operator of the scalar field Σ_d . Moreover, we list the points inside the mass interval of the dark matter particle for which we generated $\sim \mathcal{O}(10^6)$ events.

channel $p+p \longrightarrow \psi + \psi$ which we introduced as an auxiliary means to generate decays.

- We apply final state radiation because this naturally occurs in dark matter decays.
- A number of long-lived particles whose decay lengths usually exceed the dimensions of a collider are predefined to be stable so that we manually have to force them to decay. These particles may be created during the hadronization of a dark matter decay and will, eventually, decay while propagating through the galaxy. To this class of particles belongs the neutron which we have to treat separately. In order to obtain antideuteron spectra via the isotropic coalescence model we need antineutron energy spectra. Thus, we have to turn off neutron decays to derive these spectra. However, antineutrons decay into antiprotons and, therefore, contribute to the overall antiproton yield of a dark matter decay which, in return, implies that studying antiproton spectra is only possible while allowing (anti)neutrons to decay. In this sense, we have to evaluate each LHE file twice with neutron decay turned on and off.
- We use the default pp -collision tune of PYTHIA8. The tune refers to a certain choice of parameters which affects, for example, the hadronization process as it involves non-perturbative QCD physics.

As a matter of fact, we have to generate the energy spectra of each particle species with respect to the rest frame of the decaying particle. Since we simulate the dark matter production through hadron collisions $p+p \longrightarrow \psi + \psi$ we rarely produce the dark matter at rest and mainly boosted in some direction. On one side, we can try to raise the number of dark matter particles at rest by reducing the center-of-mass energy of the colliding proton beams but this method drastically decreases the number of available events as only the constituent quarks of the protons interact which possess a fraction of the total proton momentum. On the other side, boosting the decay products of a dark matter decay into the rest frame of the respective dark matter particle seems to be a better alternative. To this end, PYTHIA provides the full four-momentum of any particle produced in an event. Since we have access to the direction of flight of the dark matter particle, we can boost each particular decay product in the opposite direction using the Lorentz boost in Eq. B.2.6. Thus, we obtain the four-momentum of the particle in the rest frame of ψ .

To find all decay products after the hadronization of a dark matter decay, we make use of the daughter particle lists² of all intermediate states in the hadronization process which are accessible in the PYTHIA8 output. In detail, starting with the daughter particle list of the decaying dark matter particle, we iterate through the lists of all daughter particles until we have found all stable final states. From this list of final states we can afterwards filter out the particle species in question and store their energy after the application of the boost. In addition, we count the number of successful dark matter decays and the total number of antiprotons, antineutrons or photons given a particular mass m_ψ . This way we can derive the average number of particles per decay event. As a last remark, we only include photons with an energy greater than 50 MeV to avoid any conflicts with the PYTHIA8-internal treatment of infrared photons.

An example of the necessary PYTHIA8 code to perform our analyses is given in Appendix D.3.

5.1.4 Comparison between Theoretical Prediction and Simulation

As a last step we have to calculate the normalized decay spectra per decay event for each particle species in consideration. To this end, we make use of the binning algorithm implemented in PYTHON and generate 150 bins chosen equidistantly on a logarithmic scale and covering a kinetic energy range from 100 keV to $m_\psi/2$ for antiprotons and antineutrons or from 50 MeV to $m_\psi/2$ in case of photons. Finally we normalize the binned data according to the scripts provided in Appendix D.4.

Before we present the results of our simulations, we first want to check the consistency of their implementation by comparing the theoretical predictions of the differential decay rates in Eqs. 4.2.12, 4.2.13, C.3.5 and C.3.6 of the distinct decay channels with the outcome of MADGRAPH5 and PYTHIA8. To this end, we apply the formula in Eq. 4.2.1 relating the differential decay rate of a particle to its energy spectrum since all of the necessary quantities are known. We choose $m_\psi = 100$ GeV and the quarks of the first generation for this specific comparison and depict the resulting spectra in Figs. 5.1.1a and 5.1.1b.

We observe that theoretical prediction and simulation are in accordance with each other which implies that our approach to generate energy spectra is reasonable and

²These lists only contain the direct daughter particles of an unstable mother particle.

(b) $\psi \rightarrow ude$

Figure 5.1.1: Energy spectra per decay event of the daughter particles of ψ given its decay channel: (a) $\psi \rightarrow udd$ and (b) $\psi \rightarrow u\bar{d}e$. We display as histograms the results of the Monte Carlo simulations with PYTHIA8 and compare them to the theoretical predictions, depicted as solid lines, using the respective differential decay rate and total decay rate according to $dN/dT = d\Gamma/(\Gamma dT)$. The energy spectra for the decays $\psi \rightarrow d\bar{d}\nu_e$ are equivalent to the ones given in (b) by assigning $u \mapsto d$ and $e \mapsto \nu_e$.

it produces plausible spectra. Nevertheless, there is in any case a tiny deviation from the theoretical behavior since the simulated data seem to be slightly shifted towards lower energies. This deviation arises due to the massless final state approximation in our previous calculations. MADGRAPH5 fixes the masses of up- and down-quarks at values of $m_{\text{down}} = 5.04$ MeV and $m_{\text{up}} = 2.55$ MeV, i.e. they are not treated as massless. Consequently, these small masses lead to the observed effects.

5.2 Comparison of Generated Decay Spectra

In the subsequent section we present, compare and discuss a selection of primary photon and antiproton spectra generated after the hadronization of various dark matter decay modes.

Comparison of antiproton spectra from $\lambda''_{d,1} \bar{u}d^c \Sigma_d^\dagger$

By the minimality principle, we do not consider any flavor-mixing operators such that this specific scalar interaction operator gives rise to three distinct decay modes into quarks, namely $\psi \rightarrow udd$, $\psi \rightarrow css$ and $\psi \rightarrow tbb$ as well as the respective charge conjugated processes. The resulting antiproton spectra after the hadronization are depicted in Fig. 5.2.1 where we selected the spectra for dark matter masses $m_\psi \in \{15 \text{ GeV}, 100 \text{ GeV}, 1 \text{ TeV}\}$. Although we want to study the limits for dark matter masses between 10 GeV and 1 TeV, we display here the decay spectra for 15 GeV due to kinematical limitations originating from the decay $\psi \rightarrow tbb$. In fact, for dark matter masses below the W -boson mass m_W , all final states will include at least three bottom quarks so that the sum of masses lies above 10 GeV. Thus, we start our analyses at the kinematically accessible region above 15 GeV. Besides, we display the spectra with respect to the scaled kinetic energy $x = 2T/m_\psi$ of the antiprotons. The value of x cannot exceed 1 since every final state particle must have an energy E smaller than $m_\psi/2$ in the rest frame of the decaying particle. The spectra itself are, in addition, multiplied with x .

This collection of decay spectra reveals certain remarkable features: For each choice of dark matter mass, the antiprotons seem to peak at low kinetic energies, implying that the majority of them are rather soft. In detail, we observed that the position of the peak is approximately stable under variation of the dark matter mass. Furthermore, these spectra do not exhibit any special line structure and the overall

5.2 Comparison of Generated Decay Spectra

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 5.2.1: Antiproton decay spectra from the dark matter decays into udd (blue), css (green) and tbb (brown) as induced by the scalar's interaction operator $\lambda''_{d,1} \bar{u} d^c \Sigma_d^\dagger$. These spectra are given for dark matter masses of (a) 15 GeV, (b) 100 GeV and (c) 1 TeV. We show here the dependence on the scaled kinetic energy $x = 2T/m_\psi$ and multiply the spectrum with it.

antiproton yield is growing with increasing dark matter mass. These qualitative features can be compared to existing spectra in the literature which are, for example, given in Fig. 3 of [48] or Fig. 3 of [61].

Unfortunately, those references only provide spectra with respect to dark matter annihilation processes with two-body final states. However, far above the kinematical threshold of a decay or the respective annihilation mode both types of dark matter interactions should yield antiproton spectra only differing by a factor of 2 because an annihilation involves two dark matter particles and, in this sense, an annihilation can be viewed as a pseudo-particle of twice the dark matter mass decaying into the considered final state [48]. Thus, the qualitative features of the generated spectra are supposed to coincide and, indeed, our results are in good agreement with them. Nevertheless, there must be differences since, on one side, we are examining here the case of three-body decays and on the other side, in these references the underlying dark matter model is quite generic.³ It would, therefore, be desirable to have spectra of dark matter models which share more similarities with our model like the one in [73, 74, 75]. But, in fact, the authors do not provide their decay spectra and rather directly display final indirect limits such that we are restricted to qualitative comparisons.

Beside from the general shape of our decay spectra in Fig. 5.2.1, we recognize distinct features of each decay mode: Trilinear decays into udd and css share more or less the same spectra with the exception that for large kinetic energies around $m_\psi/2$ we expect more antiprotons from the decay $\psi \rightarrow udd$. This is quite reasonable, as the charm quarks possess a mass of $m_c \approx 1.3 \text{ GeV}/c^2$ such that the available phase space for the hadronized final states is more restricted than in the case of the very light quarks of the first generation. Hence, it is far less probable to produce antiprotons with large kinetic energies via the decay mode $\psi \rightarrow css$. This reasoning also applies to the decay into third generation quarks where the effect is even more drastic. For example, the spectra for $m_\psi = 15 \text{ GeV}$ unambiguously show this impact because the decay $\psi \rightarrow tbb$ has nearly no available phase space. Quite interestingly, we observe a minor dent in the spectrum of the tbb -mode for $m_\psi = 100 \text{ GeV}$ which is also an impact of the available phase space but in this case the W -boson is on-shell. In [48], such a feature is reported for the annihilation into $b\bar{b}$, too.

³For example, the spectra in the literature exhibit a more rapid decrease than our findings when going to low kinetic energies. This behavior might be due to our study of three-body decays since, on average, the daughter particles possess a smaller fraction of the available energy than it would be the case for two-body decays.

All in all, we infer from this analysis that the actual antiproton yield per decay event is not much affected by the choice of the decay mode but the respective spectrum might exhibit individual features which are in agreement with results in the literature.

Comparison of antiproton spectra from the two operators $\lambda''_{d,1}\bar{u}d^c\Sigma_d^\dagger$ and $\lambda'_{d,1}\bar{q}l^c\Sigma_d$

The scalar's interaction operator $\lambda'_{d,1}\bar{q}l^c\Sigma_d$ involves leptons such that there are only two quarks in the final state of a dark matter decay. Thus, we expect differences in the shape of the antiproton spectra which might give rise to observable differences in the derived bounds on the lifetime. Moreover, this operator yields dark matter decays which partly coincide with the ones in [74] which enables us to compare their results with ours.

Before we investigate similarities and differences between the decay modes of distinct operators, we examine the impact of varying the lepton flavor for a fixed quark generation. To be more precise, we compare the antiproton decay spectra of the modes $\psi \longrightarrow u\bar{d}e^-, d\bar{d}\nu_e$ and $\psi \longrightarrow u\bar{d}\tau^-, d\bar{d}\nu_\tau$ in Fig. 5.2.2.

A priori it is plausible to assume a slight difference distinguishing both antiproton spectra because of the hadronic decay channels of the tau lepton. However, as it turned out, there is no observable impact of varying the lepton flavor in the case of antiprotons. By examining the photon spectra of both decay modes we notice an equivalent behavior of the spectra with a tiny increase of the photon yield in the case of tau leptons which is, nonetheless, negligible. Thus, in the following we will discard decays that involve quarks and leptons of different generations since the effect does not play any significant role for the resulting antiproton or photon spectra.

Now, we are able to make a comparison between two decay modes of $\lambda'_{d,1}\bar{q}l^c\Sigma_d$, namely $\psi \longrightarrow u\bar{d}e^-, d\bar{d}\nu_e$ as well as $\psi \longrightarrow t\bar{b}\tau^-, b\bar{b}\nu_\tau$ and a reference decay mode of the contrasting operator $\lambda''_{d,1}\bar{u}d^c\Sigma_d^\dagger$ where we have chosen $\psi \longrightarrow udd$ because it encompasses all general features of the antiproton spectra discussed in the previous section. As we have pointed out in the analysis of Fig. 5.2.1, the differences between spectra from first and second generation quarks are less important. Therefore we do not consider the respective decay modes of the operator $\lambda'_{d,1}\bar{q}l^c\Sigma_d$. Again, in Fig. 5.2.3 we provide exemplifying antiproton spectra for dark matter masses $m_\psi \in \{15 \text{ GeV}, 100 \text{ GeV}, 1 \text{ TeV}\}$ with respect to the scaled kinetic energy x .

Figure 5.2.2: Comparison of the antiproton decay spectra from the dark matter decays into $u\bar{d}e^-$, $d\bar{d}\nu_e$ (dotted line) and $u\bar{d}\tau^-$, $d\bar{d}\nu_\tau$ (dash-dotted line) as induced by the scalar's interaction operator $\lambda'_{d,1}\bar{q}l^c\Sigma_d$. These spectra are given for dark matter masses of 15 GeV (yellow), 100 GeV (blue) and 1 TeV (brown). We show here the dependence on the scaled kinetic energy $x = 2T/m_\psi$ and multiply the spectrum with it.

In principle, the antiproton spectra from quark-lepton final states resemble very much the spectra of trilinear decays into three quarks. Moreover, the decay involving top quarks possesses the characteristic shift towards lower kinetic energies which we have already encountered in the previous examples. The most striking difference is, nevertheless, a sizable reduction of the antiproton yield as compared to $\psi \rightarrow udd$ where the number of antiprotons from $\psi \rightarrow t\bar{b}\tau^-, b\bar{b}\nu_\tau$ is slightly increased in comparison to $\psi \rightarrow u\bar{d}e^-, d\bar{d}\nu_e$. In fact, viewed over the complete range of dark matter masses, the antiproton yield of decay modes induced by $\lambda''_{d,1}\bar{u}d^c\Sigma_d^\dagger$ is approximately twice the respective yield of decays from $\lambda'_{d,1}\bar{q}l^c\Sigma_d$. Thus, we expect tighter bounds from trilinear decays into three quarks.

Comparison of photon spectra

Finally, we examine in Fig. 5.2.4 the generated photon decay spectra by virtue of the three decay modes $\psi \rightarrow udd$, $\psi \rightarrow tbb$ and $\psi \rightarrow t\bar{b}\tau^-, b\bar{b}\nu_\tau$ which together give a satisfying overall picture of the expected behavior of photon spectra from the minimal dark matter model. To this end, we consider the same three sample masses as beforehand and display all spectra with respect to the scaled photon energy x

Figure 5.2.3: Comparison of the antiproton spectra from two different scalar interaction operators where we display the decay channel $\psi \rightarrow udd$ (solid) induced by $\lambda''_{d,1} \bar{u} d^c \Sigma_d^\dagger$ and the two decay channels $\psi \rightarrow u \bar{d} e^-, d \bar{d} \nu_e$ (dotted) as well as $\psi \rightarrow t \bar{b} \tau^-, b \bar{b} \nu_\tau$ (dash-dotted) arising from $\lambda'_{d,1} \bar{q} l^c \Sigma_d$. We give the respective scaled spectra for dark matter masses of 15 GeV (yellow), 100 GeV (blue) and 1 TeV (brown) while showing the dependence on the scaled kinetic energy $x = 2T/m_\psi$.

while multiplying the spectrum itself with x^2 . Recall, that we applied a cutoff at $T = 50 \text{ MeV}$ to minimize uncertainties due to PYTHIA's treatment of infrared photons.

In general, we observe quite smooth photon spectra with no internal structure like spectral lines in analogy to the case of antiprotons. Besides, the shapes of the photon spectra from decays into third generation quarks also display the previously described shifts towards lower energies or respectively characteristic dents at higher energy which all account for the reduction of available phase space due to the heavy quarks. The resulting photon yield of a dark matter decay depends, again, on the choice of the scalar's interaction operator where decay modes involving three quarks produce more photons than decays into two quarks and one lepton. However, this time it is not a factor of two but merely a slight enhancement.

5.2 Comparison of Generated Decay Spectra

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 5.2.4: Comparison of photon spectra from two different scalar interaction operators where we display the decay channel $\psi \rightarrow t\bar{t}\tau^-$, $b\bar{b}\nu_\tau$ (brown) induced by $\lambda'_{d,1}\bar{q}l^c\Sigma_d$ and the two decay channels $\psi \rightarrow udd$ (yellow) as well as $\psi \rightarrow tbb$ (green) arising from $\lambda'_{d,1}\bar{u}d^c\Sigma_d^\dagger$. We give the respective scaled spectra for dark matter masses of 15 GeV (a), 100 GeV (b) and 1 TeV (c) while showing the dependence on the scaled energy $x = 2T/m_\psi$.

5.3 Application of Indirect Searches

Having collect the necessary particle physics ingredients, i.e. the decay spectra, of the minimal decaying dark matter model, we can insert them into the source terms of the equations predicting the cosmic ray fluxes as introduced in Sec. 3.2. This way we have at hand all means to compare experimental measurements of a specific cosmic ray channel with the dark matter contribution and, if available, the theoretical prediction of the respective astrophysical background. In the subsequent section, we first illustrate how we derive lower bounds on the dark matter lifetime through this comparison and afterwards present the resulting limits for antiprotons, gamma-rays and antideuterons.

5.3.1 Derivation of lower lifetime bounds

We perform a conservative analysis to derive lower limits on the dark matter lifetime: Given the experimental measurements of a particular cosmic ray channel, we demand that the sum of dark matter and astrophysical background contribution in the case of antiprotons (or the single dark matter flux in the case of gamma-rays) does not overshoot these data by more than a fixed significance interval.

In particular as explained in Secs. 3.1.1 and 3.1.2, we make use of the PAMELA data from 2013 in [12] to constrain our model in the antiproton channel and the Fermi-LAT measurements of the IGRB in [7] to set lower bounds due to the gamma-ray channel. Both data sets provide the respective flux in terms of binned measurements Φ_i^{exp} with measurement uncertainty σ_i , where i runs over the available number of bins. We proceed by binning the theoretical prediction Φ_i^{theo} in the same way as the considered data and fix the confidence interval to be $3\sigma_i$ in every bin. Thus, we find the lower lifetime bound τ_ψ by

$$\tau_\psi = \inf \left\{ \tau \mid \Phi_i^{\text{theo}}(\tau) \leq \Phi_i^{\text{exp}} + 3\sigma_i \forall i \right\}.$$

We should emphasize at this point that the energy range of the considered experiments sometimes outreaches the ranges of available dark matter fluxes. The PAMELA data cover an interval from 60 MeV to 350 GeV which implies that dark matter masses above 700 GeV yield fluxes in the whole energy range. This is not a problem in this case since the background contribution is known to even higher kinetic energies such that the binning procedure of the theoretical prediction is always

possible. The situation changes when passing over to the Fermi-LAT measurements covering a range from 100 MeV to 820 GeV. Since we applied a cutoff at a photon energy of 50 MeV our fluxes always include the lowest bin edge of the data but not the largest. Moreover, we do not take into account any background model for the diffusive gamma-ray flux so that we are only able to probe the data until we reach the largest bin edge still inside the range of our dark matter flux. Hence, we are limited to a smaller subset of the Fermi-LAT data.

As a final remark, we compare the integrated dark matter gamma-ray flux to the Fermi-LAT data in each bin since their measurement results are given as intensity of the IGRB in the respective energy interval.

5.3.2 Limits from antiproton searches

To gain a first insight on the impact of different decay modes, dark matter masses, transport equation parameter sets and other adjustable quantities like the local dark matter density, we display in Fig. 5.3.1 the dark matter antiproton fluxes originating from the decay modes $\psi \rightarrow udd$, $\psi \rightarrow tbb$ and $\psi \rightarrow u\bar{d}e^-, \bar{d}\bar{d}\nu_e$ given $m_\psi = 15$ GeV, 100 GeV, 1 TeV. Along with the dark matter contributions we provide the expected astrophysical background flux as calculated from Eq. 3.2.6 for the MED parameter set with a Fisk potential of $\phi_F = 0.7$ GV as well as the PAMELA data of 2013 with their 1σ -uncertainty. The reference lifetime of the dark matter is set to $\tau_\psi = 1 \cdot 10^{28}$ s.

From this figure we extract that the astrophysical background of cosmic antiprotons describes the PAMELA measurements very well such that a putative dark matter contribution can only make up a small fraction of the total flux. However, even in the case of a reasonable lifetime, like the chosen value of $\tau_\psi = 1 \cdot 10^{28}$ s, the dark matter flux originating from $\psi \rightarrow udd$ for $m_\psi = 15$ GeV competes with the order of magnitude of the astrophysical expectation in the low-energy range. Thus, we expect lifetime bounds being tighter for light dark matter and looser for heavy dark matter. This observation is supported by the behavior of the dark matter flux with increasing dark matter mass since its maximal value shifts to higher kinetic energies where the astrophysical background dominates. Only for heavy dark matter in the TeV-range the resulting antiproton flux becomes again comparable to the expectations in the high-energy bin at 128.9 GeV. Nonetheless, the experimental measurements up to approximately 1 GeV seem to constrain the dark matter contribution most severely.

Figure 5.3.1: Antiproton flux $\Phi_{\bar{p}}$ originating from dark matter decays with respect to two different scalar interaction operators for three distinct choices of dark matter masses 15 GeV (blue), 100 GeV (brown) and 1 TeV (green). We display the expectations from $\psi \rightarrow u\bar{d}d$ (dot-dashed) and $\psi \rightarrow t\bar{b}b$ (dotted) associated to $\lambda''_{d,1} \bar{u}d^c \Sigma_d^\dagger$ and $\psi \rightarrow u\bar{d}e^-, d\bar{d}\nu_e$ (dot-dot-dashed) coming from $\lambda'_{d,1} \bar{q}l^c \Sigma_d$ fixing the dark matter lifetime to be $\tau_\psi = 1 \cdot 10^{28}$ s, the local dark matter density at $\rho_\odot = 0.4 \text{ GeV cm}^{-3}$ and assuming the NFW density profile. Moreover, we show the astrophysical antiproton flux contribution as computed in [38] for the MED parameter set of galactic propagation with a Fisk potential of $\phi_F = 0.7 \text{ GV}$ accounting for solar modulation effects. As a reference the refined PAMELA measurements of 2013 [12] are displayed where the horizontal error bars represent the bin width and the vertical error bars state the 1σ -uncertainty of the measurement.

This situation can to some extent be accounted to the impact of solar modulation because it affects, in particular, low-energy antiprotons and further reduces their kinetic energy.

Besides, the difference in the antiproton yield between the decay modes of distinct operators is still observable at the level of antiproton fluxes such that the derived limits will reflect these discrepancies. Apart from the effect of different decay modes, we also want to study the behavior of the dark matter fluxes when varying the other parameters determining its order of magnitude. To this end, we examine the uncertainty of the dark matter flux introduced by changing the local dark matter density $\rho_\odot \in \{0.3, 0.4, 0.5\} \text{ GeV cm}^{-3}$, the dark matter density profile (NFW, Einasto, Burkert), displayed in Fig. 5.3.3, and the transport equation's parameter set (MIN, MED, MAX) for the fixed decay mode $\psi \rightarrow c\bar{s}s$, shown in Fig. 5.3.2. All calculations were

Figure 5.3.2: Comparison of the MIN-MED-MAX uncertainty due to the realization of galactic propagation for the dark matter antiproton flux contribution exemplified on the decay mode $\psi \rightarrow css$ for three distinct dark matter masses: 15 GeV (yellow), 100 GeV (blue) and 1 TeV (green) where we consider a reference lifetime of $\tau_\psi = 1 \cdot 10^{28} \text{ s}$ and fix the remaining parameters according to the specifications in the figure. Alongside the dark matter fluxes, we provide the astrophysical background and the PAMELA data of 2013.

performed with respect to a dark matter lifetime of $\tau_\psi = 1 \cdot 10^{28} \text{ s}$ and the three dark matter masses as before.

The dominating source of uncertainty arises from the choice of the parameter set determining the transport equation. In fact, this outcome was expected since those three parameter sets describe quite distinct realizations of the galactic diffusion of charged particles which makes it necessary to determine lower limits on the dark matter lifetime for each particular set. We derive from this figure that the choice of a galactic propagation model affects the low-energy range of the fluxes more intensely than the high-energy ranges. Given a lifetime of $\tau_\psi = 1 \cdot 10^{28} \text{ s}$ and dark matter masses between 100 GeV and 1 TeV, we find antiproton fluxes from dark matter decays that overshoot the 3σ -range of the PAMELA measurements in the low-energy bins when applying galactic propagation with respect to the MAX parameters. This observation also confirms our prior conjecture that the low-energy data points with rather small error bars most dominantly restrict the antiproton fluxes from dark matter decays of our model.

Figure 5.3.3: Comparison of uncertainty sources for the dark matter antiproton flux contribution exemplified on the decay mode $\psi \rightarrow css$ for three distinct dark matter masses: 15 GeV (yellow), 100 GeV (blue) and 1 TeV (green) where we consider a reference lifetime of $\tau_\psi = 1 \cdot 10^{28}$ s and fix the remaining parameters according to the specifications in the respective figure. In (a) we investigate the uncertainty arising from the contentious value of the local dark matter density (cf. Sec. 2.4) and in (b) we examine the effect of varying the dark matter density profile. Again, we provide the astrophysical background and the PAMELA data of 2013.

On the other hand, the uncertainties of the dark matter antiproton flux originating from the choice of the dark matter density profile or its local density at the Sun's position cannot compete with the ones of the propagation model. In fact, varying the density profile seems to have nearly no impact on the size of the resulting fluxes. For our specific selection the Einasto profile results in the largest fluxes whereas the Burkert profile produces the smallest ones. The relative uncertainty compared to the NFW profile is, nonetheless, only about 4% such that we will neglect this uncertainty source in the following limits and state the results with respect to the NFW profile. This behavior was also expected since the density profiles behave very much the same in the outer regions of the galaxy and show their major differences in the vicinity of the galactic center. As it is very unlikely to observe any antiproton coming from the galactic center, the actual shape of the density profile accounts only for a small fraction of uncertainty.

However, the putative value of the local dark matter density ρ_{\odot} cannot be ignored completely since the relative uncertainty introduced by increasing or decreasing the assumed value of 0.4 GeV cm^{-3} about 0.1 GeV cm^{-3} is approximately 25%. This great impact is due to the fact that the local dark matter density enters as a scaling factor of the flux in Eq. 3.2.8 such that any uncertainty on its value directly affects the size of the flux. Furthermore, the relative uncertainty due to the local density remains constant for all dark matter masses. Consequently, we reflect this issue in our lifetime limits by providing error bars with respect to $\rho_{\odot} \in \{0.3, 0.4, 0.5\} \text{ GeV cm}^{-3}$.

Apart from these sources of uncertainty there are plenty of other effects that may alter the size of the antiproton fluxes. For example, the impact of solar modulation could be studied by varying the Fisk potential or by a numerical simulation of the solar wind's effects as in [71]. Nevertheless, we decided to adopt the astrophysical background as calculated in [38] together with the best-fit values of the Fisk potential for every parameter set of the transport equation.

Having discussed all relevant uncertainties, we now turn to the limits on the dark matter lifetime which we derived as stated in the previous section. To this end, we also provide the PYTHON script in Lst.D.7 with which we performed the calculations of antiproton fluxes and the derivations of lower lifetime bounds. Furthermore, we rewrite the lifetime bounds in terms of upper bounds on the model dependent factor $|\lambda_{\psi}|^2 |\lambda|^2 / m_{\Sigma}^4$ in cases where it is possible, i.e. in cases where the assumption of massless final state particles after a dark matter decay is satisfied. This is approximately true for the decay modes $\psi \rightarrow udd$, $\psi \rightarrow css$ and $\psi \rightarrow u\bar{d}e^{-}, d\bar{d}\nu_e$.

Such a translation of bounds is possible since the lifetime of the dark matter is connected to its total decay width by $\tau_\psi = 1/\Gamma_{\psi,\text{tot}}$ and we have computed these total widths under the assumption of massless final states. Hence, we can make use of this relation and we provide the results in Fig. 5.3.4.

These bounds reflect the observation we made earlier, namely that light dark matter is more severely constrained than heavy dark matter. In fact, in the case of the MAX parameter set the lower lifetime bounds almost decrease by about 2 orders of magnitude when going from 10 GeV to 1 TeV. This effect becomes less significant in the case of MED or MIN propagation where the decrease is only by about one order of magnitude. Besides, our limits span over a wide range of lifetimes constraining light dark matter to $\sim 1 \cdot 10^{31}$ s for galactic propagation according to the MAX parameters and $\sim 7 \cdot 10^{26}$ s for heavy dark matter in the MIN case. As a remarkable feature, we recognize a wide gap between the MED and MAX limits which can be ascribed to the choices of the Fisk potential for the respective application of solar modulation: For MIN and MED parameters we used $\phi_F = 0.74$ GV or resp. $\phi_F = 0.70$ GV which are nearly equivalent whereas in the case of the MAX parameter set we applied $\phi_F = 0.38$ GV being only half of the previous values. Thus, a larger amount of low-energy antiprotons is allowed to penetrate the Earth's atmosphere and we have shown that in this energy range lies the maximum of the dark matter antiproton flux. This implies that the choice of the Fisk potential additionally reinforces or reduces the size of the dark matter contribution.

However, trilinear decays into three quarks are more severely constrained than trilinear decays into a quark pair and a lepton. This result we have already expected from the study of certain dark matter fluxes in Fig. 5.3.1. The difference between the two choices of the scalar's interaction operator is persistent in all three propagation models, although the effect diminishes for heavier dark matter in the MIN and MED case. It is, in addition, quite striking that the decay modes associated to a specific operator produce fairly similar lower lifetime bounds. These differences translate likewise into the upper bounds on the parameter $|\lambda_\psi|^2 |\lambda|^2 / m_\Sigma^4$.

As a conclusion, we present our results in the context of earlier studies of the very similar model in [73, 74, 75], though it is necessary to keep in mind the different physical assumptions, choices of propagation parameters, data sets and methods to derive lower lifetime bounds. To this end, we display in Fig. 5.3.5 the limits on the dark matter lifetime obtained from antiproton searches as provided in [74].

(a)

(b)

Figure 5.3.4: Lower lifetime bounds (a) as a function of the dark matter mass derived from the comparison of the sum of calculated antiproton fluxes and astrophysical background taken from Eq. 3.2.6 to the refined 2013 PAMELA data provided in [12]. We show the bounds in the case of the NFW density profile and display error bars accounting for the uncertainty of the local dark matter density where the depicted bounds are stated with respect to $\rho_{\odot} = 0.4 \text{ GeV cm}^{-3}$. Besides, we separately address each set of propagation parameters and each decay mode within the scope of this thesis. In (b) we provide the resulting upper bounds on the model specific parameter $|\lambda_{\psi}|^2 |\lambda|^2 / m_{\Sigma}^4$ for the decay modes where the approximation of massless final state quarks is reasonable.

Figure 5.3.5: Lower lifetime bounds on the decaying dark matter model of [73, 74, 75] featuring decays of the type $\text{DM} \rightarrow q\bar{q}N$ where q refers to any up- or down-type quark and N could be any neutral fermion. From lower to larger lifetimes the dashed lines state the bounds in case of the MIN, MED or MAX parameter set of galactic propagation. Moreover, red lines correspond to down quarks, green lines to charm quarks, orange lines to bottom quarks and blue lines to top quarks. The neutral particle is always a neutrino. All limits were derived with respect to the antiproton-to-proton ratio of the PAMELA measurements of 2010 [10] using a χ^2 goodness-of-fit test statistic such that the provided bounds are at 95% C.L. The plot is taken directly from [74].

This specific model focuses on the modes $\psi \rightarrow q\bar{q}N$ where ψ refers to the dark matter particle, q to any up- or down-type quark and N represents any neutral fermion. All model couplings are of the Yukawa-type as well and the decay is mediated by a heavy scalar particle. In this respect, their model is comparable to our decay mode $\psi \rightarrow d\bar{d}\nu$ from the scalar's interaction operator $\lambda'_{d,1}\bar{q}l^c\Sigma_d$. Hence, our lifetime bounds should be somewhat comparable to their findings for this specific channel. However, there are two major differences between our and their approach: On the one hand side, they used the antiproton-to-proton ratio of the PAMELA data of 2010 [10] displaying larger error bars in the low-energy range of the fluxes than the refined measurements of 2013 and on the other side, they applied a goodness-of-fit test to derive their bounds while considering a Fisk potential of 0.5 GV for all parameter sets of the propagation model and the background prediction of [40] which does not include details like tertiary production of antiprotons.

The red lines in Fig. 5.3.5 correspond to the decay into a down anti-down quark pair, the green lines to the respective decay into charm quarks, the orange lines to bottom quarks and finally the blue lines to top quark decays. We read off this figure

that the limits for bottom quarks always stay below the limits for down quarks in the range of dark matter masses from 100 GeV to 1 TeV. Such a behavior we also identify in our results for the decay modes $\psi \longrightarrow u\bar{d}e^-$, $d\bar{d}\nu_e$ and $\psi \longrightarrow t\bar{b}\tau^-$, $b\bar{b}\nu_\tau$. Nonetheless, we do not observe the top quark limits to be stronger than any other limit but this is due to the fact that top and bottom quarks cannot be treated separately in our model since their associated decay modes originate from the same operator. In general, it seems that the MIN and MED limits of Garny et al. are stronger than our bounds, even if we take into account the more constrained three quark decays. This may be ascribed to the higher value of the Fisk potential we applied in our analyses as lowering its value would increase our bounds. However, our limits on the MAX propagation model are clearly about two orders of magnitude larger which, again, should be mostly due to the choice of the Fisk potential and the corresponding astrophysical background contribution. Moreover, the bounds of Garny et al. appear to be smoother than our findings which mainly results from the χ^2 goodness-of-fit test they applied. This method has the advantage of taking into account all data points at the same time whereas our approach probes each of the PAMELA data points on its own.

In this sense, we derive from this comparison that our results are competitive with the existing bounds in the literature and even yield increased lower bounds on the lifetime of decaying dark matter models with these types of interactions. Moreover, the chosen model of galactic propagation and the realization of solar modulation effects are a crucial ingredient for the determination of antiproton fluxes that severely affect the resulting limits.

5.3.3 Limits from gamma-ray searches

We arrange our results of the gamma-ray limits in the same manner that we used in the previous section. Therefore, we first depict in Fig. 5.3.6 the expected gamma-ray fluxes from the dark matter decay modes $\psi \longrightarrow udd$, $\psi \longrightarrow tbb$ and $\psi \longrightarrow u\bar{d}e^-$, $d\bar{d}\nu_e$ given $m_\psi = 15$ GeV, 100 GeV, 1 TeV. Furthermore, we added the measurement results of the IGRB intensity collected by the Fermi-LAT experiment after an exposure time of 50 months [7] and fix the dark matter lifetime to be $\tau_\psi = 1 \cdot 10^{28}$ s while we assume the NFW profile.

The shape of resulting gamma-ray fluxes resemble very much the shape of the inserted photon spectra of the dark matter decays. The galactic contribution to the

Figure 5.3.6: Gamma-ray fluxes $E^2 d\Phi_\gamma/dE$ originating from dark matter decays with respect to two different scalar interaction operators for three distinct choices of dark matter masses 15 GeV (blue), 100 GeV (brown) and 1 TeV (green). We display the expectations from $\psi \rightarrow udd$ (dot-dot-dashed) and $\psi \rightarrow tbb$ (dotted) associated to $\lambda''_{d,1} \bar{u}d^c \Sigma_d^\dagger$ and $\psi \rightarrow t\bar{b}\tau^-, b\bar{b}\nu_\tau$ (dash-dotted) coming from $\lambda'_{d,1} \bar{q}l^c \Sigma_d$ fixing the dark matter lifetime to be $\tau_\psi = 1 \cdot 10^{28}$ s, the local dark matter density at $\rho_\odot = 0.4 \text{ GeV cm}^{-3}$ and assuming the NFW density profile. Moreover, we included the gamma-ray flux contributions from extragalactic and galactic origin and depict as a reference the 50 months Fermi-LAT measurement of the IGRB intensity taken from Tab. 3 in [7].

gamma-ray fluxes was expected to behave like this since the fluxes are the result of a mere rescaling of the injection spectra and, besides, the size of the galactic contribution is about one order of magnitude larger than the extragalactic gamma-ray component. Moreover, we found in Fig.5.2.4 that the peak value of the photon spectra nearly stays constant over the whole range of dark matter masses considered in this thesis which also translates into the gamma-ray fluxes' behavior. Since the measurements of the Fermi-LAT experiment indicate a decrease of the diffusive gamma-ray flux with increasing energies we expect heavier dark matter to be constrained stronger than lighter dark matter. In fact, the gamma-ray flux induced by the dark matter decay mode $\psi \rightarrow udd$ for TeV-dark matter with a lifetime of $\tau_\psi = 1 \cdot 10^{28}$ s is of the size of the experimental measurement. Hence, the lower lifetime bounds from gamma-rays will be competitive with the MIN and MED antiproton bounds for heavy dark matter and they may be even stronger.

Additionally, we observe again that the size of the fluxes from decay modes induced by the operator $\lambda'_{d,1}\bar{q}l^c\Sigma_d$ is smaller than the one from fluxes induced by model realizations featuring $\lambda''_{d,1}\bar{u}d^c\Sigma_d^\dagger$ which will lead to less stringent lifetime bounds. This is, of course, a direct effect of the lower number of photons per decay event with $q\bar{q}l$ final state compared to final states with three quarks.

Although we do not have to keep track of any specific propagation model for gamma-rays and the uncertainties due to the choice of the galactic dark matter density profiles are negligible, the value of the local dark matter density introduces sizable uncertainties as in the case of antiproton cosmic rays since it likewise enters in the computation of the flux. Hence, we include these uncertainties as an error band in Fig. 5.3.7 which displays our lower limits on the dark matter lifetime derived in the gamma-ray channel. The PYTHON script we applied to generate the listed limits is given in Lst. D.8 in Appendix D.5.

All limits lie within the range from $1 \cdot 10^{27}$ s to $1 \cdot 10^{28}$ s where we find our expectations confirmed, namely that the strength of these bounds is increasing with increasing dark matter mass and they become stronger than the MED antiproton limits for heavy dark matter in the vicinity of 1 TeV. This increase is quite complementary to the behavior of the antiproton bounds. For gamma-rays, however, energy losses that occur on the way from their production site to the position of the Earth are much smaller such that we, in principle, observe the photon decay spectrum of a dark matter decay. This implies that there is a non-negligible flux contribution in the high-energy range which is different from the situation we encounter in the case of antiprotons. They suffer from a galactic propagation with energy losses during their way through the galaxy altering and deforming the original source spectra of antiprotons. Thus, the low-energy range of antiproton fluxes dominate the analysis of lower lifetime limits, although the theoretical, astrophysical antiproton background and the PAMELA measurements indicate a very low background in the high-energy range. In this sense, we can understand the observed complementarity between the bounds from these two distinct cosmic ray channels.

Moreover, Fig. 5.3.7a shows that the decay modes featuring third generation quarks are less severely constrained than other decay modes which is an impact of the shape of the photons' decay spectra. They suffer from dents and shifts into lower energy ranges resulting from the large rest mass of the top quark. This explains why an analogous effect was not observable in the case of antiprotons. There, the low-energy behavior of the flux is the important part of the analysis.

Figure 5.3.7: Lower lifetime bounds (a) as a function of the dark matter mass derived from the comparison of the sum of extragalactic and galactic gamma-ray contribution due to dark matter decays according to Eqs.3.2.1 and 3.2.3 to the 50 months IGRB measurements of the Fermi-LAT experiment [7]. We show the bounds in the case of the NFW density profile and display error bands accounting for the uncertainty of the local dark matter density where the solid lines denote the result for $\rho_\odot = 0.4 \text{ GeV cm}^{-3}$. Besides, we separately address each decay mode within the scope of this thesis. In (b) we provide the resulting upper bounds on the model specific parameter $|\lambda_\psi|^2 |\lambda|^2 / m_\Sigma^4$ for the decay modes where the approximation of massless final state quarks is reasonable.

Nonetheless, we should remark that the used errors of the Fermi-LAT data do not take into consideration all possible sources of uncertainty which are given in [7]. In this sense, our derived bounds should be seen as a raw estimate and, of course, introducing larger errors would possibly decrease the limits such that they appear to be less stringent than the antiproton limits of the MED propagation model, for example. Thus, we can conclude that limits from both cosmic ray channels are competitive but refined and detailed studies have to be conducted exploiting the full uncertainties of the IGRB measurements.

5.3.4 Limits from antideuteron searches and further prospects

Since the antideuteron spectra are not direct outcomes of the PYTHIA8 analyses we did not include their discussion in Sec. 5.2. Nonetheless, we make use of the antiproton and antineutron spectra resulting after the hadronization of a particular dark matter decay mode by applying the isotropic coalescence model via Eq. 3.2.13. We give the obtained spectra from the three decay modes $\psi \rightarrow udd$, $\psi \rightarrow tbb$ and $\psi \rightarrow t\bar{b}\tau^-$, $b\bar{b}\nu_\tau$ for the dark matter masses $m_\psi = 250$ GeV and $m_\psi = 1$ TeV because then we can easily compare our results with those found by Dal et al. in [53]. There, the authors considered generic supersymmetric dark matter annihilating into various standard model particles among which we find the bottom-antibottom pair that is also covered by our minimal model in its three body decay $\psi \rightarrow b\bar{b}\nu_\tau$. In Fig. 5.3.8 we put our antideuteron spectra and the findings of Dal et al. side by side.

At first, we focus on the antideuteron spectra from the decay mode $\psi \rightarrow t\bar{b}\tau^-$, $b\bar{b}\nu_\tau$ and the dashed spectra in the plot of Dal et al. Of course, their blue lines are associated to a dark matter particle of 300 GeV which should not differ much from the behavior of dark matter with a mass of 250 GeV. From a qualitative point of view, the spectra in both figures almost coincide although, on one side, we have chosen a slightly smaller coalescence momentum than that of Dal et al. which is $p_0 = 160$ MeV and, on the other side, we consider in this thesis dark matter decays and not annihilations. Thus, we should expect the sizes of our spectra to be slightly decreased. Several explanations can be invoked, for example, our decay mode is a mixture of top and bottom quark final states whereas the annihilations only feature bottom quarks such that maybe our antineutron and antiproton yields are higher or the difference is due to the event generators that were used, namely PYTHIA8 or

Figure 5.3.8: Comparison of antideuteron spectra from the isotropic implementation of the coalescence model as given in Eq. 3.2.13 between three decay modes of the minimal decaying dark matter model in for dark matter masses of 250 GeV (blue) as well as 1 TeV (red) in (a) and a generic supersymmetric dark matter candidate’s annihilations into $b\bar{b}$ for masses of 300 GeV (dotted blue line) as well as 1 TeV (red dotted line) in (b) as reported in [52, 53]. In addition, the figure in (b) provides the corresponding antideuteron spectra when applying the coalescence condition in an event-by-event analysis. Moreover, these spectra were generated using a coalescence momentum $p_0 = 160$ MeV and the event generator HERWIG++. The sample decays of our model were chosen in order to show the outcome of both interaction Lagrangians of the scalar field and with $\psi \rightarrow t\bar{b}\tau^-, \bar{b}\bar{b}\nu_\tau$ we have a comparable decay mode featuring a bottom-antibottom pair in the final state. All spectra are displayed with respect to the scaled kinetic energy $x = T/m_{DM}$.

HERWIG++ respectively. Nevertheless, our spectra fit into the expectations of the isotropic approach to the coalescence model.

As expected, the larger antiproton and antineutron yield of trilinear decays into quarks leads to an increase of the number of formed antideuterons and, hence, enhanced values of the antideuteron spectra. Moreover, the difference between the spectra of the decay modes $\psi \rightarrow udd$ and $\psi \rightarrow tbb$ is marginal so that the limits from indirect searches in the antideuteron channel should exhibit only minor deviations.

However, Fig. 5.3.8b also yields information about the antideuteron spectra generated from the coalescence model applied in an event-by-event analysis. In fact, these spectra do not decrease as fast as the isotropic spectra in the direction of high-kinetic energies. Thus, the antideuteron yield of this approach is remarkably higher than estimated from our findings. Already from this comparison we can identify limitations of the isotropic approach.

In the following, we want to study the limits from dark matter antideuteron fluxes on the lifetime of the dark matter. This analysis will be not as detailed as the one of the previous cosmic ray channels especially because there is only one experimental measurement of the antideuteron flux available. The BESS balloon-borne experiment did not observe a single antideuteron event with a kinetic energy per nucleon in the range of 0.17 (GeV/n) and 1.15 (GeV/n) from which an upper bound on the antideuteron flux of $\Phi_{\bar{d}} < 1.9 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ (GeV/n)}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1} \text{ sr}^{-1}$ was derived in [72].

We impose lower bounds by demanding that the sum of dark matter antideuteron flux and astrophysical background [89] does not exceed this upper bound in the stated energy bin. Since this background flux was derived for the MED propagation model and with a Fisk potential of $\phi_F = 0.5 \text{ GV}$ we will not go beyond this setting. Furthermore, we adopt the treatment of the uncertainties from the previous studies by referring only to the NFW profile and by giving an error band due to the uncertainty of the local dark matter density. Fig. 5.3.9 summarizes the obtained lower limits in case of the sample decay modes $\psi \rightarrow udd$, $\psi \rightarrow css$ and $\psi \rightarrow u\bar{d}e^-$, $d\bar{d}\nu_e$. The PYTHON script we applied to perform this study is listed in Lst. D.9 of Appendix D.5.

Since the antideuteron spectra of the different decay modes associated to a particular interaction operator of the scalar do not show many differences we only refer to these three decay modes in order to not clutter the plot. Moreover, as the upper bound from the BESS experiment is not as stringent as the PAMELA or Fermi-LAT measurements, the antideuteron bounds are much weaker than the antiproton or gamma-ray limits. In fact, we do not gain any new constraints from this analysis. However, these rather weak bounds should be seen as a first estimate of the viability of the antideuteron cosmic ray channel. It was not the purpose of the BESS experiment to concentrate on the detection of antideuterons, the resulting upper bound was a mere byproduct. The upcoming AMS-02 experiment and the GAPS balloon-borne experiment will probe this specific antimatter cosmic ray channel with an increased sensitivity. To be more precise, they will outperform the BESS upper limit by more than two orders of magnitude: AMS-02 searches for cosmic antideuterons in two energy windows, namely $0.2 \leq T \leq 0.8 \text{ (GeV/n)}$ and $2.2 \leq T \leq 4.4 \text{ (GeV/n)}$. The second one covers the region where the estimated astrophysical background flux exhibits its maximum value. In both windows the expected flux sensitivity is $\Phi_{\bar{d}} = 1 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ (GeV/n)}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1} \text{ sr}^{-1}$ [45]. The balloon-borne GAPS experiment will perform a series of flights in Antarctica so that a total

Figure 5.3.9: Lower lifetime bounds derived from the upper limit on the antideuteron flux given by the measurements of the BESS balloon-borne experiment [72] for sample decay modes of the minimal decaying dark matter model over the range of dark matter masses considered in this thesis. These bounds are with respect to the sum of the dark matter antideuteron flux and the astrophysical background [89] in the MED propagation model and solar modulation according to a Fisk potential of $\phi_F = 0.5$ GV choosing the NFW density profile. The error bands display the uncertainty due to the value of the local dark matter density ρ_\odot where the solid line refers to $\rho_\odot = 0.4 \text{ GeV cm}^{-3}$.

flux sensitivity of $\Phi_{\bar{d}} = 3.5 \cdot 10^{-7} (\text{GeV/n})^{-1} \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1} \text{ sr}^{-1}$ is reached in the energy range $0.1 \leq T \leq 0.25$ (GeV/n) in the ultra-long duration flight [70]. This way both experiments probe complementary energy windows with a small overlap.

These sensitivity prospects are helpful to estimate the viability of constraints on dark matter models which we will confirm by comparing the dark matter antideuteron fluxes for several decay modes of our model to the expected sensitivities in the respective energy region. To this end, we depict the fluxes of the decay modes of Fig. 5.3.8 with respect to the usual dark matter mass samples $m_\psi \in \{15, 100, 1000\}$ GeV and choose the dark matter lifetime to be $\tau_\psi = 1 \cdot 10^{28}$ s. Adopting the parameter settings of the astrophysical antideuteron background flux, we obtain the desired comparison in Fig. 5.3.10.

It is quite striking that the dark matter antideuteron fluxes populate the low-energy ranges whereas the astrophysical background peaks at larger kinetic energies due to the discussed production thresholds. Thus, AMS-02 and GAPS were built to explore

Figure 5.3.10: Antideuteron flux $\Phi_{\bar{d}}$ from dark matter decays with respect to two different scalar interaction operators for three distinct choices of dark matter masses 15 GeV (blue), 100 GeV (brown) and 1 TeV (green). We display the expectations from $\psi \rightarrow u\bar{d}d$ (dot-dashed) and $\psi \rightarrow t\bar{b}b$ (dotted) associated to $\lambda'_{d,1} \bar{u}d^c \Sigma_d^\dagger$ as well as $\psi \rightarrow u\bar{d}e^-, d\bar{d}\nu_e$ (solid) and $\psi \rightarrow t\bar{b}\tau^-, b\bar{b}\nu_\tau$ coming from $\lambda'_{d,1} \bar{q}l^c \Sigma_d$ fixing the dark matter lifetime to be $\tau_\psi = 1 \cdot 10^{28} \text{ s}$, the local dark matter density at $\rho_\odot = 0.4 \text{ GeV cm}^{-3}$ and assuming the NFW density profile. Moreover, we show the astrophysical antideuteron flux contribution as computed in [89] for the MED parameter set of galactic propagation with a Fisk potential of $\phi_F = 0.5 \text{ GV}$ accounting for solar modulation effects. In addition, the existing upper bound [72] from the BESS balloon-borne experiment is given in red. Moreover, the expected flux sensitivity of the AMS-02 experiment (orange) [45] and the ultra long duration balloon flight with GAPS (yellow) [70] are depicted in the respective kinetic energy range.

exactly this energy range as it is nearly free of disturbing background. Indeed, we find that the antideuteron fluxes of our model lie inside the GAPS and possibly AMS-02 sensitivity ranges such that a hypothetical antideuteron signal would be a strong sign of dark matter presence. Of course, the second AMS-02 window at about 3 GeV is capable of testing the expected size of the background flux.

Besides, as in the case of antiprotons, lighter dark matter is constrained more severely by antideuteron searches since their induced fluxes reach higher values in the probed sensitivity ranges. Such a behavior we also observed for the antiproton fluxes where, nonetheless, the heavier dark matter still produced sizable fluxes at kinetic energies around 100 GeV. The antideuteron fluxes decrease much faster leaving only imprints in the low-energy ranges. In fact, this can be accounted to

the isotropic coalescence model that we used since the antideuteron spectra revealed such a sharp decrease, too. The antideuteron fluxes in [39, 53] which are based in the isotropic approach coincide with ours in this characteristic feature. Antideuteron fluxes derived with respect to an event-by-event analysis in [53, 57, 97] possess a shape that very much resembles the corresponding antiproton fluxes such that they seem to better reflect the physical realization of the actual antideuteron formation. In general, the antideuteron channel possesses a great potential to observe remnants of dark matter interactions in the sensitivity ranges of the upcoming experiments AMS-02 and GAPS. Nevertheless, it is obvious that the simple but limited and inaccurate isotropic realization of the coalescence model should not be used to constrain a dark matter model with indirect searches. More physical models of antideuteron formation should be taken into account when, finally, measurement results will become available.

6 Summary and outlook

The unresolved question about the nature of dark matter is one of the most flourishing branches of research in modern physics. A plethora of dark matter models was developed in order to yield a suitable solution to this problem. In this thesis we examined one of these models featuring only a minimal set of new particles and interactions among which we find a decaying dark matter candidate and a heavy, charged scalar field. Although coupling very weakly to ordinary matter, we illustrated suitable mechanisms that are capable of producing this kind of dark matter in amounts necessary to account for the correct dark matter relic density. From a cosmological point of view, this minimal dark matter model is viable and by virtue of its generality and simplicity it is an excellent candidate for further studies.

In this sense, we examined in detail the impacts of decays of the minimal model's unstable dark matter candidate on the shape and strength of the Earth's cosmic rays in order to constrain its lifetime. To this end, we gave arguments why a particular cosmic ray channel might be a suitable starting point of such indirect searches or not. Among those channels, we identified the gamma-ray as well as antimatter channels to possess the most promising prospects of constraining dark matter models and we stated some of the experimental data of recent measurements of cosmic ray fluxes by Fermi-LAT and PAMELA.

Having established the theoretical framework to calculate the cosmic ray fluxes of gamma-rays, antiprotons and antideuterons induced by dark matter decays, we gave a detailed description of the minimal decaying dark matter model we wanted to study. Moreover, we identified the two interaction operators $\lambda''_{d,1} \bar{u} d^c \Sigma_d^\dagger$ and $\lambda'_{d,1} \bar{q} l^c \Sigma_d$ of the scalar field among the hadronic models of this theory which are of certain interest due to a large antiproton and photon yield of the associated dark matter decays. In fact, we analytically calculated the total and differential decay rates of trilinear R -parity violating decays into either three quarks or two quarks and a lepton which result from these two particular choices. Having at hand explicit formulæ

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for the total decay width of the dark matter particle enables us to rewrite bounds on the lifetime of the dark matter in terms of bounds on the model's parameters.

We then turned to the particle physics input necessary for the calculation of dark matter cosmic ray fluxes. We illustrated our approach to generate photon, antiproton and antineutron decay spectra according to our model with MADGRAPH5 and PYTHIA8 and provided the used scripts and programs to perform this step. The subsequent discussion of these spectra revealed that our results qualitatively match the corresponding spectra available in the literature and it is possible to distinguish the spectra of both operators by comparing their respective photon or antiproton yield which is larger in the case of trilinear decay into three quarks. On the other hand, we observed that the spectra of both operators very much resemble each other so that a clear distinction between these spectra solely based on their shapes seems not feasible. In fact, the shape of the decay spectra becomes more important if we want to distinguish decay modes of different flavor: On one side, decay modes featuring first or second generation quarks/leptons exhibit nearly coinciding decay spectra where processes with first generation particles produce slightly larger numbers of high-energy antiprotons, antineutrons or photons. On the other side, the reduction of the amount of high-energy final states in case of third generation decay modes is clearly sizable. As a matter of fact, compared to the gamma-ray limits from lighter generations, this behavior led to reduced limits on the dark matter lifetime in this particular cosmic ray channel.

Besides, we simulated the formation of antideuterons after dark matter decays via the application of the isotropic (factorized) coalescence model which comprises of the multiplication of antiproton and antineutron spectra. We noted that our findings very well coincide with preceding studies of antideuteron formation with respect to the isotropic coalescence model. Nevertheless, we remarked several difference between this approach and the spectra of antideuterons whose formation is based on an event-by event application of the coalescence condition.

Subsequently, we tried to estimate the strength of the constraints on the dark matter lifetime in case of antiproton and gamma-ray fluxes by comparing them to the available experimental measurements in the respective cosmic ray channel. We concluded that the low-energy range below 1 GeV of the antiproton flux as probed by the PAMELA satellite seems to be the stronger limitation for a hypothetical dark matter contribution whereas the high-energy range above 100 GeV is the dominant limiting factor for gamma-ray fluxes. Moreover, we investigated the degree of uncertainty on

the limits due to the choice of dark matter density profile or the local dark matter density. It turned out, that different choices of dark matter density profiles do not alter the results significantly such that we ignored this factor in our further analyses but the local dark matter density is a non-negligible uncertainty in our studies. Besides, we gave prospects on the observation of antideuterons in the low-energy range which is probed by the upcoming AMS-02 and GAPS experiments. As a matter of fact, the extremely low astrophysical background paired with the comparatively large dark matter induced antideuteron fluxes in their sensitivity ranges imply that the antideuteron channel might be an essential way to unambiguously confirm the presence of dark matter.

After describing the method how we derive lower bounds on the dark matter lifetime, we performed this analysis with respect to the three mentioned cosmic ray channels and dark matter masses between 10 GeV and 1 TeV. The resulting lower bounds we summarize in Fig. 6.0.1 displaying one sample decay mode per interaction operator, namely $\psi \longrightarrow udd$ in blue representing $\lambda''_{d,1} \bar{u}d^c \Sigma_d^\dagger$ and $\psi \longrightarrow u\bar{d}e^-, d\bar{d}\nu_e$ in brown representing $\lambda'_{d,1} \bar{q}l^c \Sigma_d$.

We were able to derive lower lifetime bounds spanning over approximately eight orders of magnitude where the bounds from antideuteron searches are the weakest with $\tau_\psi \sim 10^{25} - 10^{26}$ s and the bounds from antiprotons with MAX propagation are the strongest with $\tau_\psi \sim 10^{28} - 10^{31}$ s. We observed the antideuteron and antiproton bounds to become less stringent with increasing dark matter masses whereas the gamma-ray limits increase in this direction, eventually exceeding the antiproton MED limits at dark matter masses of about 1 TeV. Under the assumption of MIN propagation parameters, the limits from antiproton searches are dominated by the gamma-ray limits for any dark matter mass. Furthermore, in the case of antiproton searches we concluded that our limits can compete with the bounds being derived with respect to a similar dark matter model in [74] and even outperform them when considering trilinear decays into three quarks.

Our analyses of the dark matter antiproton fluxes revealed a great impact of solar modulation on the lifetime limits. In fact, most of the derived lower bounds originate from the PAMELA data in the low-energy region ≤ 1 GeV which is heavily affected by energy losses due to the solar wind. The force-field approximation which is paraphrased with the help of the Fisk potential does yield reasonable results for antiprotons. However, it is not entirely based on a solid theoretical foundation and since a theoretically sound description of solar modulation is still a subject of

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Figure 6.0.1: Summary plot of the lower bounds on the dark matter lifetime from antiprotons, gamma-rays and antideuterons for two distinct interaction operators of the scalar field. We display one sample decay mode for each operator, namely $\psi \rightarrow u d d$ (blue) representing $\lambda''_{d,1} \bar{u} d^c \Sigma_d^\dagger$ and $\psi \rightarrow u \bar{d} e^-, d \bar{d} \nu_e$ (brown) representing $\lambda'_{d,1} \bar{q} l^c \Sigma_d$. All bounds are with respect to the parameter settings stated in the respective plots in Sec. 5.3 while fixing the NFW dark matter density profile.

research, we should find a method to at least estimate the limits from dark matter antiproton fluxes independent of a specific model of solar modulation. As the solar wind mainly affects low-energetic charged particles, it is believed that particles with kinetic energies larger than ~ 10 GeV suffer from these energy losses only to a minor extent. Thus, we can apply our scheme of chapter 5 only to the PAMELA data for energies above 10 GeV while dropping the application of solar modulation to both the astrophysical background and the dark matter antiproton flux. Fortunately, the authors of [38] also give the best-fit parameters of the fit function of the astrophysical component also for this scenario.

In this setting, a re-evaluation of the antiproton limits yields drastically reduced bounds for light dark matter ≤ 100 GeV which is intuitively clear since either the spectra do not extend to energies larger than 10 GeV or only one or two of the PAMELA energy bins can be probed. This means that the gamma-ray limits are most stringent for these dark matter masses. The mass range from 100 GeV to 1 TeV yields more reliable results because the number of available data points increases.

Here, we find that for all decay modes the MIN limits are not much lower than the corresponding limits including solar modulation whereas the MED limits are reduced by almost one order of magnitude. However, this effect washes out the larger the dark matter mass becomes so that the bound for 1 TeV dark matter is nearly the same in both cases. On the other side, the MAX limits without solar modulation are not comparable to the ones that include this effect. To be more precise, these lower bounds take values around $\sim 1 \cdot 10^{28}$ s which corresponds to our findings that the MAX antiproton fluxes are predominantly constrained by the low-energy range of the PAMELA measurements. Moreover, the flavor aspect of the five decay modes becomes more important without solar modulation since decays involving third generation quarks show weaker bounds than their counterparts for all three propagation schemes. This can be traced back to the shape of the antiproton decay spectra which were affected by shifts to lower energies so that the resulting antiproton fluxes are also reduced in comparison with the respective decay modes with first or second generation quarks. All in all, these analyses yield quite conservative bounds with the advantage that they do not incorporate any peculiarities due to the modeling of solar modulation.

Using the lower bounds from gamma-ray and antiproton searches, we could proceed further in the following way: We have already computed the corresponding upper bounds on the model specific parameter $|\lambda_\psi|^2 |\lambda|^2 / m_\Sigma^4$ for those decay modes whose final states can be assumed to be massless. The authors of [23] examined the collider phenomenology of the minimal decaying dark matter model assuming the mass of the scalar field to lie within the LHC reach, i.e. $m_\Sigma \lesssim 3$ TeV. Moreover, they provide regions in the (m_Σ, λ) -plane where striking collider signals of the scalar field are expected such that a reconstruction of the model parameters seems feasible. Using Eq. 4.3.4, which is true for scalar masses in the LHC range, we are able to fix the value of the parameter λ_ψ by demanding the correct dark matter relic density for the dark matter candidate of the minimal model. This way, our lifetime bounds yield upper limits on the ratio $|\lambda|/m_\Sigma^2$, thus we are able to check whether the regions of interest in the (m_Σ, λ) -plane can still be populated and constrain the model's collider prospects.

However, we have seen during the discussion of our results that there is much room for improvements of the approaches and methods we have chosen. For example, we adopted the precalculated analytic solutions of the transport equation for the three parameter sets in case of the dark matter flux. As we stressed in the respective

section, in order to obtain this analytic solution of the two-zone diffusion model, it is necessary to exclude further energy-losses and to modify the inelastic scattering of antiprotons on the interstellar matter. Moreover, we used a more elaborate astrophysical antiproton flux that encompasses these processes such that the dark matter component should be treated in the same way. Thus, a numerical simulation of the galactic propagation of the particles produced in dark matter decays might improve our findings. To this end, there exist public codes, for instance GALPROP¹ or DRAGON², performing the mentioned numerical treatment. Likewise, we observed a strong impact of solar modulation on the dark matter antiproton and antideuteron fluxes which is governed by the choice of the Fisk potential. Apart from this force-field realization of solar modulation one could also consider to simulate this effect numerically, too. In principle, one could adopt the approach in [71].

We always emphasized the differences between an event-by-event or isotropic implementation of the coalescence model. Since up to now, there is only one rather weak upper limit on the antideuteron flux these discrepancies do not come into play very much. Nevertheless, when the data of AMS-02 and GAPS become available, more refined models for the antideuteron formation should be taken into consideration because of their immense sensitivity in the promising energy ranges. In this sense, the investigation of the antideuteron channel should be redone with a Monte Carlo event-by-event implementation of the coalescence condition or it should even apply, for instance, the recently developed probabilistic formation model in [55].

A dedicated study of the preliminary data of the antiproton-to-proton ratio of the AMS-02 experiment in [79] concluded that there is no clear sign of an excess of the \bar{p}/p -ratio in any energy range which would make it mandatory to include primary antiprotons from dark matter annihilations or decays. Nevertheless, the AMS-02 experiment probes energy ranges above the PAMELA results and they might further refine the existing measurements of the antiproton flux. Thus, a reanalysis of the phenomenological impacts of the minimal model on the cosmic ray antiproton channel given the final AMS-02 measurements might yield tighter bounds.

In order to unambiguously detect a dark matter imprint in charged cosmic rays, it is necessary to address the main limitation of current indirect searches, namely the determination of the propagation parameters. The upcoming AMS-02 experiment will provide refined, accurate and reliable measurements of fluxes of light nuclei,

¹<http://galprop.stanford.edu>

²<http://www.dragonproject.org/Home.html>

like B- and C-nuclei, which are commonly used to find the best fit parameters of galactic propagation such that a better tuning of this essential astrophysical problem is possible. However, the authors of [94] question the common approach of determining propagation parameters with respect to Boron-to-Carbon ratios. They performed a Bayesian fit of the GALPROP parameters that best fit the observed proton, antiproton and helium fluxes and found significant deviations from the usual parameters derived with fits to Boron-to-Carbon ratios. As a conclusion, the authors remark as one interpretation that the properties of the interstellar medium might vary over scales of kpc while non-negligibly affecting the propagation of charged cosmic rays. In this sense, a hypothetical excess in a charged cosmic ray channel could simply reflect a misunderstanding of the galactic propagation of the respective charged particle. Thus, it is only possible to exploit the full potential of indirect searches by improving the current understanding of the astrophysical phenomena occurring in Milky Way.

Nonetheless, our analyses support the fact that indirect searches are a worthwhile subject of research in the field of dark matter. The already published high-precision measurements of AMS-02 as well as the upcoming data releases of this experiment will help improve the existing theoretical models. Moreover, they will extend our knowledge about the behavior of cosmic ray fluxes to energies in the TeV range so that the room for possible dark matter signals will be widened. In fact, a combination of the results of indirect searches with respect to different cosmic ray channels might increase the chance to identify a discovery of dark matter presence because the uncertainties and systematics affecting each particular channel can be reduced in a combined study. For example, considering our minimal model we could show that gamma-ray limits as well as antiproton limits in the MIN and MED setting are of comparable size. This means that a signal in one of these two channels should cause a detectable impact on the other one in order to be consistent with a decaying dark matter explanation. This picture will be completed by the increased sensitivities of GAPS and AMS-02 in the antideuteron channel. For the first time they will probe energy regions which are supposed to be mainly populated by antideuterons from putative dark matter interactions. In this sense, antideuteron events in these nearly background-free energy ranges are a smoking gun of dark matter presence.

6 *Summary and outlook*

A Units and Physical Constants

Throughout this thesis we will adopt the common notion of natural units which set the vacuum speed of light c , the reduced Planck constant \hbar and the Boltzmann constant k_B to unity:

$$c = \hbar = k_B = 1.$$

Within these special physical units of measurement the fundamental units time, length, mass and temperature are expressed in terms of the energy unit $1 \text{ eV} = 1.6021766208(98) \cdot 10^{-19} \text{ J}$ [108]. Recovering the standardized SI-units is accomplished via the following conversion factors [108] where the numbers in parentheses denote the one standard deviation uncertainty on the last digits:

Dimension	Unit	Conversion Factor	Value
time	1 eV^{-1}	$= 1 \text{ eV}^{-1} \hbar$	$= 6.58211899(16) \cdot 10^{-25} \text{ s}$
length	1 eV^{-1}	$= 1 \text{ eV}^{-1} \hbar c$	$= 1.973269631(49) \cdot 10^{-16} \text{ m}$
mass	1 eV	$= 1 \text{ eV} c^{-2}$	$= 1.782661758(44) \cdot 10^{-36} \text{ kg}$
temperature	1 eV	$= 1 \text{ eV} k_B^{-1}$	$= 1.1604505(20) \cdot 10^4 \text{ K}$

Subsequently, we give a list of the physical constants and parameters appearing in this thesis which are followed by their current value according to [108]:

Physical Constant or Parameter	Symbol	Value in SI-units
vacuum speed of light	c	$299792458 \frac{\text{m}}{\text{s}}$
reduced Planck constant	$\hbar = h/(2\pi)$	$1.054571800(13) \cdot 10^{-34} \text{ J s}$
elementary charge	e	$1.6021766208(98) \cdot 10^{-19} \text{ C}$
electron mass	m_e	$0.5109989461(31) \frac{\text{MeV}}{c^2}$
proton mass	m_p	$938.2720813(58) \frac{\text{MeV}}{c^2}$
neutron mass	m_n	$939.565346(23) \frac{\text{MeV}}{c^2}$
deuteron mass	m_d	$1875.612928(12) \frac{\text{MeV}}{c^2}$
charm quark mass	m_c	$1.275(25) \frac{\text{GeV}}{c^2}$

A Units and Physical Constants

Physical Constant or Parameter	Symbol	Value in SI-units
bottom quark mass	m_b	$4.18(3) \frac{\text{GeV}}{c^2}$
top quark mass	m_t	$(173.21 \pm 0.51 \pm 0.71) \frac{\text{GeV}}{c^2}$
gravitational constant	G	$6.67408(31) \cdot 10^{-11} \frac{\text{m}^3}{\text{kg s}^2}$
parsec	pc	$3.0856776 \cdot 10^{16} \text{ m}$
Planck mass	$m_{Pl} = \sqrt{\frac{\hbar c}{G}}$	$2.17651(13) \cdot 10^{-8} \text{ kg}$
reduced Planck mass	$M_{Pl} = \frac{m_{Pl}}{\sqrt{8\pi}}$	$4.34151(26) \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ kg}$
tropical year (equinox to equinox) (2011)	yr	556925.2 s
solar distance from Galactic center	r_\odot	8.33 kpc
local dark matter density	ρ_\odot	$0.4(1) \frac{\text{GeV}}{c^2 \text{cm}^3}$
present day Hubble expansion rate	H_0	$100h \frac{\text{km}}{\text{sMpc}}$
scale factor for Hubble expansion rate	h	0.673(12)
critical density of the universe	ρ_{crit}	$\frac{1.87847(23) \cdot 10^{-29}}{h^2} \frac{\text{g}}{\text{cm}^3}$
baryon density of the universe	Ω_b	$\frac{0.02207(27)}{h^2} = 0.0499(22)$
cold dark matter density of the universe	Ω_c	$\frac{0.1198(26)}{h^2} = 0.265(11)$
dark energy density of the Λ CDM universe	Ω_Λ	$0.685^{+0.0017}_{-0.0016}$
curvature	Ω_{tot}	1.000(7) (95% C.L.; CMB+BAO)
redshift of decoupling	z_{dec}	1090.2(7)

B Conventions, Dirac Algebra and associated formulæ

In this thesis we work in flat Minkowski space-time and use the language of special relativity. For the sake of consistency, we state here the most important choices of conventions and list the relevant formulæ occurring in the framework of quantum field theories.

B.1 Conventions in flat Minkowski space-time

Lorentz indices of the contravariant components of four-vectors and four-tensors are denoted by superscript Greek letters μ, ν, \dots which range from 0 to 3 whereas the covariant components are denoted by subscript Greek letters. Moreover, the indices of the spatial components of these objects are denoted by superscript (subscript) Latin letters i, j, \dots with values between 1 and 3.

The metric of flat Minkowski space-time is given by

$$\eta_{\mu\nu} = \eta^{\mu\nu} = \begin{pmatrix} +1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (\text{B.1.1})$$

We apply the Einstein summation convention in all our derivations, i.e. a pair of repeated indices must be summed over.

The invariant pseudo-scalar product of two four-vectors x^μ and y^μ is denoted by

$$x \cdot y = x_\mu y^\mu = \eta_{\mu\nu} x^\mu y^\nu = \eta^{\mu\nu} x_\mu y_\nu. \quad (\text{B.1.2})$$

In order to raise or lower the Lorentz indices of an object of space-time, one has to apply the metric according to

$$x^\mu = \eta^{\mu\nu} x_\nu, \quad x_\mu = \eta_{\mu\nu} x^\nu. \quad (\text{B.1.3})$$

A particular tensor of interest is the four-dimensional totally antisymmetric tensor $\varepsilon^{\mu\nu\rho\sigma}$ whose behavior is completely determined by fixing

$$\varepsilon^{0123} = +1. \quad (\text{B.1.4})$$

Its three-dimensional counterpart ε_{ijk} shall be equipped with the sign convention

$$\varepsilon_{123} = +1. \quad (\text{B.1.5})$$

B.2 Energy-momentum four-vector and Lorentz transformations

The energy E and the three-momentum \vec{p} of a particle with mass m define its energy-momentum four-vector $p^\mu = (E, \vec{p})^T$ which satisfies $p^2 = p_\mu p^\mu = E^2 - |\vec{p}|^2 = m^2$. The velocity $\vec{\beta}$ of this particle can then be recovered by

$$\vec{\beta} = \frac{\vec{p}}{E}. \quad (\text{B.2.1})$$

This relation may be reformulated as

$$\vec{p} = \gamma m \vec{\beta}, \quad (\text{B.2.2})$$

with

$$\gamma = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - |\vec{\beta}|^2}} = \frac{E}{m}. \quad (\text{B.2.3})$$

Transformations between two inertial frames S and S' are described by Lorentz transformations $\Lambda^\mu{}_\nu$ according to

$$x^\mu \mapsto (x')^\mu = \Lambda^\mu{}_\nu x^\nu \quad (\text{B.2.4})$$

and satisfying

$$\eta^{\mu\nu} = \Lambda^\mu{}_\rho \eta^{\rho\sigma} (\Lambda^\nu{}_\sigma)^T \quad (\text{B.2.5})$$

to ensure the invariance of the pseudo-scalar product in Minkowski space. Relation B.2.5 fully determines the allowed transformations between two inertial frames, namely rotations and boosts.

Consider now the case, where the coordinate axes of both inertial frames are aligned but the inertial frame S' moves with velocity $\vec{\beta}$ in an arbitrary direction. Thus, the energy E' and momentum \vec{p}' of the particle in S observed from S' are given by

$$\begin{pmatrix} E' \\ (p^1)' \\ (p^2)' \\ (p^3)' \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \gamma & -\beta^1\gamma & -\beta^2\gamma & -\beta^3\gamma \\ -\beta^1\gamma & 1 + (\gamma-1)\frac{(\beta^1)^2}{|\vec{\beta}|^2} & (\gamma-1)\frac{\beta^1\beta^2}{|\vec{\beta}|^2} & (\gamma-1)\frac{\beta^1\beta^3}{|\vec{\beta}|^2} \\ -\beta^2\gamma & (\gamma-1)\frac{\beta^1\beta^2}{|\vec{\beta}|^2} & 1 + (\gamma-1)\frac{(\beta^2)^2}{|\vec{\beta}|^2} & (\gamma-1)\frac{\beta^2\beta^3}{|\vec{\beta}|^2} \\ -\beta^3\gamma & (\gamma-1)\frac{\beta^1\beta^3}{|\vec{\beta}|^2} & (\gamma-1)\frac{\beta^2\beta^3}{|\vec{\beta}|^2} & 1 + (\gamma-1)\frac{(\beta^3)^2}{|\vec{\beta}|^2} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} E \\ p^1 \\ p^2 \\ p^3 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (\text{B.2.6})$$

The 4×4 -matrix connecting both energy-momentum four-vectors corresponds then to a pure Lorentz boost because of the alignment of the coordinate axes of both inertial frames. In particular, the Lorentz boost in Eq. B.2.6 transforms only the part of the momentum \vec{p} of the particle that is parallel to the relative velocity $\vec{\beta}$ between the inertial frames; the perpendicular part is not changed at all.

B.3 The Dirac Algebra

We want to briefly state the most important relations which often occur during the evaluation of Feynman diagrams. These relations are mainly taken from [113].

Treating fermions in quantum field theories involves the so-called Dirac gamma matrices γ^μ which form a Clifford algebra, known as the Dirac algebra, under the defining anticommutation relation

$$\{\gamma^\mu, \gamma^\nu\} = 2\eta^{\mu\nu}. \quad (\text{B.3.1})$$

These gamma matrices also carry spinor indices which are commonly suppressed in the notation. The individual gamma matrices fulfill certain relations on their own, namely

$$(\gamma^0)^2 = \mathbb{1}_4, \quad (\gamma^i)^2 = -\mathbb{1}_4 \quad (\text{B.3.2})$$

and for their hermitean conjugate holds

$$(\gamma^\mu)^\dagger = \gamma^0 \gamma^\mu \gamma^0. \quad (\text{B.3.3})$$

The covariant vector of gamma matrices γ_μ is derived in the same way as in the case of four-vectors given in Eq. B.1.3. Therefore, we find

$$\gamma_0 = \gamma^0 \quad \text{and} \quad \gamma_i = -\gamma^i. \quad (\text{B.3.4})$$

It is useful to introduce a fifth gamma matrix γ^5 which is built from the four fundamental matrices according to

$$\gamma^5 := i\gamma^0\gamma^1\gamma^2\gamma^3 = -\frac{i}{4!}\varepsilon_{\mu\nu\rho\sigma}\gamma^\mu\gamma^\nu\gamma^\rho\gamma^\sigma. \quad (\text{B.3.5})$$

It follows from Eq. B.3.1 that

$$\{\gamma^\mu, \gamma^5\} = 0, \quad (\gamma^5)^2 = \mathbb{1}_4, \quad (\gamma^5)^\dagger = \gamma^5. \quad (\text{B.3.6})$$

This additional matrix is used to construct two chirality projection operators P_L and P_R which project on the left-handed or right-handed component of a given Dirac spinor. These operators are defined by

$$P_L = \frac{1}{2}(\mathbb{1}_4 - \gamma^5) \quad \text{and} \quad P_R = \frac{1}{2}(\mathbb{1}_4 + \gamma^5). \quad (\text{B.3.7})$$

In particular, these projectors are orthogonal, i.e.

$$P_L P_R = P_R P_L = 0. \quad (\text{B.3.8})$$

Throughout the literature there exist many representations of the Dirac algebra leading to various representations of the gamma matrices. Which of these representations is chosen depends on the underlying problem but one standard choice is the Dirac representation that is most suitable when dealing with Dirac spinors. In this representation the gamma matrices are

$$\gamma^0 = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbb{1}_2 & 0 \\ 0 & -\mathbb{1}_2 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \gamma^i = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \sigma^i \\ -\sigma^i & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \gamma^5 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \mathbb{1}_2 \\ \mathbb{1}_2 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (\text{B.3.9})$$

where we used the Pauli matrices

$$\sigma^1 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \sigma^2 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -i \\ i & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \sigma^3 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (\text{B.3.10})$$

As already mentioned, gamma matrices are applied to Dirac spinors Ψ_D which should better be named bispinors as they are composed out of two two-component Weyl spinors χ_α and $\eta^{\dagger\dot{\alpha}}$ according to

$$\Psi_D := \begin{pmatrix} \chi_\alpha \\ \eta^{\dagger\dot{\alpha}} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (\text{B.3.11})$$

These Weyl spinors are anticommuting, complex objects that carry two distinct types of spinor indices, namely $\alpha = 1, 2$ or $\dot{\alpha} = 1, 2$, respectively. Raising and lowering of spinor indices is done by the means of the antisymmetric symbols

$$\varepsilon_{\alpha\beta}, \quad \varepsilon^{\alpha\beta}, \quad \varepsilon_{\dot{\alpha}\dot{\beta}}, \quad \varepsilon^{\dot{\alpha}\dot{\beta}}, \quad \text{such that} \quad \varepsilon^{12} = +1, \quad \varepsilon_{12} = -1. \quad (\text{B.3.12})$$

Since these spinor indices are commonly suppressed to shorten the notation, the complete expression can be recovered by using

$$\chi\eta = \chi^\alpha\eta_\alpha, \quad \chi^\dagger\eta^\dagger = \chi^\dagger_{\dot{\alpha}}\eta^{\dagger\dot{\alpha}}. \quad (\text{B.3.13})$$

To construct a Lorentz-invariant quantity from Dirac spinors, the adjoint Dirac spinor $\overline{\Psi}_D$ is introduced via

$$\overline{\Psi}_D := \Psi_D^\dagger \gamma^0 = (\eta^\alpha, \chi^\dagger_{\dot{\alpha}}) \quad (\text{B.3.14})$$

because the product $\overline{\Psi}_D \Psi_D$ is an invariant Lorentz scalar.

Likewise, there is the charge-conjugated Dirac spinor Ψ_D^c , obtained by

$$\Psi_D^c := C (\overline{\Psi}_D)^T = \begin{pmatrix} \eta_\alpha \\ \chi^{\dagger\dot{\alpha}} \end{pmatrix} \quad (\text{B.3.15})$$

which involves the charge conjugation matrix C of the Dirac algebra satisfying [58]

$$-C = C^T = C^{-1} = C^\dagger \quad \text{and} \quad C(\Gamma^i)^T C^\dagger = \eta_i \Gamma^i, \quad (\text{B.3.16})$$

where

$$\eta_i = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{for } \Gamma^i = \mathbb{1}_4, \gamma^\mu \gamma^5, \gamma^5 \\ -1 & \text{for } \Gamma^i = \gamma^\mu, \frac{i}{2} [\gamma^\mu, \gamma^\nu] \Big|_{\mu < \nu}. \end{cases} \quad (\text{B.3.17})$$

A Majorana spinor Ψ_M can now be defined as a four-component spinor being invariant under charge conjugation, such that it corresponds to a Dirac spinor whose Weyl spinors fulfill $\eta = \chi$ and in this sense

$$\Psi_M^c := C (\overline{\Psi_M})^T = \Psi_M = \begin{pmatrix} \chi_\alpha \\ \chi^{\dagger\dot{\alpha}} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (\text{B.3.18})$$

The importance of Dirac spinors results from the fact that they are part of the solutions of the Dirac equation

$$(i\gamma^\mu \partial_\mu - m)\psi(x) = 0 \quad (\text{B.3.19})$$

describing the dynamics of spin- $\frac{1}{2}$ fermions with $\partial_\mu = \partial/\partial x^\mu$. In particular, there exist four linearly independent plane-wave solutions of the Dirac equation, each involving a Dirac spinor u^s or v^s respectively denoting particle or antiparticle solutions of the Dirac equation with $s = \pm\frac{1}{2}$:

$$\psi(x) = u^s(p)e^{-ip \cdot x}, \quad \psi(x) = v^s(p)e^{ip \cdot x}. \quad (\text{B.3.20})$$

In these solutions p denotes the four-momentum of the fermion with mass m and the Dirac spinors obey

$$(\not{p} - m)u^s(p) = 0, \quad (\not{p} + m)v^s(p) = 0, \quad (\text{B.3.21})$$

where we used the Feynman slash notation

$$\not{p} = \gamma^\mu p_\mu. \quad (\text{B.3.22})$$

The constraints in Eq. B.3.21 lead to the spin sums for spin- $\frac{1}{2}$ fermions which simplify the calculations of spin-averaged squared matrix elements. They are written

in the following way

$$\begin{aligned}\sum_{s=\pm\frac{1}{2}} u^s(p)\bar{u}^s(p) &= (\not{p} - m), \\ \sum_{s=\pm\frac{1}{2}} v^s(p)\bar{v}^s(p) &= (\not{p} + m).\end{aligned}\tag{B.3.23}$$

Additionally, the evaluation of squared matrix elements can be simplified by taking into account the following identities for traces of gamma matrices that can be derived from their fundamental anticommutation relation:

$$\begin{aligned}\text{tr}(\mathbf{1}_4) &= 4, \\ \text{tr}(\text{product of odd \#s of } \gamma\text{'s}) &= 0, \\ \text{tr}(\gamma^\mu\gamma^\nu) &= 4\eta^{\mu\nu}, \\ \text{tr}(\gamma^\mu\gamma^\nu\gamma^\rho\gamma^\sigma) &= 4(\eta^{\mu\nu}\eta^{\rho\sigma} - \eta^{\mu\rho}\eta^{\nu\sigma} + \eta^{\mu\sigma}\eta^{\nu\rho}), \\ \text{tr}(\gamma^5) &= 0, \\ \text{tr}(\gamma^\mu\gamma^\nu\gamma^5) &= 0, \\ \text{tr}(\gamma^\mu\gamma^\nu\gamma^\rho\gamma^\sigma\gamma^5) &= -4i\varepsilon^{\mu\nu\rho\sigma}.\end{aligned}\tag{B.3.24}$$

C Feynman Rules of the Minimal Decaying Dark Matter Model and Kinematics

The Lagrangian of the minimal decaying dark matter model introduced in Eqs. 4.1.1 and 4.1.2 of Sec. 4.1 gives rise to a number of different decay channels of the dark matter particle ψ . The calculation of the respective differential and total decay rates relies on the knowledge of the Feynman rules that can be derived from the operator content of the model. In the following we provide a summary of the Feynman rules which are necessary to compute squared matrix elements of the decay channels that we investigated in this thesis and which are stated in Sec. 4.2. Subsequently, we give a list of kinematical relations useful in the context of three-body decays which we apply in order to derive explicit expressions for differential and total decay rates.

C.1 Feynman Rules

The Feynman rules of the minimal decaying dark matter model are extracted from its interaction Lagrangian displayed in Eqs. 4.1.1 and 4.1.2. Since the dark matter particle ψ is a Majorana fermion we cannot apply the usual spinor assignments to incoming and outgoing (anti)fermions because Wick contractions of Majorana particles with Dirac fermions include the charge conjugation matrix C . Nevertheless, the authors of [58] developed an approach which yields Feynman rules for Majorana particles without ambiguities in the choice of the relative sign between interfering diagrams and without an explicit appearance of the charge conjugation matrix. This scheme introduces a continuous fermion flow for every complete fermion chain whose direction can be chosen arbitrarily as long as the resulting Feynman rules are applied consistently. Hence, the matrix element is written down in the opposite direction of this flow.

We will adopt the continuous fermion flow and denote it with arrows above the usual fermion lines. It should not be confused with the momentum flow in the diagram which we do not display. In principle, the fermion flow can be extended to Lagrangians with an explicit charge conjugation as it is the case in the interaction Lagrangian of the scalar field Σ_f . However, we spell out explicitly the scalar's interaction vertices originating from Eq.4.1.2, i.e. we state the spinor structure together with the vertex factor.

In the following, we display chiral fermions with solid lines, scalar fields with dashed lines and the dark matter particles with solid lines equipped with two arrows pointing at each other. The Greek letters α, β and γ are reserved for the color indices of the scalar particle as well as those of the Dirac fermions and, in addition, $\varepsilon_{\alpha\beta\gamma}$ denotes the totally antisymmetric fundamental $SU(3)$ -triplet tensor of the color algebra. Furthermore, we only give the Feynman rules for the scalar field Σ_d .

The Feynman diagrams in this thesis were drawn with the ‘‘TikZ-Feynman’’ package designed by J. Ellis [65].

In all diagrams below the momentum p flows from the left to the right.

External fermion lines at vertices with Majorana particles:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \begin{array}{ccc} \xrightarrow{\quad} \bullet & \xleftarrow{\quad} \bullet & \xleftrightarrow{\quad} \bullet \\ \xrightarrow{\quad} \bullet & \xleftarrow{\quad} \bullet & \xleftrightarrow{\quad} \bullet \end{array} = u(p, r), \\
 & \begin{array}{ccc} \bullet \xrightarrow{\quad} & \bullet \xleftarrow{\quad} & \bullet \xleftrightarrow{\quad} \\ \bullet \xrightarrow{\quad} & \bullet \xleftarrow{\quad} & \bullet \xleftrightarrow{\quad} \end{array} = \bar{u}(p, r), \\
 & \begin{array}{ccc} \bullet \xleftarrow{\quad} & \bullet \xleftarrow{\quad} & \bullet \xleftarrow{\quad} \\ \bullet \xleftarrow{\quad} & \bullet \xleftarrow{\quad} & \bullet \xleftarrow{\quad} \end{array} = v(p, r), \\
 & \begin{array}{ccc} \xleftarrow{\quad} \bullet & \xleftarrow{\quad} \bullet & \xleftarrow{\quad} \bullet \\ \xleftarrow{\quad} \bullet & \xleftarrow{\quad} \bullet & \xleftarrow{\quad} \bullet \end{array} = \bar{v}(p, r).
 \end{aligned}$$

External scalar lines:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \begin{array}{ccc} \cdots \xrightarrow{\quad} \bullet & \cdots \xleftarrow{\quad} \bullet & \\ \bullet \cdots \xrightarrow{\quad} & \bullet \cdots \xleftarrow{\quad} & \end{array} = 1, \\
 & \begin{array}{ccc} \bullet \cdots \xrightarrow{\quad} & \bullet \cdots \xleftarrow{\quad} & \\ \bullet \cdots \xrightarrow{\quad} & \bullet \cdots \xleftarrow{\quad} & \end{array} = 1.
 \end{aligned}$$

Scalar propagator:

$$\bullet \cdots \xrightarrow{\quad} \bullet = \frac{i}{p^2 - m_\Sigma^2}.$$

Fermion propagators:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \bullet \xrightarrow{\quad} \bullet &= \frac{i(\not{p} + m_f)}{p^2 - m_f^2}, \\
 \bullet \xleftarrow{\quad} \bullet &= \frac{i(-\not{p} + m_f)}{p^2 - m_f^2}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Dark matter Yukawa interaction vertices:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \begin{array}{c} \alpha \\ \nearrow \\ \xrightarrow{\quad} \\ \leftarrow \\ \searrow \\ \beta \end{array} &= -i\lambda_{\psi dR} P_L \delta_{\alpha\beta}, & \begin{array}{c} \alpha \\ \searrow \\ \xleftarrow{\quad} \\ \leftarrow \\ \nearrow \\ \beta \end{array} &= -i\lambda_{\psi dR} P_L \delta_{\alpha\beta}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Scalar Yukawa interaction vertices due to $\lambda''_{d,1} \bar{u} d^c \Sigma_d^\dagger$:

$$\begin{array}{c} f_\beta \\ \nearrow \\ \Sigma_\alpha^\dagger \text{---} \\ \leftarrow \\ \searrow \\ f_\gamma^c \end{array} = \bar{u}_\beta i\lambda''_{d,1} P_L \varepsilon_{\alpha\beta\gamma} \gamma^0 C u_\gamma^*.$$

Scalar Yukawa interaction vertices due to $\lambda'_{d,1} \bar{q} l^c \Sigma_d$:

$$\begin{array}{c} f_\beta \\ \nearrow \\ \Sigma_\alpha \text{---} \\ \rightarrow \\ \searrow \\ f^c \end{array} = \bar{u}_\beta i\lambda'_{d,1} P_L \delta_{\alpha\beta} \gamma^0 C u_\gamma^*.$$

Figure C.2.1: Schematic picture of a generic three-body decay establishing the definitions of variables we use throughout this section. Figure taken from [108].

C.2 Kinematical Relations

We want to discuss helpful relations in the context of a three-body decay, i.e. an interaction of the form $1 \rightarrow 3$ which is schematically depicted in Fig. C.2.1 that also includes the definitions of variables we use in the subsequent formulæ. The initial situation is characterized by a mother particle with mass M and four-momentum P^μ which is decaying into three daughter particles with masses m_1 , m_2 and m_3 as well as the respective four-momenta p_1^μ , p_2^μ and p_3^μ . Energy-momentum conservation at the decay vertex is expressed as

$$P^\mu = p_1^\mu + p_2^\mu + p_3^\mu. \quad (\text{C.2.1})$$

To shorten the notation and to obtain Lorentz invariant quantities which are of use in the further discussion, we define the following kinematic variables

$$\begin{aligned} s &= P^2 && = M^2 \\ s_1 &= (P - p_1)^2 && = (p_2 + p_3)^2 \\ s_2 &= (P - p_2)^2 && = (p_1 + p_3)^2 \\ s_3 &= (P - p_3)^2 && = (p_1 + p_2)^2. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{C.2.2})$$

The variable s does not contain any kinematical information about the decay since it solely is the invariant mass of the mother particle and, therefore, constant. The remaining three variables s_i simply represent the invariant masses of the subsystems that do not include particle i . Besides, these three variables are not independent but rather connected according to

$$s_1 + s_2 + s_3 = M^2 + m_1^2 + m_2^2 + m_3^2 \quad (\text{C.2.3})$$

which is derived from energy-momentum conservation and the definitions of these quantities.

Given the squared matrix element $|\mathcal{M}|^2$ of the three-body decay, the general expression for the decay rate Γ reads [108]

$$d\Gamma = \frac{(2\pi)^4}{2E} |\mathcal{M}|^2 \delta^4(P^\mu - p_1^\mu - p_2^\mu - p_3^\mu) \frac{d^3p_1}{(2\pi)^3 2E_1} \frac{d^3p_2}{(2\pi)^3 2E_2} \frac{d^3p_3}{(2\pi)^3 2E_3}, \quad (\text{C.2.4})$$

where E denotes the total energy of the mother particle. Since the squared matrix element as well as the integration measures in Eq. C.2.4 are Lorentz invariant quantities, the expression for the decay rate can be evaluated in any frame of reference by taking care of the value of E in this frame. To simplify the calculations we perform them in the rest frame of the mother particle. In the case of a scalar mother particle or after spin-averaging the squared matrix element, the decay rate becomes [108]

$$\begin{aligned} d\Gamma &= \frac{1}{(2\pi)^3} \frac{1}{32M^3} \langle |\mathcal{M}|^2 \rangle ds_1 ds_3 \\ &= \frac{1}{(2\pi)^3} \frac{1}{8M} \langle |\mathcal{M}|^2 \rangle dE_1 dE_3. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{C.2.5})$$

Hence, we need to find the boundaries of the kinematic variables s_1 , s_2 and s_3 . To this end, we find in the rest frame of the mother particle

$$s_1 = P^2 + p_1^2 - 2P \cdot p_1 = M^2 + m_1^2 - 2ME_1,$$

where $E_1 = \sqrt{|\vec{p}_1|^2 + m_1^2}$ and \vec{p}_1 denotes the three-momentum of daughter particle 1 in the mother's rest frame. Accordingly $E_1 \geq m_1$, so it follows that

$$\max s_1 = (M - m_1)^2.$$

In order to find the minimum value of s_1 we consider the rest frame of the subsystem of particles 2 and 3 which is determined by $\overset{\circ}{p}_2 = -\overset{\circ}{p}_3$. The circle over the variables indicates that they have to be taken with respect to the rest frame of this subsystem which is suppressed in case of invariant variables. By Eq. C.2.1 this leads to $\overset{\circ}{p}_1 = \overset{\circ}{P}$ and at first, we derive with Eq. C.2.2

$$s_1 = (\overset{\circ}{p}_2 + \overset{\circ}{p}_3)^2 = \left(\overset{\circ}{E}_2 + \overset{\circ}{E}_3 \right)^2 \geq (m_2 + m_3)^2.$$

This reasoning also applies to s_2 and s_3 with the due changes and we conclude

$$\begin{aligned} s_1 &\in [(m_2 + m_3)^2, (M - m_1)^2], \\ s_2 &\in [(m_1 + m_3)^2, (M - m_2)^2], \\ s_3 &\in [(m_1 + m_2)^2, (M - m_3)^2]. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{C.2.6})$$

Nevertheless, according to Eq. C.2.3 not the full parameter space is accessible due to the mutual dependence of these kinematic variables. This plays an important role for the evaluation of Eq. C.2.5 because it has to be integrated over two of these quantities. Therefore, we have to find the boundaries of s_3 for fixed values of $s_1 \in [(m_2 + m_3)^2, (M - m_1)^2]$ where we follow the steps of [98]. To this end, we maintain our view from the rest frame of the subsystem of particle 2 and 3 and find

$$s_1 = (\mathring{E} - \mathring{E}_1)^2 = \left(\sqrt{M^2 + |\mathring{p}_1|^2} - \sqrt{m_1^2 + |\mathring{p}_1|^2} \right)^2. \quad (\text{C.2.7})$$

This equation can be solved for $|\mathring{p}_1|^2$ which yields

$$|\mathring{p}_1|^2 = \frac{1}{4s_1} [s_1 - (M - m_1)^2] [s_1 - (M + m_1)^2] =: \frac{1}{4s_1} \lambda(s_1, M^2, m_1^2), \quad (\text{C.2.8})$$

where we defined the function $\lambda(x, y, z) = x^2 + y^2 + z^2 - 2xy - 2xz - 2yz$. Analogously, we can determine the values of $|\mathring{p}_2|^2$ and $|\mathring{p}_3|^2$ using the characterization $s_1 = (\mathring{p}_2 + \mathring{p}_3)^2$ with the outcome

$$|\mathring{p}_2|^2 = |\mathring{p}_3|^2 = \frac{1}{4s_1} \lambda(s_1, m_2^2, m_3^2). \quad (\text{C.2.9})$$

Now we consider the invariant s_3 and rewrite it in this specific frame of reference as

$$s_3 = (\mathring{p}_1 + \mathring{p}_2)^2 = m_1^2 + m_2^2 + 2(\mathring{E}_1 \mathring{E}_2 - |\mathring{p}_1| |\mathring{p}_2| \cos \varphi), \quad (\text{C.2.10})$$

where φ is the angle between \mathring{p}_1 and \mathring{p}_2 . Thus, by using Eqs. C.2.8 and C.2.9, s_3 only depends on φ if s_1 is fixed. Since we are interested in exactly this case, we find the minimal value s_3^- and the maximal value s_3^+ of s_3 at $\varphi = 0$ or respectively $\varphi = \pi$, namely

$$s_3^\pm = m_1^2 + m_2^2 + 2(\mathring{E}_1 \mathring{E}_2 \pm |\mathring{p}_1| |\mathring{p}_2|). \quad (\text{C.2.11})$$

Finally, we need to write \mathring{E}_1 and \mathring{E}_2 in terms of s_1 according to

$$\mathring{E}_1 = \frac{1}{2\sqrt{s_1}} (s - s_1 - m_1^2) \quad \text{and} \quad \mathring{E}_2 = \frac{1}{2\sqrt{s_1}} (s_1 + m_2^2 - m_3^2)$$

to explicitly determine s_3^\pm in terms of s_1 :

$$s_3^\pm = m_1^2 + m_2^2 + \frac{1}{2s_1} \left[(s - s_1 - m_1^2) (s_1 + m_2^2 - m_3^2) \pm \sqrt{\lambda(s_1, s, m_1^2) \lambda(s_1, m_2^2, m_3^2)} \right]. \quad (\text{C.2.12})$$

C.3 The decay channels $\psi \longrightarrow u\bar{d}l^-$ and $\psi \longrightarrow d\bar{d}\nu$

In the following we give the detailed derivation of the (differential) decay rates associated to the dark matter decay channels $\psi \longrightarrow u\bar{d}l^-$ and $\psi \longrightarrow d\bar{d}\nu$. To this end, we concentrate on the decay $\psi \longrightarrow u\bar{d}l^-$, where all necessary definitions of variables can be read off from Fig. 4.2.2 in Sec. 4.2.2, since $\psi \longrightarrow d\bar{d}\nu$ features the same kinematics as well as the same structure of the squared amplitude.

Applying the Feynman rules of the model yields

$$i\mathcal{M} = \frac{i\lambda_{\psi dR} \lambda'_{d,1} \delta_{\alpha\beta}}{(p-k_1)^2 - m_\Sigma^2} [\bar{v}(p;r) P_L v_\alpha(k_1;t_1)] [\bar{u}_\beta(k_2;t_2) P_L \gamma^0 C u^*(k_3;t_3)], \quad (\text{C.3.1})$$

where r , t_1 , t_2 and t_3 denote the spin states of the respective particles whereas α and β are the color indices of the involved quarks. By squaring the amplitude we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} |\mathcal{M}|^2 &= \frac{|\lambda_{\psi dR}|^2 |\lambda'_{d,1}|^2 \delta_{\alpha'\beta'} \delta_{\alpha\beta}}{(s_1 - m_\Sigma^2)^2} [\bar{v}(p;r) P_L v_\alpha(k_1;t_1)] [\bar{u}_\beta(k_2;t_2) P_L \gamma^0 C u^*(k_3;t_3)] \times \\ &\quad \times [\bar{u}_{\beta'}(k_2;t_2) P_L \gamma^0 C u^*(k_3;t_3)]^\dagger [\bar{v}(p;r) P_L v_{\alpha'}(k_1;t_1)]^\dagger \\ &= \frac{|\lambda_{\psi dR}|^2 |\lambda'_{d,1}|^2 \delta_{\alpha'\beta'} \delta_{\alpha\beta}}{(s_1 - m_\Sigma^2)^2} [\bar{v}(p;r) P_L v_\alpha(k_1;t_1)] [\bar{u}_\beta(k_2;t_2) P_L \gamma^0 C u^*(k_3;t_3)] \times \\ &\quad \times [u^T(k_3;t_3) C^\dagger P_R u_{\beta'}(k_2;t_2)] [\bar{v}_{\alpha'}(k_1;t_1) P_R v(p;r)] \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \frac{|\lambda_{\psi dR}|^2 |\lambda'_{d,1}|^2 \delta_{\alpha'\beta'} \delta_{\alpha\beta}}{(s_1 - m_\Sigma^2)^2} [\bar{v}(p;r) P_L v_\alpha(k_1;t_1)] [\bar{v}_{\alpha'}(k_1;t_1) P_R v(p;r)] \times \\
 &\quad \times \left[\bar{u}_\beta(k_2;t_2) P_L C(\gamma^0)^T u^*(k_3;t_3) \right] \left[u^T(k_3;t_3) C P_R u_{\beta'}(k_2;t_2) \right] \\
 &= \frac{|\lambda_{\psi dR}|^2 |\lambda'_{d,1}|^2 \delta_{\alpha'\beta'} \delta_{\alpha\beta}}{(s_1 - m_\Sigma^2)^2} [\bar{v}(p;r) P_L v_\alpha(k_1;t_1)] [\bar{v}_{\alpha'}(k_1;t_1) P_R v(p;r)] \times \\
 &\quad \times \left[\bar{u}_\beta(k_2;t_2) P_L C(u(k_3;t_3) \bar{u}(k_3;t_3))^T C P_R u_{\beta'}(k_2;t_2) \right] \\
 &= \frac{|\lambda_{\psi dR}|^2 |\lambda'_{d,1}|^2 \delta_{\alpha'\beta'} \delta_{\alpha\beta}}{(s_1 - m_\Sigma^2)^2} \text{tr} [v(p;r) \bar{v}(p;r) P_L v_\alpha(k_1;t_1) \bar{v}_{\alpha'}(k_1;t_1) P_R] \times \\
 &\quad \times \text{tr} [u_{\beta'}(k_2;t_2) \bar{u}_\beta(k_2;t_2) P_L C(u(k_3;t_3) \bar{u}(k_3;t_3))^T C P_R]
 \end{aligned} \tag{C.3.2}$$

which is then evaluated using spin-averaging and summation over the colors, eventually leading to

$$\begin{aligned}
 \langle |\mathcal{M}|^2 \rangle &= \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\text{color}} \sum_{r,t_1,t_2,t_3} |\mathcal{M}|^2 \\
 &= \frac{3 |\lambda_{\psi dR}|^2 |\lambda'_{d,1}|^2}{2 (s_1 - m_\Sigma^2)^2} \text{tr} [(\not{p} + m_\psi) P_L (\not{k}_1 + m_d) P_R] \times \\
 &\quad \times \text{tr} [(\not{k}_2 - m_e) P_L C(\not{k}_3 - m_u)^T C P_R] \\
 &= \frac{3 |\lambda_{\psi dR}|^2 |\lambda'_{d,1}|^2}{2 (s_1 - m_\Sigma^2)^2} \text{tr} [(\not{p} + m_\psi) P_L (\not{k}_1 + m_d) P_R] \times \\
 &\quad \times \text{tr} [(\not{k}_2 - m_e) P_L (\not{k}_3 + m_u) P_R] \\
 &= \frac{3 |\lambda_{\psi dR}|^2 |\lambda'_{d,1}|^2}{2 (s_1 - m_\Sigma^2)^2} \text{tr} [\not{p} \not{k}_1 P_R] \text{tr} [\not{k}_2 \not{k}_3 P_R] \\
 &= \frac{6 |\lambda_{\psi dR}|^2 |\lambda'_{d,1}|^2}{(s_1 - m_\Sigma^2)^2} (p \cdot k_1) (k_2 \cdot k_3).
 \end{aligned} \tag{C.3.3}$$

Now, we proceed analogously to the calculations in Sec.4.2.1, i.e. we make the assumption of massless final state particles and apply $s_1 \ll m_\Sigma^2$ in the denominator

C.3 The decay channels $\psi \longrightarrow u\bar{d}l^-$ and $\psi \longrightarrow d\bar{d}\nu$

of the squared amplitude. Furthermore, we rewrite the products of momenta as

$$\begin{aligned} p \cdot k_1 &= \frac{1}{2} (m_\psi^2 - s_1), \\ k_2 \cdot k_3 &= \frac{1}{2} s_1 \end{aligned}$$

and recall that

$$\begin{aligned} s_1 &\in [0, m_\psi^2], \\ s_3 &\in [0, m_\psi^2 - s_1]. \end{aligned}$$

Consequently, the decay rate of this particular decay reads

$$\begin{aligned} \Gamma(\psi \longrightarrow u\bar{d}l^-) &= \frac{3 |\lambda_{\psi dR}|^2 |\lambda'_{d,1}|^2}{64 m_\psi^3 (2\pi)^3 m_\Sigma^4} \int_0^{m_\psi^2} \int_0^{m_\psi^2 - s_1} [s_1 (m_\psi^2 - s_1)] ds_3 ds_1 \\ &= \frac{|\lambda_{\psi dR}|^2 |\lambda'_{d,1}|^2 m_\psi^5}{256 (2\pi)^3 m_\Sigma^4}. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{C.3.4})$$

To find the differential decay rates with respect to all three daughter particles, we start from Eq. C.2.4 in the rest frame of the dark matter particle and rewrite the squared amplitude according to

$$p^\mu = \begin{pmatrix} m_\psi \\ \vec{0} \end{pmatrix}, \quad k_1^\mu = \begin{pmatrix} \omega_1 := |\vec{k}_1| \\ \vec{k}_1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad k_2^\mu = \begin{pmatrix} \omega_2 := |\vec{k}_2| \\ \vec{k}_2 \end{pmatrix}, \quad k_3^\mu = \begin{pmatrix} \omega_3 := |\vec{k}_3| \\ \vec{k}_3 \end{pmatrix}$$

which yields

$$\langle |\mathcal{M}|^2 \rangle = \frac{3 |\lambda_{\psi dR}|^2 |\lambda'_{d,1}|^2}{m_\Sigma^4} \omega_1 m_\psi^2 (m_\psi - 2\omega_1).$$

We do not have to make any further reasonings since the following calculation is exactly the same as the one in Sec. 4.2.1. We only need to pay attention to the order of integration where in the case of $d\Gamma/d\omega_1$ we may begin with either d^3k_2 or d^3k_3 whereas in the case of $d\Gamma/d\omega_2$ we start with d^3k_3 followed by d^3k_1 and, finally, in the case of $d\Gamma/d\omega_3$ the order is d^3k_2 then d^3k_1 . Thus, we obtain

$$\frac{d\Gamma(\psi \longrightarrow u\bar{d}l^-)}{d\omega_1} = \frac{3 |\lambda_{\psi dR}|^2 |\lambda'_{d,1}|^2}{(4\pi)^3 m_\psi m_\Sigma^4} \omega_1 m_\psi^2 (m_\psi - 2\omega_1) \int_{\frac{m_\psi}{2} - \omega_1}^{\frac{m_\psi}{2}} d\omega_2$$

$$= \frac{3 |\lambda_{\psi dR}|^2 |\lambda'_{d,1}|^2}{8 (2\pi)^3 m_\Sigma^4} m_\psi \omega_1^2 (m_\psi - 2\omega_1) \quad (\text{C.3.5})$$

and, since $d\Gamma/d\omega_2$ as well as $d\Gamma/d\omega_3$ coincide,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d\Gamma(\psi \rightarrow u\bar{d}l^-)}{d\omega_2} &= \frac{3 |\lambda_{\psi dR}|^2 |\lambda'_{d,1}|^2}{(4\pi)^3 m_\psi m_\Sigma^4} \int_{\frac{m_\psi}{2} - \omega_2}^{\frac{m_\psi}{2}} [\omega_1 m_\psi^2 (m_\psi - 2\omega_1)] d\omega_1 \\ &= \frac{3 |\lambda_{\psi dR}|^2 |\lambda'_{d,1}|^2}{16 (2\pi)^3 m_\Sigma^4} m_\psi \omega_2^2 \left(m_\psi - \frac{4}{3} \omega_2 \right). \end{aligned} \quad (\text{C.3.6})$$

D Documentation of used Scripts

D.1 Calculation of J - factors with MATLAB

```
1 function [omega, J] = two_dim_J_integration(DM_profile, l_min, l_max, b_min, b_max,n,m)
2
3 %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
4 %Provided interpolation data from http://www.marcocirelli.net/PPPC4DMID.html
5
6 JDec_theta = [-12.75812263240917,-12.658122632409171,-12.558122632409171, ...];
7
8 JDec_Bur = [0.6507053039106887,0.6507053039106878,0.6507053039106885, ...];
9
10 JDec_EiB = [1.8560975388960017,1.856097538897213,1.8560975388991328, ...];
11
12 JDec_Ein = [1.427982636836902,1.427982636836929,1.4279826368369706, ...];
13
14 JDec_Iso = [0.809885504743549,0.8098855047435484,0.8098855047435487, ...];
15
16 JDec_Moo = [2.8667309772450738,2.8667309976725637,2.8667310300479896, ...];
17
18 JDec_NFW = [1.9102128393488795,1.910212845286391,1.9102128546967232, ...];
19
20 %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
21 %Define integration grid
22
23 x = linspace(l_min,l_max,n);
24 y = linspace(b_min,b_max,m);
25 z_omega = zeros(n,m); %
26 z_J = zeros(n,m);
27
28 for i = 1:n
29     for j = 1:m
30         z_omega(i,j)=cos(y(j)*pi/180.0);
31     end
32 end
33 omega = 4.0*trapz(y*pi/180.0,trapz(x*pi/180.0,z_omega));
34
35 %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
36 %Perform integration with spline interpolated functions
37
38 for i = 1:n
39     for j = 1:m
40         if DM_profile == 'NFW'
41             z_J(i,j) = interp1(power(10,JDec_theta)*180/pi, power(10,JDec_NFW), acos(cos(x(i)
42                 )*pi/180.0)*cos(y(j)*pi/180.0))*180.0/pi, 'spline')*cos(y(j)*pi/180.0);
43         end
44         if DM_profile == 'Iso'
45             z_J(i,j) = interp1(power(10,JDec_theta)*180/pi, power(10,JDec_Iso), acos(cos(x(i)
46                 )*pi/180.0)*cos(y(j)*pi/180.0))*180.0/pi, 'spline')*cos(y(j)*pi/180.0);
47         end
48         if DM_profile == 'Bur'
49             z_J(i,j) = interp1(power(10,JDec_theta)*180/pi, power(10,JDec_Bur), acos(cos(x(i)
50                 )*pi/180.0)*cos(y(j)*pi/180.0))*180.0/pi, 'spline')*cos(y(j)*pi/180.0);
51         end
52         if DM_profile == 'Ein'
```

```

50         z_J(i,j) = interp1(power(10,JDec_theta)*180/pi, power(10,JDec_Ein), acos(cos(x(i)
51             )*pi/180.0)*cos(y(j)*pi/180.0))*180.0/pi, 'spline')*cos(y(j)*pi/180.0);
52     end
53     if DM_profile == 'EiB'
54         z_J(i,j) = interp1(power(10,JDec_theta)*180/pi, power(10,JDec_EiB), acos(cos(x(i)
55             )*pi/180.0)*cos(y(j)*pi/180.0))*180.0/pi, 'spline')*cos(y(j)*pi/180.0);
56     end
57     if DM_profile == 'Moo'
58         z_J(i,j) = interp1(power(10,JDec_theta)*180/pi, power(10,JDec_Moo), acos(cos(x(i)
59             )*pi/180.0)*cos(y(j)*pi/180.0))*180.0/pi, 'spline')*cos(y(j)*pi/180.0);
60     end
61 end
62 end
63 J = 4.0*trapz(y*pi/180.0,trapz(x*pi/180.0,z_J))/omega;

```

Listing D.1: MATLAB function to average over the dark matter density profile in a certain region of the observable galaxy.

D.2 Mathematica[®] scripts to implement the Lagrangian

```

1  M$ModelName = "MinimalDecayingDarkMatter_Model";
2  M$Information = {
3  Authors -> {"Me"},
4  Institutions -> {"Institut fuer theoretische Physik , Goettingen"},
5  Emails -> {"c.e@s.u-g.de"},
6  Date -> "August 18, 2015",
7  References -> {"Some papers"}
8  };
9
10 M$Parameters = {
11
12     lamPsi == {
13         ParameterType -> External,
14         ComplexParameter -> False,
15         Value -> 1.8e-11,
16         InteractionOrder -> {DDM,1},
17         Description -> "coupling strength to Dark matter particle Psi"
18     },
19
20     lamSig == {
21         ParameterType -> External,
22         ComplexParameter -> False,
23         Value -> 5.5e-10,
24         InteractionOrder -> {DDM,1},
25         Description -> "coupling strength to heavy scalar Sigma"
26     },
27
28     MSig == {
29         ParameterType -> External,
30         ComplexParameter -> False,
31         Value -> 800.0,
32         Description -> "mass of heavy scalar Sigma in GeV"
33     },
34
35     MPsi == {
36         ParameterType -> External,
37         ComplexParameter -> False,
38         Value -> 10.0,
39         Description -> "mass of Dark matter particle Psi"
40     }
41 };
42
43 M$ClassesDescription = {

```

```

44
45     S[4] == {
46         ClassName -> sig ,
47         SelfConjugate -> False ,
48         Indices -> {Index[ Colour ]},
49         QuantumNumbers -> {Q -> -1/3},
50         Mass -> MSig,
51         Width -> {WSig, 9.634029e-18},
52         ParticleName -> "sig"
53     },
54
55     F[5] == {
56         ClassName -> psi ,
57         SelfConjugate -> True,
58         Mass -> MPsi,
59         Width -> {WPsi, 7.537500e-52},
60         ParticleName -> "psi"
61     }
62 };

```

Listing D.2: File used to implement the dark matter particle and the scalar field together with the four parameters of the minimal decaying dark matter model in FeynRules2.0.

D.3 Pythia8 scripts

```

1  #include "Pythia8/Pythia.h"
2  #include <list>
3  #include <algorithm>
4  #include <fstream>
5  #include <iostream>
6  #include <cmath>
7  #define m_p 0.9382720813
8  #define m_n 0.9395654133
9
10 using namespace Pythia8;
11
12 //#####
13 // Definition of the function that filters out all stable final states of a dark matter decay.
14
15 void find_end_particles(Pythia* pythia , vector<int>* result , int start_id)
16 {
17     vector<int> daughters = pythia->event[start_id].daughterList();
18     //If the particle has no daughters, store it as stable final state.
19     if(daughters.size() == 0) result->push_back(start_id);
20     else
21     {
22         //If there are daughters, apply this function to its daughters.
23         for(unsigned i = 0; i < daughters.size(); i++)
24         {
25             find_end_particles(pythia , result , daughters[i]);
26         }
27     }
28 }
29
30 int main(int argc , char* argv[])
31 {
32     ofstream antiprot_energy("pbar_energy.dat");
33     ofstream prot_energy("p_energy.dat");
34     ofstream gamma_energy("gamma_energy.dat");
35     ofstream neut_energy("n_energy.dat");
36     ofstream antineut_energy("nbar_energy.dat");
37
38     //#####
39     // Pythia generator.
40
41     Pythia pythia;

```

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```
42
43 //#####
44 // Initialize Les Houches Event File run. List initialization information.
45
46 pythia.readFile(argv[1]);
47
48 pythia.init();
49
50 //#####
51 // Begin event loop; generate until nothing left in input file.
52
53 for (int iEvent = 0; ; ++iEvent)
54 {
55     //#####
56     // Initialize counters for each particle species.
57
58     int nAntiProt= 0;
59     int nProt= 0;
60     int nGamma = 0;
61     int nAntiNeut = 0;
62     int nNeut = 0;
63
64     //#####
65     // Generate events, and check whether generation failed.
66
67     if (!pythia.next())
68     {
69         //#####
70         // Abort processing of the end of the LHE file is reached.
71         if (pythia.info.atEndOfFile()) break;
72     }
73
74     //#####
75     //Search for last copies of DM particles psi in the Event Record. As there are
76     //two particles per event, initialize two distinct pointers.
77
78     vector<int> Psis;
79     int iPsi_matter = 0;
80     int iPsi_antimatter = 0;
81
82     //#####
83     //Enter Particle Loop and find all appearing dark matter particles.
84
85     for (int i = 0; i < pythia.event.size(); ++i)
86     {
87         if (pythia.event[i].id() == 9000006) Psis.push_back(i);
88     }
89
90     //#####
91     //Keep only those copies that, indeed, decayed and assign the two tags.
92
93     std::reverse(Psis.begin(), Psis.end());
94
95     while(abs(Psis.size()) > 2)
96     {
97         Psis.pop_back();
98     }
99
100     int i_daughter_psi_1 = pythia.event[ Psis[0] ].daughter1();
101
102     if(pythia.event[i_daughter_psi_1].id() > 0)
103     {
104         iPsi_matter = Psis[0];
105         iPsi_antimatter = Psis[1];
106     }
107     else
108     {
109         iPsi_matter = Psis[1];
110         iPsi_antimatter = Psis[0];
111     }
112
113     //#####
```

```

114 //Identify all created daughter particles after the hadronization of a psi
115 //decay took place.
116
117 vector<int> end_particlesmatter;
118 vector<int> end_particlesantimatter;
119
120 find_end_particles(&pythia, &end_particlesmatter, iPsi_matter);
121 find_end_particles(&pythia, &end_particlesantimatter, iPsi_antimatter);
122
123 //Store four-vector of dark matter particle in lab frame.
124 Vec4 matterfour = pythia.event[iPsi_matter].p();
125 Vec4 antimatterfour = pythia.event[iPsi_antimatter].p();
126
127 //Compute gamma factor of each boosted dark matter particle.
128 double gammamatter = 1.0/sqrt(1-(matterfour.px()*matterfour.px()+matterfour.py()
    *matterfour.py()+matterfour.pz()*matterfour.pz())/(matterfour.e()*matterfour
    .e()));
129 double gammaantimatter = 1.0/sqrt(1-(antimatterfour.px()*antimatterfour.px()+
    antimatterfour.py()*antimatterfour.py()+antimatterfour.pz()*antimatterfour.
    pz())/(antimatterfour.e()*antimatterfour.e()));
130
131 for (int i = 0; i < pythia.event.size(); ++i)
132 {
133     //#####
134     //Find all protons in the final states of a dark matter particle,
135     //boost it into the its rest frame and store the energy.
136
137     if (pythia.event[i].id() == 2212 && (std::find(end_particlesmatter.begin
        (),end_particlesmatter.end(), i) != end_particlesmatter.end()))
138     {
139         nProt +=1;
140         Vec4 prot = pythia.event[i].p();
141         prot.bst(-matterfour.px()/matterfour.e(), -matterfour.py()/
            matterfour.e(), -matterfour.pz()/matterfour.e(), gammamatter
            );
142         prot_energy << prot.e() << endl;
143     }
144     if (pythia.event[i].id() == 2212 && (std::find(end_particlesantimatter.
        begin(),end_particlesantimatter.end(), i) != end_particlesantimatter
        .end()))
145     {
146         nProt +=1;
147         Vec4 prot = pythia.event[i].p();
148         prot.bst(-antimatterfour.px()/antimatterfour.e(), -
            antimatterfour.py()/antimatterfour.e(), -antimatterfour.pz()
            /antimatterfour.e(), gammaantimatter);
149         prot_energy << prot.e() << endl;
150     }
151     //#####
152     //Find all antiprotons in the final states of a dark matter particle,
153     //boost it into the its rest frame and store the energy.
154
155     if (pythia.event[i].id() == -2212 && (std::find(end_particlesmatter.
        begin(),end_particlesmatter.end(), i) != end_particlesmatter.end()))
156     {
157         nantiProt +=1;
158         Vec4 antiprot = pythia.event[i].p();
159         antiprot.bst(-matterfour.px()/matterfour.e(), -matterfour.py()/
            matterfour.e(), -matterfour.pz()/matterfour.e(), gammamatter
            );
160         antiprot_energy << antiprot.e() << endl;
161     }
162     if (pythia.event[i].id() == -2212 && (std::find(end_particlesantimatter.
        begin(),end_particlesantimatter.end(), i) != end_particlesantimatter
        .end()))
163     {
164         nantiProt +=1;
165         Vec4 antiprot = pythia.event[i].p();
166         antiprot.bst(-antimatterfour.px()/matterfour.e(), -
            antimatterfour.py()/matterfour.e(), -antimatterfour.pz()/
            matterfour.e(), gammaantimatter);
167

```

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```

168         antiprot_energy << antiprot.e() << endl;
169     }
170
171     #####
172     //Find all photons in the final states of a dark matter particle ,
173     //boost it into the its rest frame and store the energy.
174
175     if (pythia.event[i].id() == 22 && (std::find(end_particlesmatter.begin()
176         ,end_particlesmatter.end(), i) != end_particlesmatter.end()))
177     {
178         nGamma +=1;
179         Vec4 photons = pythia.event[i].p();
180         photons.bst(-matterfour.px()/matterfour.e(), -matterfour.py()/
181             matterfour.e(), -matterfour.pz()/matterfour.e(), gammamatter
182             );
183         if (photons.e() >= 0.05) {gamma_energy << photons.e() << endl;}
184     }
185
186     if (pythia.event[i].id() == 22 && (std::find(end_particlesantimatter.
187         begin(),end_particlesantimatter.end(), i) != end_particlesantimatter
188         .end()))
189     {
190         nGamma +=1;
191         Vec4 photons = pythia.event[i].p();
192         photons.bst(-antimatterfour.px()/antimatterfour.e(), -
193             antimatterfour.py()/antimatterfour.e(), -antimatterfour.pz()
194             /antimatterfour.e(), gammaantimatter);
195         if (photons.e() >= 0.05) {gamma_energy << photons.e() << endl;}
196     }
197
198     #####
199     //Find all neutrons in the final states of a dark matter particle ,
200     //boost it into the its rest frame and store the energy.
201
202     if (pythia.event[i].id() == 2112 && (std::find(end_particlesmatter.begin()
203         (),end_particlesmatter.end(), i) != end_particlesmatter.end()))
204     {
205         nNeut += 1;
206         Vec4 neut = pythia.event[i].p();
207         neut.bst(-matterfour.px()/matterfour.e(), -matterfour.py()/
208             matterfour.e(), -matterfour.pz()/matterfour.e(), gammamatter
209             );
210         neut_energy << neut.e() << endl;
211     }
212
213     if (pythia.event[i].id() == 2112 && (std::find(end_particlesantimatter.
214         begin(),end_particlesantimatter.end(), i) != end_particlesantimatter
215         .end()))
216     {
217         nNeut += 1;
218         Vec4 neut = pythia.event[i].p();
219         neut.bst(-antimatterfour.px()/antimatterfour.e(), -
220             antimatterfour.py()/antimatterfour.e(), -antimatterfour.pz()
221             /antimatterfour.e(), gammaantimatter);
222         neut_energy << neut.e() << endl;
223     }
224
225     #####
226     //Find all antineutrons in the final states of a dark matter particle ,
227     //boost it into the its rest frame and store the energy.
228
229     if (pythia.event[i].id() == -2112 && (std::find(end_particlesmatter.
230         begin(),end_particlesmatter.end(), i) != end_particlesmatter.end()))
231     {
232         nantiNeut += 1;
233         Vec4 antineut = pythia.event[i].p();
234         antineut.bst(-matterfour.px()/matterfour.e(), -matterfour.py()/
235             matterfour.e(), -matterfour.pz()/matterfour.e(), gammamatter
236             );
237         antineut_energy << antineut.e() << endl;
238     }
239
240     }

```

D.4 Generation and normalization of energy spectra with PYTHON

```
221         if (pythia.event[i].id() == -2112 && (std::find(end_particlesantimatter.  
                begin(), end_particlesantimatter.end(), i) != end_particlesantimatter.  
                .end()))  
222         {  
223             nantiNeut += 1;  
224             Vec4 antineut = pythia.event[i].p();  
225             antineut.bst(-antimatterfour.px()/antimatterfour.e(), -  
                antimatterfour.py()/antimatterfour.e(), -antimatterfour.pz()  
                /antimatterfour.e(), gammaantimatter);  
226             antineut_energy << antineut.e() << endl;  
227         }  
228     }  
229  
230     //#####  
231     // Give statistics of processing the LHE files.  
232  
233     cout << "Number of neutrons in final states:" << nNeut << endl;  
234     cout << "Number of anti neutrons in final states:" << nantiNeut << endl;  
235     cout << "Number of up-quarks in histogramme:" << nUp << endl;  
236     cout << "Number of anti up-quarks in histogramme:" << nantiUp << endl;  
237  
238     pythia.stat();  
239  
240     antiprot_energy.close();  
241     prot_energy.close();  
242     gamma_energy.close();  
243     neut_energy.close();  
244     antineut_energy.close();  
245  
246     return 0;  
247  
248 }
```

Listing D.3: Script used to process the LHE files generated with MadGraph5 and to find the energies of the considered particle species in the rest frame of the decayed dark matter particle.

```
1 Beams:frameType = 4  
2 Beams:LHEF = /usr/scratch1/c.eckner/MG5_aMC_v2_3_2/pp2psipi_up_fifty/Events/mpsi_15GeV_50000_5/  
    events.lhe  
3 ResonanceWidths:minWidth = 1e-30  
4 2112:mayDecay = true !allow neutron decay  
5 2112:mWidth = 1e-20  
6 2112:tau0 = 1.0e-12  
7 321:mayDecay = true !allow charged Kaon decay  
8 130:mayDecay = true !allow K long decay  
9 211: mayDecay = true !allow charged pion decay  
10 13: mayDecay = true !allow muon decay  
11 PartonLevel:ISR = off ! initial state radiation  
12 PartonLevel:MPI = off ! multi-parton interactions  
13 PartonLevel:FSR = on ! final state radiation  
14 HadronLevel:all = on ! switches of hadronization and decays  
15 Tune:pp = 5
```

Listing D.4: Parameter card specifying the settings of the Pythia run. In particular, we enable a number of decays and turn off initial state radiation as well as multi-parton interactions.

D.4 Generation and normalization of energy spectra with Python

D Documentation of used Scripts

```
1 import numpy as np
2 import sys
3
4 m_p = 0.9382720813
5 m_n = 0.9395654133
6
7 #####
8 ##Read in necessary parameters of binning
9
10 channel = str(input("Specify the input ID channel (p/n/gamma): "))
11 mass = float(input("Insert mass of DM particle: "))
12 refined_bin_width = int(input("Insert number of bins: "))
13 starting_point = float(input("Insert starting point of spectrum: "))
14 normed = int(input("Normalize spectrum (0=no/1=yes)? "))
15
16 #####
17 ##Generate equidistant points on a logarithmic scale from starting_point to
18 ##half of the dark matter mass
19
20 bin_edges = list(np.exp(np.linspace(np.log(starting_point), np.log(mass*0.5), refined_bin_width)
21 ))
22 #####
23 ##Read in data into a list depending on the particle species and count the
24 ##total number of particles in the declared energy range
25
26 data = []
27 n_gamma = 0
28 n_prot = 0
29 n_neut = 0
30
31 for m in range(1, len(sys.argv)-1):
32     print(str(sys.argv[m]))
33     with open(sys.argv[m], "r") as f:
34         for line in f:
35             line = line.rstrip()
36             if channel == "p":
37                 n_prot += 1
38                 data.append(float(line)-m_p)
39             if channel == "n":
40                 n_neut += 1
41                 data.append(float(line)-m_n)
42             if channel == "gamma":
43                 if float(line) > starting_point:
44                     n_gamma += 1
45                     data.append(float(line))
46
47 print(n_gamma)
48 print(n_prot)
49 print(n_neut)
50
51 #####
52 ##Generate and write histograms with numpy's algorithms
53
54 if normed == 1:
55     (n,bins) = np.histogram(data, bins = bin_edges, density = True)
56 else:
57     (n,bins) = np.histogram(data, bins = bin_edges)
58
59 with open(sys.argv[-1], "w") as v:
60     for k in range(len(n)):
61         v.write(str(bins[k])+" "+str(n[k])+"\n")
```

Listing D.5: Python script used to bin the extracted particle energies in bins distributed equidistantly on a logarithmic scale. The number of bins and the starting point of the spectrum are free to choose.

```
1 import sys
2 import math as m
```

```

3
4 #####
5 ##Read in dark matter mass.
6
7 mass = float(sys.argv[1])
8 mass2 = mass/2.0
9
10 #####
11 ##If the spectrum should be derived with a scaled kinetic energy then the
12 ##scaling_factor has to be specified, otherwise it is simply one.
13
14 scale_factor = float(sys.argv[2])
15
16 #####
17 ##Normalization of spectra for scaled and non-scaled kinetic energies.
18
19 lastbx = -1
20 lastnx = -1
21 ntot = 0
22
23 with open(sys.argv[3], "r") as f:
24     for line in f:
25         nx = float(line.split()[1])
26         ntot += nx
27
28 with open(sys.argv[3], "r") as f:
29     for line in f:
30         (bx, nx) = line.split()
31         bx = float(bx)/scale_factor
32         nx = float(nx)/ntot
33
34         if lastnx != -1:
35             bw = bx - lastbx
36
37             newnx = lastnx / bw
38
39             print(str(lastbx)+" "+str(newnx))
40
41         lastnx = nx
42         lastbx = bx
43 bw = mass2/scale_factor - lastbx
44 newnx = lastnx / bw
45 print(str(lastbx)+" "+str(newnx))

```

Listing D.6: Python script to normalize the derived binned spectra to arbitrarily scaled kinetic energies on the x-axis.

D.5 Derivation of lifetime limits

```

1 import math as m
2 import sys
3 from scipy import interpolate
4 import numpy as np
5 import scipy.integrate as integrate
6
7 #####
8 ##Fix the operator to be investigated, define constants, provide the fit functions of Cirelli et
9 ##al. for DM antiproton flux and astrophysical background.
10
11 halo = str(input("Specify DM density profile (NFW/Moo/Iso/Ein/EiB/Bur): "))
12 operator = input("Specify operator to test (udd/css/tbb/ude/udtau/tbtau): ")
13
14 m_p = 0.938272046
15 r_dot = 8.33
16 Myr = 3.15576e13
17 c_0 = 299792458

```

D Documentation of used Scripts

```
18 e = 1.6021766208e-19
19 hbar = 6.626070040e-34/(2.0*m.pi)
20
21 #####
22 ##Function for the velocity of the antiprotons.
23
24 def v_p(T):
25     return m.pow((1.0-m_p**2/(T+m_p)**2),0.5)*c_0
26
27 #####
28 ##Fit function of the semi-analytic solution of the two-zone diffusion model as given by Cirelli
29 ##et al.
30
31 def R_K(K):
32     if (halo == "NFW"):
33         if (dataset == "MIN"):
34             a_0 = 0.9175
35             a_1 = 0.6429
36             a_2 = -0.3121
37             a_3 = -0.0910
38             a_4 = 0.0406
39             a_5 = -0.0039
40         if (dataset == "MED"):
41             a_0 = 1.7507
42             a_1 = 0.3892
43             a_2 = -0.3101
44             a_3 = -0.0070
45             a_4 = 0.0151
46             a_5 = -0.0016
47         if (dataset == "MAX"):
48             a_0 = 2.4353
49             a_1 = -0.1549
50             a_2 = -0.1004
51             a_3 = 0.0144
52             a_4 = -0.0007
53             a_5 = -0.0000
54 #####
55 ##The values of all other density profile are likewise implemented in this function. In order to
56 ##reduce the length of this script, we only provide one example.
57     return m.pow(10.0,a_0+a_1*m.log10(K)+a_2*m.log10(K)**2+a_3*m.log10(K)**3+a_4*m.log10(K)
58                 **4+a_5*m.log10(K)**5)*Myr
59
60 def intermed_flux(T, spectrum, tau_DM):
61     return (v_p(T)/(4.0*m.pi))*((rho_dot*1e06/M_DM)*R_K(T)*(1.0/tau_DM)*spectrum*avrgd_p)
62
63 def background_flux(T):
64     if (dataset == "MED"):
65         a_0=-1.5079
66         a_1=0.34279
67         a_2=-0.71347
68         a_3=-0.89053
69         a_4=0.18914
70         a_5=0.32518
71         a_6=-0.19223
72         a_7=0.04022
73         a_8=-0.00299
74     if (dataset == "MAX"):
75         a_0=-1.6192
76         a_1=0.34986
77         a_2=-0.69943
78         a_3=- 0.86758
79         a_4=0.19016
80         a_5=0.30858
81         a_6=-0.18192
82         a_7=0.03777
83         a_8=-0.00279
84     if (dataset == "MIN"):
85         a_0=-1.5116
86         a_1=0.37991
87         a_2=-0.69686
88         a_3=-0.92051
89         a_4=0.17873
```

```

89         a_5=0.34161
90         a_6=-0.19910
91         a_7=0.04154
92         a_8=-0.00309
93     X = m.log10(T)
94     return m.pow(10.0, (a_0+a_1*X+a_2*X*X+a_3*X*X*X+a_4*X*X*X*X+a_5*X*X*X*X*X+a_6*X*X*X*X*X*X
95         +a_7*X*X*X*X*X*X*X+a_8*X*X*X*X*X*X*X*X))
96
97 def solar_modulation_bkgrd(T):
98     if (dataset == "MED"):
99         phi_F=0.7
100        A=1.24
101     if (dataset == "MAX"):
102        phi_F=0.38
103        A=1.25
104     if (dataset == "MIN"):
105        phi_F=0.74
106        A=1.22
107     return A*background_flux(T+phi_F)*T*(T+2.0*m_p)/((T+m_p+phi_F)**2-m_p**2)
108
109 def solar_modulation(flux, T):
110     return flux*T*(T+2.0*m_p)/((T+m_p+fisk_pot)**2-m_p**2)
111
112 #####
113 ##List of raw DM lifetimes to be scanned over.
114
115 lifetimes = [1.0e25, 2.0e25, 3.0e25, 4.0e25, 5.0e25, 6.0e25, 7.0e25, 8.0e25, 9.0e25, 1.0e26, 2.0e26, 3.0e26,
116             4.0e26, 5.0e26, 6.0e26, 7.0e26, 8.0e26, 9.0e26, 1.0e27, 2.0e27, 3.0e27, 4.0e27, 5.0e27, 6.0e27, 7.0e27,
117             8.0e27, 9.0e27, 1.0e28, 2.0e28, 3.0e28, 4.0e28, 5.0e28, 6.0e28, 7.0e28, 8.0e28, 9.0e28, 1.0e29, 2.0e29,
118             3.0e29, 4.0e29, 5.0e29, 6.0e29, 7.0e29, 8.0e29, 9.0e29, 1.0e30, 2.0e30, 3.0e30, 4.0e30, 5.0e30, 6.0e30,
119             7.0e30, 8.0e30, 9.0e30, 1.0e31, 2.0e31, 3.0e31, 4.0e31, 5.0e31, 6.0e31, 7.0e31, 8.0e31, 9.0e31, 1.0e32,
120             2.0e32, 3.0e32, 4.0e32, 5.0e32, 6.0e32, 7.0e32, 8.0e32, 9.0e32]
121 lifetimes.reverse()
122
123 #####
124 ##Hard-coded data of PAMELA and the antiproton multiplicities of DM decays for all operators and
125 ##masses.
126
127 PAMELA_kin_energy = [0.09, 0.28, 0.56, 0.81, 1.07, 1.34, 1.63, 2.03, 2.42, 2.90, 3.47, 4.14,
128 4.93, 5.90, 7.0, 8.4, 10.1, 12.3, 15.3, 19.60, 26.20, 38.00, 67.4, 128.9, 240.0]
129 PAMELA_low_bin_edge = list(map(lambda x: m.sqrt(x*x+m_p*m_p)-m_p, [0.35, 0.5, 1.01, 1.34, 1.63,
130 1.93, 2.23, 2.58, 2.99, 3.45, 3.99, 4.62, 5.36, 6.23, 7.3, 8.5, 10.1, 12.0, 14.6, 18.1, 23.3, 31.7, 48.5, 100.0,
131 180.0]))
132 PAMELA_high_bin_edge = list(map(lambda x: m.sqrt(x*x+m_p*m_p)-m_p, [0.5, 1.01, 1.34, 1.63,
133 1.93, 2.23, 2.58, 2.99, 3.45, 3.99, 4.62, 5.36, 6.23, 7.3, 8.5, 10.1, 12.0, 14.6, 18.1, 23.3, 31.7, 48.5, 100.0,
134 180.0, 350.0]))
135 PAMELA_all_bin_edge = list(map(lambda x: m.sqrt(x*x+m_p*m_p)-m_p, [0.35, 0.5, 1.01, 1.34, 1.63,
136 1.93, 2.23, 2.58, 2.99, 3.45, 3.99, 4.62, 5.36, 6.23, 7.3, 8.5, 10.1, 12.0, 14.6, 18.1, 23.3, 31.7, 48.5, 100.0,
137 180.0, 350.0]))
138 PAMELA_flux = [3.5e-03, 7.67e-03, 10.43e-03, 16.79e-03, 20.23e-03, 22.78e-03, 21.65e-03, 25.75e
139 -03, 21.44e-03, 20.05e-03, 16.46e-03, 15.26e-03, 11.79e-03, 9.47e-03, 6.92e-03, 5.18e-03, 3.76e
140 -03, 2.25e-03, 1.36e-03, 0.727e-03, 0.338e-03, 0.122e-03, 0.025e-03, 0.0045e-03, 0.0008e-03]
141 PAMELA_flux_errors = [0.0, 2.75e-03, 3.86e-03, 3.92e-03, 4.00e-03, 4.06e-03, 2.56e-03, 2.33e-03, 1.83e
142 -03, 1.76e-03, 1.34e-03, 1.13e-03, 0.77e-03, 0.59e-03, 0.45e-03, 0.40e-03, 0.26e-03, 0.18e-03, 0.13e
143 -03, 0.070e-03, 0.029e-03, 0.016e-03, 0.005e-03, 0.0037e-03, 0.0]
144
145 averaged_prots_udd = [(10.0, 0.62613262201475430334), (15.0, 0.74064227798147330014)
146 , (20.0, 0.84236337186279454613), (25.0, 0.93974174916253562037), (30.0, 1.01369129251303684498)
147 , (35.0, 1.08762633000900570361), (40.0, 1.15286213954884459693), (45.0, 1.21436222310209014942)
148 , (50.0, 1.27514859050459527193), (55.0, 1.32446704274915464829), (60.0, 1.3758561322622734871)
149 , (65.0, 1.42343669886157578587), (70.0, 1.46957090812081599987), (75.0, 1.51444839465987199968)
150 , (80.0, 1.55333666666666666667), (85.0, 1.59361423815800333644), (90.0, 1.62931329860268758175)
151 , (95.0, 1.6667929624488877218), (100.0, 1.7051043638797065), (150.0, 2.00483840720135025317)
152 , (200.0, 2.2437767714477898943), (250.0, 2.44730991607398293471)
153 , (500.0, 3.18080642378259967141), (750.0, 3.69441382122415693855)
154 , (1000.0, 4.09627508378940223156)]
155
156 averaged_prots_css = [(10.0, 0.5571459719175910618), (15.0, 0.64415592988436080389)
157 , (20.0, 0.7290543293760608765), (25.0, 0.80971221133003817681), (30.0, 0.88487549607521564405)
158 , (35.0, 0.95102669430186537591), (40.0, 1.01252832235203933971)
159 , (45.0, 1.07165283219713269766), (50.0, 1.12775070447538774275), (55.0, 1.17975085236934787069)
160 , (60.0, 1.22774876146801321459), (65.0, 1.27559047189925163681), (70.0, 1.31816897645581203956)

```

D Documentation of used Scripts

```
,(75.0, 1.36219593720348486155),(80.0,1.40263262155552823203),(85.0,1.43916561820885279652)
,(90.0,1.47814212345933621487),(95.0,1.51546158863488124215),(100.0,1.55145688077868273717)
,(150.0,1.85128217951763543842),(200.0,2.0930888504922246755),(250.0,
2.29532696726701722539),(500.0,3.0260910222880088812),(750.0,3.537997481110831234257)
,(1000.0,3.94827021153038988518)]
139
140 averaged_prots_tbb = [(15.0,0.71861052927636204842),(25.0,0.77655569612052062838)
,(50.0,0.90038161406728496885),(75.0,1.0147801170411686248),(100.0,1.45497190140258511296)
,(125.0, 1.56464609579453472095),(150.0,1.71933930693752053511)
,(200.0,1.86790824929631986773),(250.0, 2.19500453652563797645)
,(500.0,3.06927149103688158078),(750.0,3.61157307555717243112)
,(1000.0,4.03146533740310503085)]
141
142 averaged_prots_ude_ddnu = [(10.0,0.20119833565131964168),(15.0,0.28505516048049129335)
,(25.0,0.40856836680232170258),(50.0,0.61883485672348800747),(75.0,0.76571616710565798686)
,(100.0,0.8835730699775208),(150.0,1.06997176773019052406),(200.0,1.21809066586652664216)
,(250.0, 1.34122983366839699543),(500.0,1.79967715072384758313)
,(750.0,2.11836530525473326164),(1000.0,2.36731527432200001469)]
143
144 averaged_prots_udtau_ddnu = [(10.0,0.19492574525276047596),(15.0,0.28201581185809337478),(25.0,
0.40817563370251965879),(50.0,0.61885011290031908916),(75.0,0.76743252139565503621)
,(100.0,0.88284786884500380868),(150.0,1.06912488899652861871)
,(200.0,1.21950310807499387387),(250.0,1.34589888876664099461)
,(500.0,1.79727300007502063067),(750.0,2.11607288006302599822)
,(1000.0,2.36790644536193447894)]
145
146 averaged_prots_tbttau_bbn = [(15.0,0.38823678062886688233),(25.0,0.30369375041109534593)
,(50.0,0.30054499570446735395),(75.0,0.35656512326105225669),(100.0,0.62927213870231332153)
,(125.0, 0.72313025163993769334),(150.0,0.80844699410283679685)
,(200.0,0.9523752463539613717),(250.0,1.08599813603862372426),(500.0,1.6860962165810491582)
,(750.0,2.04688344345094422549),(1000.0, 2.30252578619465850213)]
147
148
149
150 #####
151 ##Derive lower lifetime bounds in a fully automated way for a specific operator choice. The file
152 ##location points to the directory where all spectra of this operator are stored. The for loop
153 ##runs over each tuple in the hard-coded data and each parameter set for galactic propagation.
154
155 parametersets = ["MIN", "MED", "MAX"]
156
157 if (operator == "udd"):
158     file_location = "/directory/of/photon/spectra/udd"
159     model = averaged_gammas_udd
160 if (operator == "css"):
161     file_location = "/directory/of/photon/spectra/css"
162     model = averaged_gammas_css
163 if (operator == "ude"):
164     file_location = "/directory/of/photon/spectra/ude"
165     model = averaged_gammas_ude
166 if (operator == "udtau"):
167     file_location = "/directory/of/photon/spectra/udtau"
168     model = averaged_gammas_udtau
169 if (operator == "tbb"):
170     file_location = "/directory/of/photon/spectra/tbb"
171     model = averaged_gammas_tbb
172 if (operator == "tbttau"):
173     file_location = "/directory/of/photon/spectra/tbttau"
174     model = averaged_gammas_tbttau
175
176 for (M_DM,avrgd_p) in model:
177
178     result_summary = []
179
180     kin_energy = []
181     spectrum = []
182
183     #####
184     ##Read in the photon spectrum.
185
186     with open(file_location, "r") as infile:
187         for line in infile:
```

```

188         tmp = line.split()
189         if (len(tmp) > 1 and float(tmp[1]) > 0.0):
190             kin_energy.append(float(tmp[0]))
191             spectrum.append(float(tmp[1]))
192         else:
193             continue
194
195     for dataset in parametersets: #loop over propagation models with respective Fisk
        potential
196         if (dataset == "MED"):
197             fisk_pot=0.7
198             A=1.24
199         if (dataset == "MAX"):
200             fisk_pot=0.38
201             A=1.25
202         if (dataset == "MIN"):
203             fisk_pot=0.74
204             A=1.22
205
206     for z in [0,1]: #Loop over local dark matter density to obtain the uncertainty.
207
208         if z == 0:
209             rho_dot = 0.3
210         else:
211             rho_dot = 0.4
212
213         bound_tau = 0.0
214         found_raw_bound = False
215
216         for tau_DM in lifetimes: #Start loop over raw lifetimes.
217
218             #####
219             ## Caluclation of antiproton flux and application of solar
220             ## modulation.
221
222             resulting_flux = [intermed_flux(kin_energy[i],spectrum[i],
223                                     tau_DM) for i in range(0,len(kin_energy))]
224
225             theor_flux_DM_plus_bkgrd = []
226             dm_energies = []
227
228             for i in range(0,len(kin_energy)):
229                 if (kin_energy[i]-fisk_pot > 0.0):
230                     dm_energies.append(kin_energy[i]-fisk_pot)
231                     theor_flux_DM_plus_bkgrd.append(solar_modulation
232                                                     (resulting_flux[i],kin_energy[i]-fisk_pot)+
233                                                     solar_modulation_bkgrd(kin_energy[i]-
234                                                         fisk_pot))
235
236             f_flux_with_SM = interpolate.interpld(dm_energies,
237                                     theor_flux_DM_plus_bkgrd, kind='slinear')
238
239             #####
240             ##Here we start the integration of the flux according to the
241             ##PAMELA bins.
242
243             max_bin = 0.0
244             needed_bins = 0
245
246             #####
247             ##For each bin of the PAMELA data which is fully covered by
248             ##the dark matter decay spectrum, we increase needed_bins by
249             ##one. Needed_bins is the number of rectangles in each bin
250             ##used for the integration of the DM flux.
251
252             if (max(dm_energies) > max(PAMELA_all_bin_edge)):
253                 max_bin = PAMELA_all_bin_edge[-1]
254                 needed_bins = len(PAMELA_flux)
255             else:
256                 for E in PAMELA_all_bin_edge:
257                     if (max(dm_energies) < E):

```

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```

253         max_bin = PAMELA_all_bin_edge[
254             PAMELA_all_bin_edge.index(E) - 1]
255         break
256     else:
257         needed_bins += 1
258
259     binned_DM_flux_fast = []
260
261     for i in range(0, len(PAMELA_high_bin_edge)):
262         summe = 0
263         if (PAMELA_high_bin_edge[i] <= max_bin and (min(
264             dm_energies) < PAMELA_low_bin_edge[i])):
265             samples = list(np.exp(np.linspace(np.log(
266                 PAMELA_low_bin_edge[i]), np.log(
267                 PAMELA_high_bin_edge[i]), needed_bins)))
268             for k in range(len(samples)-1):#integration via
269                 simple Riemann sums
270                 e = samples[k]
271                 e2 = samples[k+1]
272                 summe += (e2-e)*(f_flux_with_SM(e)+
273                     f_flux_with_SM(e2))/2.0
274             binned_DM_flux_fast.append(summe/(
275                 PAMELA_high_bin_edge[i]-PAMELA_low_bin_edge[
276                 i]))
277         else:
278             binned_DM_flux_fast.append(0.0)
279
280     for k in range(len(binned_DM_flux_fast)):#apply the method to
281         set limits
282         if (binned_DM_flux_fast[k] > (PAMELA_flux[k]+3*
283             PAMELA_flux_errors[k])):
284             bound_tau = lifetimes[lifetimes.index(tau_DM) - 1]
285             found_raw_bound = True
286             break
287
288     if found_raw_bound:
289         break
290
291     #####
292     ##Having found a lifetime limit with respect to the raw list of
293     ##lifetimes we defined above, we now want to refine this lifetime to
294     ##three significant figures. To this end, we repeat all steps with this
295     ##lifetimes.
296
297     if found_raw_bound:
298
299         test_here = lifetimes.index(bound_tau)
300
301         #The following lines are necessary to treat certain limiting
302         #cases.
303
304         if (int(bound_tau) in list(map(int, [1.0e25, 1.0e26, 1.0e27, 1.0e28
305             , 1.0e29, 1.0e30, 1.0e31, 1.0e32]))):
306             exponent = m.floor(m.log10(bound_tau)) - 1
307         else:
308             exponent = m.floor(m.log10(bound_tau))
309
310         final = 0.0
311
312         while (bound_tau > lifetimes[test_here+1]):
313
314             resulting_flux = [intermed_flux(kin_energy[i], spectrum[i
315                 ], bound_tau) for i in range(0, len(kin_energy))]
316
317             theor_flux_DM_plus_bkgrd = []
318             dm_energies = []
319
320             for i in range(0, len(kin_energy)):
321                 if (kin_energy[i] - fisk_pot > 0.0):
322                     dm_energies.append(kin_energy[i] -
323                         fisk_pot)

```

```

310         theor_flux_DM_plus_bkgrd.append(
311             solar_modulation(resulting_flux[i],
312                 kin_energy[i]-fisk_pot)+
313                 solar_modulation_bkgrd(kin_energy[i]
314                     -fisk_pot))
315
316     f_flux_with_SM = interpolate.interpld(dm_energies,
317         theor_flux_DM_plus_bkgrd, kind='slinear')
318
319     max_bin = 0.0
320     needed_bins = 0
321
322     if (max(dm_energies) > max(PAMELA_all_bin_edge)):
323         max_bin = PAMELA_all_bin_edge[-1]
324         needed_bins = len(PAMELA_flux)
325     else:
326         for E in PAMELA_all_bin_edge:
327             if (max(dm_energies) < E):
328                 max_bin = PAMELA_all_bin_edge[
329                     PAMELA_all_bin_edge.index(E)
330                     -1]
331                 break
332             else:
333                 needed_bins += 1
334
335     binned_DM_flux_fast = []
336
337     for i in range(0, len(PAMELA_high_bin_edge)):
338         summe = 0
339         if ((PAMELA_high_bin_edge[i] <= max_bin) and (
340             min(dm_energies) < PAMELA_low_bin_edge[i])):
341             samples = list(np.exp(np.linspace(np.log(
342                 PAMELA_low_bin_edge[i]), np.log(
343                 PAMELA_high_bin_edge[i]),
344                 needed_bins)))
345             for k in range(len(samples)-1):
346                 e = samples[k]
347                 e2 = samples[k+1]
348                 summe += (e2-e)*(f_flux_with_SM(
349                     e)+f_flux_with_SM(e2))/2.0
350             binned_DM_flux_fast.append(summe/(
351                 PAMELA_high_bin_edge[i]-
352                 PAMELA_low_bin_edge[i]))
353         else:
354             binned_DM_flux_fast.append(0.0)
355
356     for k in range(len(binned_DM_flux_fast)):
357         if (binned_DM_flux_fast[k] > (PAMELA_flux[k]+3*
358             PAMELA_flux_errors[k])):
359             final = bound_tau
360             break
361
362     if (final != 0.0 and z == 0):
363         result_summary.append(final)
364         break
365     if (final != 0.0 and z == 1):
366         result_summary.append((final-result_summary[-1])
367             )
368         break
369     else:
370         bound_tau -= 0.01*10**exponent
371
372     if (int(final) == 0 and z == 0):
373         result_summary.append(lifetimes[test_here+1])
374     if (int(final) == 0 and z == 1):
375         result_summary.append(lifetimes[test_here+1]-
376             result_summary[-1])
377
378     print(str(M_DM)+"\t\t"+str(result_summary[0])+"\t\t"+str(result_summary[1])+"\t\t"+str(
379         result_summary[2])+"\t\t"+str(result_summary[3])+"\t\t"+str(result_summary[4])+"\t\t"
380         "+str(result_summary[5]))

```

Listing D.7: Python script to derive lower bounds on the dark matter lifetime from antiproton searches using the approach we introduced in chapter 5. Moreover, this script contains our implementation of the calculation of DM antiproton fluxes and the application of solar modulation.

```

1 import math as m
2 import sys
3 from scipy import interpolate
4 import numpy as np
5 import scipy.integrate as integrate
6
7 #####
8 ##Fix the operator to be investigated and define constants.
9
10 operator = str(input("Specify the sigma operator in the minimal model (udd/css/tbb/ude/udtau/
11 tbttau):"))
12
13 m_p = 0.938272046
14 r_dot = 8.33
15 Myr = 3.15576e13
16 c_0 = 299792458
17 e = 1.6021766208e-19
18 hbar = 6.626070040e-34/(2.0*m.pi)
19 Omega_Lambda = 0.685
20 Omega_m = 0.14187/(0.673*0.673)
21
22 #####
23 ##Function that yields the J-factor connected to the averaging over the galactic DM gamma-ray
24 flux.
25
26 def J():
27     Delta_Omega = 10.3842
28     if (halo == "NFW"):
29         return 2.0856*Delta_Omega
30     if (halo == "Ein"):
31         return 2.0981*Delta_Omega
32     if (halo == "EiB"):
33         return 2.1275*Delta_Omega
34     if (halo == "Iso"):
35         return 2.1132*Delta_Omega
36     if (halo == "Bur"):
37         return 2.0576*Delta_Omega
38     if (halo == "Moo"):
39         return 2.0930*Delta_Omega
40
41 #####
42 ##Function that yields the galactic DM gamma-ray flux.
43
44 def photon_flux(T, spectrum, tau):
45     return (rho_dot*1e06*r_dot*1e03*3.086e16/(4.0*m.pi*M_DM))*J()*(1.0/tau)*spectrum
46
47 #####
48 ##Function that yields the integrand of the extragalactic DM gamma-ray flux equation using an
49 integration method of python.
50
51 def extra_galactic_gamma_integral(E, spec, max_E):
52     if (E < max_E and max_E/E > 1.0):
53         (result, error) = integrate.quad(lambda y: spec(y*E)*m.pow(y, -3.0/2.0)*m.pow
54             (1.0+Omega_Lambda/(Omega_m*y*y*y), -1.0/2.0), 1.0, max_E/E)
55         return result
56     else:
57         return 0.0
58
59 #####
60 ##Function that yields the extragalactic DM gamma-ray flux.
61
62 def extra_galactic_gamma_flux(mass_DM,tau_DM,integral_result):

```

```

61
62     return 2.3e-04*(1.0e26/tau_DM)*(1000.0/mass_DM)*integral_result
63
64 #####
65 ##List of raw DM lifetimes to be scanned over.
66
67 lifetimes = [1.0e25,2.0e25,3.0e25,4.0e25,5.0e25,6.0e25,7.0e25,8.0e25,9.0e25,1.0e26,2.0e26,3.0e26
68             ,4.0e26,5.0e26,6.0e26,7.0e26,8.0e26,9.0e26,1.0e27,2.0e27,3.0e27,4.0e27,5.0e27,6.0e27,7.0e27
69             ,8.0e27,9.0e27,1.0e28,2.0e28,3.0e28,4.0e28,5.0e28,6.0e28,7.0e28,8.0e28,9.0e28,1.0e29,2.0e29
70             ,3.0e29,4.0e29,5.0e29,6.0e29,7.0e29,8.0e29,9.0e29,1.0e30,2.0e30,3.0e30,4.0e30,5.0e30,6.0e30
71             ,7.0e30,8.0e30,9.0e30,1.0e31,2.0e31,3.0e31,4.0e31,5.0e31,6.0e31,7.0e31,8.0e31,9.0e31,1.0e32
72             ,2.0e32,3.0e32,4.0e32,5.0e32,6.0e32,7.0e32,8.0e32,9.0e32]
73
74 lifetimes.reverse()
75
76 #####
77 ##DM density profiles to be tested.
78
79 halos = ["NFW", "Ein", "Iso", "Bur", "Moo"]
80
81 #####
82 ##Hard-coded data of Fermi-LAT and the photon multiplicities of DM decays for all operators
83 ##and masses.
84
85 FERMILAT_kin_energy_min = [0.1, 0.14, 0.20, 0.28, 0.40, 0.57, 0.8, 1.1, 1.6, 2.3, 3.2, 4.5, 6.4,
86                            9.1, 13.0, 18.0, 26.0, 36.0, 51.0, 72.0, 100.0, 140.0, 200.0, 290.0, 410.0, 580.0]
87 FERMILAT_kin_energy_max = [0.14, 0.20, 0.28, 0.40, 0.57, 0.80, 1.1, 1.6, 2.3, 3.2, 4.5, 6.4,
88                            9.1, 13.0, 18.0, 26.0, 36.0, 51.0, 72.0, 100.0, 140.0, 200.0, 290.0, 410.0, 580.0, 820.0]
89 FERMILAT_flux = [2.8e-02, 1.7e-02, 1.1e-02, 6.7e-03, 4.5e-03, 3.3e-03, 1.9e-03, 1.1e-03, 6.0e
90                  -04, 3.9e-04, 2.3e-04, 1.5e-04, 9.6e-05, 7.6e-05, 4.0e-05, 2.6e-05, 1.6e-05, 1.1e-05, 6.3e
91                  -06, 3.6e-06, 1.5e-06, 9.8e-07, 4.7e-07, 3.2e-07, 7.3e-08, 2.0e-08]
92 FERMILAT_flux_errors = [0.6e-02, 0.4e-02, 0.3e-02, 2.0e-03, 1.0e-03, 0.4e-03, 0.2e-03, 0.1e-03,
93                        0.8e-04, 0.4e-04, 0.3e-04, 0.2e-04, 1.5e-05, 1.0e-05, 0.5e-05, 0.3e-05, 0.2e-05, 0.1e-05,
94                        0.8e-06, 0.5e-06, 0.3e-06, 2.0e-07, 1.4e-07, 1.1e-07, 5.7e-08, 0.0]
95 FERMILAT_all_bin_edge = [0.1, 0.14, 0.20, 0.28, 0.40, 0.57, 0.80, 1.1, 1.6, 2.3, 3.2, 4.5, 6.4,
96                          9.1, 13.0, 18.0, 26.0, 36.0, 51.0, 72.0, 100.0, 140.0, 200.0, 290.0, 410.0, 580.0, 820.0]
97
98 averaged_gammas_udd = [(10.0,7.7688256296975506745),(15.0,10.05734726904440668238)
99                       ,(20.0,11.83198209276249150698),(25.0,13.42362859524802000834)
100                      ,(30.0,14.70886880619599244676),(35.0,15.90730170774824055235)
101                      ,(40.0,17.01083073126195945354),(45.0,18.02271448517306770584)
102                      ,(50.0,18.99244476865360566903),(55.0,19.85305473209334517451)
103                      ,(60.0,20.68026612530066239521),(65.0,21.48390115593201969211)
104                      ,(70.0,22.22018365832715025302),(75.0, 22.96156315131304710296),(80.0, 23.65567)
105                      ,(85.0,24.30116150234976627391),(90.0,24.94644844549931347367)
106                      ,(95.0,25.55969288867214365207),(100.0,26.18865575965585969665)
107                      ,(150.0,31.2893805088454085141),(200.0,35.39673503987117197991)
108                      ,(250.0,38.87646045274034950835),(500.0,51.57731145392846514908)
109                      ,(750.0,60.42613679266653578386),(1000.0,67.5023545882652411862)]
110
111 averaged_gammas_css = [(60.0, 21.56298435807350818385),(65.0,22.34217289631406585495)
112                       ,(70.0,23.11660161587996671201),(75.0, 23.84205716811869231433)
113                       ,(80.0,24.5411055097886525404),(85.0,25.20341558961454878188),(90.0,25.86274737267235527141)
114                       ,(95.0,26.47272307863631301802),(100.0,27.08674691083977003624)
115                       ,(150.0,32.21081506857878746202),(200.0,36.34960954593305144292)
116                       ,(250.0,39.81804202203869148082),(500.0,52.52763998139748866097)
117                       ,(750.0,61.40260232997481108312),(1000.0,68.47131776705783593889)]
118
119 averaged_gammas_tbb = [(15.0,15.65226594823438853074),(25.0,18.99608198839941212776)
120                       ,(50.0,23.17854294796866977638),(75.0,26.21034065744717512141)
121                       ,(100.0,31.3006154464243843611),(125.0,35.96765463656097214615)
122                       ,(150.0,39.77085860081369737435),(200.0,42.21513584799196918898)
123                       ,(250.0,49.58497837442632770452),(500.0,65.52415930038692629526)
124                       ,(750.0,75.01149858379024504327),(1000.0,82.42001654259718775848)]
125
126 averaged_gammas_ude_ddnu = [(10.0,4.67680541223919778118),(15.0,6.01467978915994038867)
127                             ,(25.0,8.04130529054640069384),(50.0,11.45080394969476598726),(75.0,13.91526981295635648318)
128                             ,(100.0,15.906469344432534),(150.0,19.02353981150146162637),(200.0,21.54638561748305953542)
129                             ,(250.0,23.69318170452385953331),(500.0,31.5489125406062364177)
130                             ,(750.0,37.08525748443088312533),(1000.0,41.46090618975709220044)]
131
132
133

```

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```
94 averaged_gammas_udtau_ddnu = [(10.0,4.93240945941851455878) ,(15.0,6.36306208714926442052)
, (25.0,8.44732781826537981748) ,(50.0,11.89300309548292713954) ,(75.0,14.36120210664911125741)
, (100.0,16.32023033982514183067) ,(150.0,19.48894884758214256882)
, (200.0,21.99696068772722953746) ,(250.0,24.14411151341781774173)
, (500.0,31.95771212083322913801) ,(750.0,37.49448397463953880976)
, (1000.0,41.89187384389752967976)]
95
96 averaged_gammas_tbttau_bbnu = [(15.0,8.74635908215702575457) ,(25.0,12.06756998017345874482)
, (50.0,14.53636168384879725086) ,(75.0,16.15708559699837234804)
, (100.0,20.87482616631010960493) ,(125.0,22.54526008643952524078)
, (150.0,24.04098515488139689539) ,(200.0,26.57834607804493496255)
, (250.0,28.92871493613640530465) ,(500.0,39.79411176522054320247)
, (750.0,46.19115792810773032834) ,(1000.0,50.90136964260574002936)]
97
98 #####
99 ##Derive lower lifetime bounds in a fully automated way for a specific operator choice. The
100 ##file location points to the directory where all spectra of this operator are stored. The for
101 ##loop runs over each tuple in the hard-coded data.
102
103 if (operator == "udd"):
104     file_location = "/directory/of/photon/spectra/udd"
105     model = averaged_gammas_udd
106 if (operator == "css"):
107     file_location = "/directory/of/photon/spectra/css"
108     model = averaged_gammas_css
109 if (operator == "ude"):
110     file_location = "/directory/of/photon/spectra/ude"
111     model = averaged_gammas_ude
112 if (operator == "udtau"):
113     file_location = "/directory/of/photon/spectra/udtau"
114     model = averaged_gammas_udtau
115 if (operator == "tbb"):
116     file_location = "/directory/of/photon/spectra/tbb"
117     model = averaged_gammas_tbb
118 if (operator == "tbttau"):
119     file_location = "/directory/of/photon/spectra/tbttau"
120     model = averaged_gammas_tbttau
121
122 for (M_DM,avrgd_gamma) in model:
123
124     result_summary = []
125
126     kin_energy = []
127     spectrum = []
128
129     #####
130     ##Read in the photon spectrum.
131
132     with open(file_location, "r") as infile:
133         for line in infile:
134             tmp = line.split()
135             if (len(tmp) > 1 and float(tmp[1]) > 0.0):
136                 kin_energy.append(float(tmp[0]))
137                 spectrum.append(float(tmp[1]))
138             else:
139                 continue
140
141     #####
142     ##Calculate the extragalactic flux for all subsequent derivations to save computation
143     ##time.
144
145     extragalact_integrand = []
146     scaled_spectrum = list(map(lambda y: avrgd_gamma*y, spectrum))
147
148     f_scaled_spec = interpolate.interp1d(kin_energy, scaled_spectrum, kind='slinear')
149
150     for E in kin_energy:
151         extragalact_integrand.append(extra_galactic_gamma_integral(E, f_scaled_spec,
152                                 max(kin_energy)))
153
154     f_extragalactic = interpolate.interp1d(kin_energy, extragalact_integrand, kind='slinear'
155 )
```

```

154
155     for halo in halos: #Loop over all halos.
156
157         for z in [0,1]: #Loop over local dark matter density to obtain the uncertainty.
158
159             if z == 0:
160                 rho_dot = 0.3
161             else:
162                 rho_dot = 0.4
163
164             bound_tau = 0.0
165             found_raw_bound = False
166
167             for tau_DM in lifetimes: #Start loop over raw lifetimes.
168
169                 resulting_flux_halo = [] #Calculate gamma-ray flux
170                 resulting_flux_halo = [photon_flux(kin_energy[i], scaled_spectrum
171                 [i], tau_DM) for i in range(0, len(kin_energy))]
172
173                 f_flux_halo = interpolate.interpld(kin_energy,
174                 resulting_flux_halo, kind='slinear', fill_value=0.01)
175
176                 #####
177                 ##Here we start the integration of the flux according to the
178                 ##Fermi-LAT bins. The procedure follows the antiproton case.
179
180                 max_bin = 0.0
181                 needed_bins = 0
182
183                 for E in FERMILAT_all_bin_edge:
184                     if (max(kin_energy) < E):
185                         max_bin = FERMILAT_all_bin_edge[
186                         FERMILAT_all_bin_edge.index(E)-1]
187                         break
188                     else:
189                         needed_bins += 1
190
191                 for j in range(0, len(FERMILAT_kin_energy_max)):
192                     intensity = 0
193                     if ( FERMILAT_kin_energy_max[j] <
194                     FERMILAT_kin_energy_max[FERMILAT_kin_energy_max.
195                     index(max_bin)+1]):
196                         samples = list(np.exp(np.linspace(np.log(
197                         FERMILAT_kin_energy_min[j]), np.log(
198                         FERMILAT_kin_energy_max[j], needed_bins)))
199                         for i in range(len(samples)-1): #integration via
200                         simple Riemann sums
201                             e = samples[i]
202                             e2 = samples[i+1]
203                             intensity += (e2-e)*(f_flux_halo(e)+
204                             extra_galactic_gamma_flux(M_DM,
205                             tau_DM, f_extragalactic(e))+
206                             f_flux_halo(e2)+
207                             extra_galactic_gamma_flux(M_DM,
208                             tau_DM, f_extragalactic(e2)))/2.0
209
210                         #Here we set our limits concerning the lifetime.
211                         if (((FERMILAT_flux[j]+3*FERMILAT_flux_errors[j]
212                         )-intensity) < 0.0):
213                             bound_tau = lifetimes[lifetimes.index(
214                             tau_DM)-1]
215                             found_raw_bound = True
216                             break
217
218                 if found_raw_bound:
219                     break
220
221                 #####
222                 ##Having found a lifetime limit with respect to the raw list of
223                 ##lifetimes we defined above, we now want to refine this lifetime to
224                 ##three significant figures. To this end, we repeat all steps with this
225                 ##lifetimes.

```

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```

211         if found_raw_bound:
212
213             test_here = lifetimes.index(bound_tau)
214
215             if (int(bound_tau) in list(map(int, [1.0e25, 1.0e26, 1.0e27, 1.0e28
216                 , 1.0e29, 1.0e30, 1.0e31, 1.0e32]))):
217                 exponent = m.floor(m.log10(bound_tau))-1
218             else:
219                 exponent = m.floor(m.log10(bound_tau))
220
221             final = 0.0
222
223             while (bound_tau > lifetimes[test_here+1]):
224
225                 resulting_flux_halo = []
226                 resulting_flux_halo = [photon_flux(kin_energy[i],
227                     scaled_spectrum[i], bound_tau) for i in range(0, len(
228                         kin_energy))]
229
230                 f_flux_halo = interpolate.interpld(kin_energy,
231                     resulting_flux_halo, kind='slinear', fill_value
232                         =0.01)
233
234                 max_bin = 0.0
235                 needed_bins = 0
236
237                 for E in FERMILAT_all_bin_edge:
238                     if (max(kin_energy) < E):
239                         max_bin = FERMILAT_all_bin_edge[
240                             FERMILAT_all_bin_edge.index(E)-1]
241                         break
242                     else:
243                         needed_bins += 1
244
245                 for k in range(0, len(FERMILAT_kin_energy_max)):
246                     intensity = 0
247                     if ( FERMILAT_kin_energy_max[k] <
248                         FERMILAT_kin_energy_max[
249                             FERMILAT_kin_energy_max.index(max_bin)+1]):
250                         samples = list(np.exp(np.linspace(np.log
251                             (FERMILAT_kin_energy_min[k]), np.log
252                             (FERMILAT_kin_energy_max[k]),
253                             needed_bins)))
254                         for i in range(len(samples)-1):
255                             e = samples[i]
256                             e2 = samples[i+1]
257                             intensity += (e2-e)*(f_flux_halo
258                                 (e)+
259                                 extra_galactic_gamma_flux(
260                                     M_DM, bound_tau,
261                                     f_extragalactic(e))+
262                                     f_flux_halo(e2)+
263                                     extra_galactic_gamma_flux(
264                                         M_DM, bound_tau,
265                                         f_extragalactic(e2)))/2.0
266                             if (((FERMILAT_flux[k]+3*
267                                 FERMILAT_flux_errors[k])-intensity)
268                                 < 0.0):
269                                 final = bound_tau
270                                 break
271
272                     if (final > 1.0 and z == 0):
273                         result_summary.append(final)
274                         break
275                     if (final > 1.0 and z == 1):
276                         result_summary.append((final-result_summary[-1])
277                             )
278                         break
279                     else:
280                         bound_tau -= 0.01*10**exponent
281
282             if (int(final) == 0 and z == 0):

```

```

261         result_summary.append(lifetimes[test_here+1])
262         if (int(final) == 0 and z == 1):
263             result_summary.append(lifetimes[test_here+1]-
264                                   result_summary[-1])
265
266     print (str(M_DM)+"\t\t"+str(result_summary[0])+"\t\t"+str(result_summary[1])+"\t\t"+str(
267           result_summary[2])+"\t\t"+str(result_summary[3])+"\t\t"+str(result_summary[4])+"\t\t"
268         "+str(result_summary[5])+"\t\t"+str(result_summary[6])+"\t\t"+str(result_summary[7])
269         "+\t\t"+str(result_summary[8])+"\t\t"+str(result_summary[9]))

```

Listing D.8: Python script to derive lower bounds on the dark matter lifetime from gamma-ray searches using the approach we introduced in chapter 5. Moreover, this scripts includes the calculation of the galactic DM gamma-ray flux as well as the extragalactic component.

```

1  import math as m
2  import sys
3  import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
4  from scipy import interpolate
5  import numpy as np
6  import scipy.integrate as integrate
7
8  #####
9  ##Fix the operator to be investigated, define constants, provide the fit functions of Cirelli et
10 ##al. for DM antideuteron flux.
11
12 operator = str(input("Specify the sigma operator in the minimal model (udd/css/tbb/ude/udtau/
13                   tbtau):"))
14
15 m_p = 0.938272046
16 m_n = 0.9395654133
17 r_dot = 8.33
18 rho_dot = 0.3
19 Myr = 3.15576e13
20 c_0 = 299792458
21 e = 1.6021766208e-19
22 hbar = 6.626070040e-34/(2.0*m.pi)
23 p_0 = 0.141
24 m_d = 1.8756128591598757
25 fisk_pot = 0.5
26 dataset = "MED"
27
28 def v_p(T):
29     return m.pow((1.0-m_d**2/(T+m_d)**2),0.5)*c_0
30
31 def R_K(K):
32     if (halo == "NFW"):
33         if (dataset == "MIN"):
34             a_0 = 1.0097
35             a_1 = 0.4282
36             a_2 = -0.3575
37             a_3 = -0.0378
38             a_4 = 0.0297
39             a_5 = -0.0033
40         if (dataset == "MED"):
41             a_0 = 1.7536
42             a_1 = 0.2154
43             a_2 = -0.2937
44             a_3 = 0.0116
45             a_4 = 0.0098
46             a_5 = -0.0013
47         if (dataset == "MAX"):
48             a_0 = 2.3010
49             a_1 = -0.1861
50             a_2 = -0.0833
51             a_3 = 0.0155
52             a_4 = -0.0026
53             a_5 = 0.0003
54
55 #####

```

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```
54 ##The values of all other density profile are likewise implemented in this function. In order to
55 ##reduce the length of this script, we only provide one example.
56     return m.pow(10.0, a_0+a_1*m.log10(K)+a_2*m.log10(K)**2+a_3*m.log10(K)**3+a_4*m.log10(K)
57         **4+a_5*m.log10(K)**5)*Myr
58 #####
59 ##Isotropic coalescence model implementation with antideuteron kinetic energy per nucleon.
60
61 def deuteron_spectrum(prot_spec, neut_spec, T):
62     return p_0*p_0*p_0*m_d/(6.0*m_p*m_n*4.0)*1.0/m.sqrt(T*T+2.0*m_d*T/2.0)*avgrd_p*prot_spec
63         *avgrd_n*neut_spec
64 #####
65 ##Function yielding antideuteron flux and solar modulated flux.
66
67 def intermed_flux(T, spectrum, tau):
68     return (v_p(2.0*T)/(4.0*m.pi))*((rho_dot*1e06/M_DM)*R_K(T)*(1.0/tau)*spectrum)
69
70 def solar_modulation(flux, T):
71     return flux*(2.0*m_d*2*T+4*T*T)/(2*m_d*(T+fisk_pot/2.0)+4*(T+fisk_pot)*(T+fisk_pot
72         /2.0))
73 #####
74 ##List of raw DM lifetimes to be scanned over as well as a list of density profiles.
75
76 lifetimes = [1.0e23, 2.0e23, 3.0e23, 4.0e23, 5.0e23, 6.0e23, 7.0e23, 8.0e23, 9.0e23, 1.0e24, 2.0e24, 3.0e24
77     , 4.0e24, 5.0e24, 6.0e24, 7.0e24, 8.0e24, 9.0e24, 1.0e25, 2.0e25, 3.0e25, 4.0e25, 5.0e25, 6.0e25, 7.0e25
78     , 8.0e25, 9.0e25, 1.0e26, 2.0e26, 3.0e26, 4.0e26, 5.0e26, 6.0e26, 7.0e26, 8.0e26, 9.0e26, 1.0e27]
79
80 lifetimes.reverse()
81
82 halos = ["NFW", "Ein", "Bur"]
83 #####
84 ##Hard-coded data of Ibarra et al. determining the antideuteron background for MED and a Fisk
85 ##potential of 0.5 GV as well as antiproton and antineutron multiplicities for each operator and
86 ##mass.
87
88 background_energy =
89     [0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5, 0.6, 0.7, 0.8, 0.9, 0.91, 1.0, 1.1, 2.0, 3.0, 4.0, 5.0, 6.0, 7.0, 8.0,
90     9.0, 10.0, 20.0, 30.0, 40.0, 50.0, 60.0, 70.0, 80.0, 90.0, 100.0]
91
92 background_flux = [5.0e-09, 9.0e-09, 1.3e-08, 1.7e-08, 2.0e-08, 2.6e-08, 3.0e-08, 3.6e-08, 4.0e-08, 4.09e
93     -08, 4.8e-08, 5.4e-08, 8.9e-08, 1.1e-07, 1.15e-07, 1.05e-07, 9.4e-08, 8.0e-08, 7.0e-08, 6.05e-08, 5.0e
94     -08, 1.3e-08, 5.0e-09, 2.73e-09, 1.7e-09, 1.0e-09, 7.1e-10, 5.0e-10, 3.2e-10, 2.4e-10]
95
96 bkgrd_flux_antid = interpolate.interp1d(background_energy, background_flux, kind='slinear')
97
98 averaged_prots_and_neuts_udd = [(10.0, 0.30526681393184123147, 0.3204406840884146765)
99     , (15.0, 0.36295743669925133461, 0.37778189270518635659)
100     , (20.0, 0.41280955219401174641, 0.42987686690037223378) , (25.0, 0.46129613974358333042,
101     0.47753352775512858351) , (30.0, 0.49822528001600686961, 0.51693330887839364394)
102     , (35.0, 0.53316371201761115373, 0.55346406891030986291) , (40.0,
103     0.56616938963534870536, 0.58734100961758930768)
104     , (45.0, 0.59761914685227249047, 0.61723696001000270907)
105     , (50.0, 0.62697464483126690296, 0.6481885276659284938)
106     , (55.0, 0.65270116452149549076, 0.67456148031404138575)
107     , (60.0, 0.67751899852847382309, 0.69778479033878451104)
108     , (65.0, 0.7008134876799239661, 0.72243562755061631644)
109     , (70.0, 0.72458128735900492701, 0.7451125876399529808)
110     , (75.0, 0.74589493501599170232, 0.76837586670357487085) , (80.0, 0.7659566666666666667, 0.78722)
111     , (85.0, 0.78566042313300502467, 0.8070171599216661206)
112     , (90.0, 0.80295881592340917219, 0.82632196959276108634) , (95.0,
113     0.82052931687736804592, 0.84380400395143239424)
114     , (100.0, 0.8420635375475194376, 0.86298214445506855568)
115     , (150.0, 0.99091329624304557104, 1.01458898543476901919)
116     , (200.0, 1.1114154828675236864, 1.13319521996034137425) , (250.0,
117     1.21311419039902369735, 1.23393939621282597605)
118     , (500.0, 1.57910829593958629747, 1.60072370581153551494)
119     , (750.0, 1.84013064576334453154, 1.8588391190742814483)
120     , (1000.0, 2.04007501899639941037, 2.0644622340839707979) ]
```

```

96 averaged_prot_and_neuts_css = [(10.0,0.3039612219118401589
97 ,0.25310373728675402038),(15.0, 0.34046876781545736592,0.30394220440593138461)
,(20.0,0.37955192576426855456,0.34883494199083552696),(25.0,
0.41982306659566329401,0.39013040619429422898)
,(30.0,0.45528957335900096254,0.42806480243009112842)
,(35.0,0.4894342868143599693,0.46188867748573028679),(40.0,
0.52074343403792653006,0.49421363592512730392)
,(45.0,0.54886771567050936516,0.52321473059588249949)
,(50.0,0.57783359128675836307,0.55068722292926742061)
,(55.0,0.60394057446742726401,0.57638789340394015285)
,(60.0,0.62647810694787547747,0.60195880251496587485)
,(65.0,0.65120435374697621499,0.62378954204602949654)
,(70.0,0.67295704191399784427,0.64810467290867606551),(75.0,
0.69436365155697403606,0.66826492818942465281)
,(80.0,0.71342404743363799063,0.68719483038922360206)
,(85.0,0.73185691410271074002,0.70764611689351481185)
,(90.0,0.75310782283404798937,0.72622014270205861039)
,(95.0,0.77218775354364530139,0.74474856424696543057)
,(100.0,0.78778335292366678214,0.76357701540846607181)
,(150.0,0.93782960953226391268,0.91366637076305622585)
,(200.0,1.05929263175793098102,1.03280726847186555277),(250.0,
1.15919103949911610195,1.13418810150700242291)
,(500.0,1.5270647536973296825,1.49961481678583384119)
,(750.0,1.78392638004497885362,1.75646241842974292531)
,(1000.0,1.9867252977503308337,1.96147717247463608293)]

98
99 averaged_prot_and_neuts_tbb = [(15.0,0.42124843213074359678,0.29699154649428145201)
,(25.0,0.45724480562716610042,0.31789903197719085586)
,(50.0,0.51436111697981247678,0.38718554890975718147)
,(75.0,0.56171830608244855744,0.45282862268644138134)
,(100.0,0.79943704303054652252,0.65661304705096779883),(125.0,
0.8419981907647872526,0.72314644663770267694)
,(150.0,0.90522654306205530549,0.81075140942539279235)
,(200.0,0.98359779686577929316,0.8830994688872860796),(250.0,
1.12855847009454026658,1.06444326042827137064)
,(500.0,1.56825788308018526755,1.5137310925124770635)
,(750.0,1.83352892776719210116,1.7818963277325480686)
,(1000.0,2.04480309300837811764,1.9855648385495887066)]

100
101 averaged_prot_and_neuts_ude_ddnu = [(10.0,0.08803200086507479101,0.11363338314415574107)
,(15.0,0.1294981046398815775,0.15580760344465448435)
,(25.0,0.19108283574621389019,0.21859676262592567883)
,(50.0,0.29599255262367815325,0.32404739466924642226)
,(75.0,0.37034891474677424732,0.39800745173873903911)
,(100.0,0.42766275460641146134,0.45625686124296105578)
,(150.0,0.52140176095344551222,0.55053176192869663938)
,(200.0,0.59598492236141324732,0.6221119945990548346),(250.0,
0.65693794320920974985,0.68648605735089667037)
,(500.0,0.88485146682604901007,0.91393666052311085659)
,(750.0,1.04466960958407323112,1.07137595978290773579)
,(1000.0,1.16986602668972486518,1.19972800280392171266)]

102
103 averaged_prot_and_neuts_udtau_ddnu = [(10.0,0.08192721476524592151,0.11337294235788580654)
,(15.0,0.1294981046398815775,0.15580760344465448435),(25.0,
0.18925305628720134752,0.21837648710689997399)
,(50.0,0.29498455664991980063,0.32351167199119795326),(75.0,
0.36790546233976890911,0.39789250692535364068)
,(100.0,0.42795266059675470729,0.45620889256119446411)
,(150.0,0.52147286469685961088,0.55032115322515540486),(200.0,
0.59548391452418697459,0.62310152378189965144)
,(250.0,0.65792879004590964102,0.68787257824143070045)
,(500.0,0.88496961664457725875,0.91295106154192402911)
,(750.0,1.04330348768867157703,1.07130878987582377731)
,(1000.0,1.17039762421880236538,1.19835016861963991128)]

104
105 averaged_prot_and_neuts_tbttau_bbnub = [(15.0,0.21555085317762351042,0.2071095502471500909)
,(25.0,0.16404638124682524254,0.138322222988869316008)
,(50.0,0.16487711955355226443,0.13492165700794161837)
,(75.0,0.19414941803437439476,0.16462317491456382254)
,(100.0,0.32969260333131887906,0.29911590355064541757)
,(125.0,0.37703876675191254432,0.34613347748301485034)
,(150.0,0.4185995985847006973,0.38692089635622504087)

```

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```
,(200.0,0.49143470638684290183,0.46001444102512360004)
,(250.0,0.55840154915940498196,0.53024649544781345794)
,(500.0,0.85526553383851906277,0.82259450439287426604)
,(750.0,1.04404124514741748806,1.0082944886207842062)
,(1000.0,1.16958190796093060694,1.13365014008637369782) ]
106
107 #####
108 ##Derive lower lifetime bounds in a fully automated way for a specific operator choice. The file
109 ##location points to the directory where all spectra of this operator are stored. The for loop
110 ##runs over each tuple in the hard-coded data and each parameter set for galactic propagation.
111
112 if (operator == "udd"):
113     file_location = "/directory/of/photon/spectra/udd"
114     model = averaged_gammas_udd
115 if (operator == "css"):
116     file_location = "/directory/of/photon/spectra/css"
117     model = averaged_gammas_css
118 if (operator == "ude"):
119     file_location = "/directory/of/photon/spectra/ude"
120     model = averaged_gammas_ude
121 if (operator == "udtau"):
122     file_location = "/directory/of/photon/spectra/udtau"
123     model = averaged_gammas_udtau
124 if (operator == "tbb"):
125     file_location = "/directory/of/photon/spectra/tbb"
126     model = averaged_gammas_tbb
127 if (operator == "tbtau"):
128     file_location = "/directory/of/photon/spectra/tbtau"
129     model = averaged_gammas_tbtau
130
131
132 for (M_DM,avgrd_p,avgrd_n) in model:
133
134     result_summary = []
135
136     resulting_spec_p = []
137     kin_energy_p = []
138
139     resulting_spec_n = []
140     kin_energy_n = []
141
142     kin_energy_deut = list(np.exp(np.linspace(np.log(0.001), np.log(M_DM/2.0), 150)))
143
144     #####
145     ##Read in the antiproton spectrum and antineutron spectrum.
146
147     with open(file_location, "r") as infile:
148         for line in infile:
149             tmp = line.split()
150             if (len(tmp) > 1 and float(tmp[1]) > 0.0):
151                 kin_energy_p.append(float(tmp[0]))
152                 resulting_spec_p.append(float(tmp[1]))
153             else:
154                 continue
155
156     with open(file_location, "r") as infile:
157         for line in infile:
158             tmp = line.split()
159             if (len(tmp) > 1 and float(tmp[1]) > 0.0):
160                 kin_energy_n.append(float(tmp[0]))
161                 resulting_spec_n.append(float(tmp[1]))
162             else:
163                 continue
164
165
166     pbar_spec = interpolate.interpld(kin_energy_p,resulting_spec_p, kind='slinear')
167     nbar_spec = interpolate.interpld(kin_energy_n,resulting_spec_n, kind='slinear')
168
169     #####
170     ##Find the antideuteron spectrum.
171
172     dbar_spec = []
```

```

173     final_deut_energy = []
174
175     for energy in kin_energy_deut:
176         if ((energy/2.0 > (min(kin_energy_n) and min(kin_energy_p))) and (energy/2.0 < (
177             max(kin_energy_n) and max(kin_energy_p)))):
178             dbar_spec.append(deuteron_spectrum(pbar_spec(energy/2.0), nbar_spec(
179                 energy/2.0), energy))
180             final_deut_energy.append(energy)
181
182     deut_spec = interpolate.interp1d(final_deut_energy, dbar_spec, kind='slinear')
183
184     for halo in halos: #Loop over density profiles
185
186         for z in [0,1]: #Loop over local DM densities
187
188             if z == 0:
189                 rho_dot = 0.3
190             else:
191                 rho_dot = 0.4
192
193             bound_tau = 0.0
194             found_raw_bound = False
195
196             for tau_DM in lifetimes: #Loop over raw lifetimes
197
198                 #####
199                 ##Caluclation of antideuteron flux and application of solar
200                 ##modulation.
201
202                 resulting_flux_noSM = [intermed_flux(final_deut_energy[i],
203                     deut_spec(final_deut_energy[i]), tau_DM) for i in range(0,
204                         len(final_deut_energy))]
205
206                 f_noSM = interpolate.interp1d(final_deut_energy,
207                     resulting_flux_noSM, kind='slinear')
208
209                 theor_flux_DM_plus_bkgrd = []
210
211                 for energy in samples: #Sum of background and DM antideuteron
212                     flux
213                     theor_flux_DM_plus_bkgrd.append(solar_modulation(f_noSM(
214                         energy+fisk_pot/2.0), energy)+bkgrd_flux_antid(energy
215                         ))
216
217                 f_flux_with_SM = interpolate.interp1d(samples,
218                     theor_flux_DM_plus_bkgrd, kind='slinear')
219
220                 #####
221                 ##Integration of flux to find its prediction for the bin with
222                 ##the upper limit of BESS.
223
224                 (result, error) = integrate.quad(lambda y: f_flux_with_SM(y),
225                     0.17, 1.15)
226                 if (result/(1.15-0.17) > 1.9e-04): #Apply limit
227                     bound_tau = lifetimes[lifetimes.index(tau_DM)-1]
228                     found_raw_bound = True
229
230                 if found_raw_bound:
231                     break
232
233                 #####
234                 ##Having found a lifetime limit with respect to the raw list of
235                 ##lifetimes we defined above, wenow want to refine this lifetime
236                 ##to three significant figures. To this end, we repeat all steps
237                 ##with this lifetimes.
238
239                 if found_raw_bound:
240
241                     test_here = lifetimes.index(bound_tau)
242
243                     if (int(bound_tau) in list(map(int, [1.0e25, 1.0e26, 1.0e27, 1.0e28,
244                         1.0e29, 1.0e30, 1.0e31, 1.0e32]))):

```

```

234         exponent = m.floor(m.log10(bound_tau))-1
235     else:
236         exponent = m.floor(m.log10(bound_tau))
237
238     final = 0.0
239
240     while (bound_tau > lifetimes[test_here+1]):
241
242         resulting_flux_noSM = [intermed_flux(final_deut_energy[i]
243         ],deut_spec(final_deut_energy[i]), bound_tau) for i
244         in range(0,len(final_deut_energy))]
245
246         f_noSM = interpolate.interp1d(final_deut_energy,
247         resulting_flux_noSM, kind='slinear', fill_value
248         =0.01)
249
250         theor_flux_DM_plus_bkgrd = []
251
252         for energy in samples:
253             theor_flux_DM_plus_bkgrd.append(solar_modulation
254             (f_noSM(energy+fisk_pot/2.0),energy)+
255             bkgrd_flux_antid(energy))
256
257         f_flux_with_SM = interpolate.interp1d(samples,
258         theor_flux_DM_plus_bkgrd, kind='slinear')
259
260         (result, error) = integrate.quad(lambda y:
261         f_flux_with_SM(y), 0.17, 1.15)
262         if (result/(1.15-0.17) > 1.9e-04):
263             final = bound_tau
264
265         if (final > 1.0 and z == 0):
266             result_summary.append(final)
267             break
268         if (final > 1.0 and z == 1):
269             result_summary.append((final-result_summary[-1])
270             )
271             break
272         else:
273             bound_tau -= 0.01*10**exponent
274
275         if (int(final) == 0 and z == 0):
276             result_summary.append(lifetimes[test_here+1])
277         if (int(final) == 0 and z == 1):
278             result_summary.append(lifetimes[test_here+1]-
279             result_summary[-1])
280
281     print(str(M_DM)+"\t\t"+str(result_summary[0])+"\t\t"+str(result_summary[1])+"\t\t"+str(
282     result_summary[2])+"\t\t"+str(result_summary[3])+"\t\t"+str(result_summary[4])+"\t\t"
283     "+str(result_summary[5]))

```

Listing D.9: Python script to derive lower bounds on the dark matter lifetime from antideuteron searches using the approach we introduced in chapter 5. Moreover, this script contains our implementation of the calculation of antideuteron spectra with the isotropic coalescence model, DM antideuteron fluxes and the application of solar modulation.

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Erklärung nach §18(8) der Prüfungsordnung für den Bachelor-Studiengang Physik und den Master-Studiengang Physik an der Universität Göttingen:

Hiermit erkläre ich, dass ich diese Abschlussarbeit selbständig verfasst habe, keine anderen als die angegebenen Quellen und Hilfsmittel benutzt habe und alle Stellen, die wörtlich oder sinngemäß aus veröffentlichten Schriften entnommen wurden, als solche kenntlich gemacht habe.

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Göttingen, den 13. April 2016

(Christopher Eckner)